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Pest management practices in greenhouses producing vegetables in Egypt

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Abstract:

Greenhouse vegetable growers in 14 of the 26 Governorates in Egypt were surveyed from May through July 2016. The Governorates surveyed were selected because they were areas of intensive greenhouse vegetable production. All surveys were conducted with face-to-face interviews of the head grower or owner of the operation using a standard set of questions focused on the growers' experience with insect and disease pests, crop scouting and pesticide application practices. In general greenhouse operators surveyed were growing tomatoes, *Solanum lycopersicum* L. (Solanales: Solanaceae) and/or cucumbers, *Cucumis sativus* L. (Violales: Cucurbitaceae). A total of 123 growers were surveyed with between 2 - 16 growers from each governorate. Across all Governorates, 43% of growers report applying pesticides more than once per week. In five Governorates (32 sites), 100% of growers report applying pesticides more than once per week. In five other Governorates (42 sites), 100% of growers apply pesticides once per week. In 5% of sites, pesticides are applied once a month or less. The data gained will serve as the basis for further work designed to implement IPM practices and reduce use of chemical pesticides. Grower interviews clearly indicated that insecticide resistance was prevalent, and growers desperately need alternative management strategies.

Introduction

Vegetables are essential components of a healthy diet for humans throughout the world. Annual per capita consumption of vegetables averaged approximately 69.28 kg in Africa, 175.75 kg in Asia and 116.51 kg in the US (FAO, 2020). As of 2009 vegetable crops occupied 10.6% of arable land in Egypt (El-Nahrawy, 2011). This is very intensive agriculture as only 3% of Egypt's land is arable (FAO, 2016). In 2019 Egypt exported

\$1.1 billion in vegetable (UN ComTrade Database, 2019). The Russian Federation was Egypt's top partner for vegetable exports, followed by Saudi Arabia and Italy. Vegetable exports are a promising means of developing the Egyptian national economy and enhancing food security in-country. In the US, vegetable and fruit exports were estimated at \$6 billion in 2015, while imports exceeded \$18 billion, resulting in trade imbalance of \$11 billion. Whereas the US in the

early 1970s was a net exporter of fruits and vegetables, it has now become a major importer (Johnson, 2016). Efforts are underway to increase vegetable production in both countries, which would significantly bolster agricultural revenues and contribute to stabilizing food security. Insect pests are a major factor reducing yields of vegetables (Kisha, 1984), and chemical insecticides remain the prominent means of control, despite their known negative impacts on the environment and human health. In fact, pesticides remain the primary means of pest management- 30% of all insecticides used worldwide are applied to vegetable crops for insect control (Shelton *et al.*, 2008). As of 2017 in Egypt, highly toxic pesticide residues were still detectable in the environment (Mansour *et al.*, 2017). While there is a shift toward biopesticide use in field crops, the use of indoor pesticides is widespread and generally inadequately managed (Mansour, 2008).

Materials and methods

To start implementing integrated pest management (IPM) strategies in greenhouses in Egypt, it was first necessary to determine what the insect pests were and how they are managed. Vegetable pests represent a broad range of plant types, production systems and pest problems. However, from a global perspective, two insect groups, whiteflies (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) and thrips (Thysanoptera: Thripidae), remain the more serious persistent and challenging problems facing farmers. Both feed by piercing the plant and sucking the sap from plant cells. They reduce crop yields, quality and shelf life by their direct feeding damage and also transmit viruses which can result in complete plant mortality. In the US, vegetable production areas yield losses ranging from 20 to 80% are often attributed to insect-borne viruses (Shelton *et al.*, 2008). While a large

number of different whitefly and thrips species are known to attack vegetable crops, only relatively few represent a serious threat. For example, silverleaf whitefly, *Bemisia tabaci* (Gennadius), feeds on a wide variety of vegetables, including beans (Fabales: Fabaceae), tomatoes, *Solanum lycopersicum* L. (Solanales: Solanaceae), eggplant (Solanales: Solanaceae), cucumber, *Cucumis sativus* L. (Violales: Cucurbitaceae) and squash (Cucurbitales: Cucurbitaceae).

This insect can easily be found in high densities across a large diversity of plants in many production landscapes (Macfadyen *et al.*, 2020). Several whitefly biotypes exist and are known to rapidly gain resistance to insecticides. Both adults and nymphs feed on the lower surfaces of leaves by sucking sap with their piercing-sucking mouthparts. Chlorotic spots then appear around feeding sites on the upper surfaces of the leaves. Whiteflies produce honeydew upon which sooty mold often grows that reduces light penetration, yield and quality of the crop. On squash whiteflies induce a condition known as silverleaf, *Chondrostereum purpureum* (Pers.) Pouzar (Agaricales: Cyphellaceae) in which the foliage becomes highly reflective and the fruit is pale in color. On tomatoes the pest causes irregular ripening of the fruit. Whiteflies are also vectors of geminiviruses (Geplafuvirales: Geminiviridae), such as the detrimental tomato yellow leaf curl virus (He *et al.*, 2020). Silverleaf whitefly is difficult to control with insecticides. Repeated applications make the situation worse by selecting strains of whitefly that are resistant to pesticides. Damage by the silverleaf whitefly in the US since 1991 is estimated to exceed \$1 billion (Paine, 2016). Two common species of thrips plague vegetable production, western flower thrips, *Frankliniella*

occidentalis Pergande, which has a broad host range including cucumber, pepper (Solanales: Solanaceae) and beans, *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. (Fabales: Fabaceae), and onion thrips, *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman, a pest of onion, *Allium cepa* L. (Asparagales: Amaryllidaceae), garlic, *Allium sativum* L. (Asparagales: Amaryllidaceae) and peppers. Both are major insect pests worldwide and transmit several deadly viruses. In general, thrips have a relatively rapid reproduction rate allowing populations to increase quickly when conditions are favorable. For this reason, as for whiteflies, pesticide resistance develops rapidly and currently few conventional pesticides are effective against western flower thrips in the US. In 2016, a survey of greenhouse vegetable growers in Egypt was conducted to obtain current information on the pest and disease challenges they face, the IPM practices they use, and the

common pesticides they apply. A copy of the survey is included in Appendix 1. Greenhouses were visited and owners or operators were met face to face and asked each of the questions in the survey. Answers were recorded and tabulated at a later date.

Results and discussion

Greenhouse vegetable growers in 14 of the 26 Governorates in Egypt were surveyed from May through July 2016 (Table 1 and Figure 1). The Governorates surveyed were selected because they were areas of intensive greenhouse vegetable production. All surveys were conducted with face-to-face interviews of the head grower or owner of the operation using a standard set of questions focused on the growers' experience with insect and disease pests, crop scouting and pesticide application practices (See grower survey in Appendix 1 and Table 2).

Table (1): Where growers were surveyed.

Region	Governorate	Area	# sites surveyed
Rashid	Beheira	North	8
Gharbia	Gharbia	Central	9
Beni Suef	Beni Suef	Central	7
Nubaria	Beheira	North	10
Dakahlia	Dakahlia	North	16
Sharqyia	Al Sharqia	North	8
Ismailia	Ismailia	North	4
Damietta	Damietta	North	8
Suez	Suez	Central	7
Luxor	Luxor	South	15
Qalyubia	Qalyubia	Central	4
Menoufia	Menoufia	Central	6
Faiyoun	Faiyoun	Central	2
Kafr El-Sheikh	Kafr El-Sheikh	North	9
Alexandria	Alexandria	North	10

Figure (1): Map of Egyptian Governorates .

Complete map of Egypt showing individual Governorates , surrounding countries and water bodies. N = northern area, C = central area, S = southern area.

Table (2): Frequency of applying pesticides over the growing season.

	All	A.	B.	G.	Be.	D.	Al.	I.	D.	S.	L.	Q.	M.	F.	K.
1-2 times	2.4	0	16.7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
1 time/wk	48.8	0	22.2	0	0	75	100	100	100	100	100	0	16.7	0	11.1
1 time/mo	2.4	0	5.6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	22.2
Over 1 time/wk	43.1	100	38.9	100	100	25	0	0	0	0	0	100	83.3	100	66.7

Values represent percent of survey responses. A: Alexandria B. Beheira G. Gharbia Be. Beni Suf D. Dakahlia Al. Al Sharqia I. Ismailia D. Damietta S. Suez L. Luxor Q. Qalyubia M. Menoufia F. Faiyoun K. Kafr El-Sheikh.

1. Vegetables grown:

Of all growers surveyed, 41-43% grow cucumbers and/or tomatoes, 36% grow peppers and 16% grow eggplant (Table S1). In Luxor and Faiyoun 100% of those surveyed grow tomatoes. Between 50-62% of the growers in Al Sharqia, Ismailia and Damietta grow tomatoes. Peppers are a common crop in Beheira (55%), Beni Suf (57%), Al Sharqia (62%), Menoufia (50%), Faiyoun (100%) and Kafr El-Sheikh (88%). Between 50-100% of the growers in Alexandria, Beheira, Al Sharqia, Damietta, Qalyubia, Menoufia, Faiyoun and Kafr El-Sheikh grow cucumbers. Crops

grown less commonly include melon (Cucurbitales: Cucurbitaceae), strawberry, *Fragaria x ananassa* Duschene (Rosales: Rosaceae), onion, wheat (Poales: Poaceae), cabbage, *Brassica oleracea* L. (Brassicales: Brassicaceae), cilantro, *Coriandrum sativum* L. (Apiales: Apiaceae), garlic, lettuce, *Lactuca sativa* L. (Asterales: Asteraceae) and dill, *Anethum graveolens* L. (Apiales: Apiaceae).

2. Insect pests:

All regions reported multiple common arthropod pests (Table S2). Of those surveyed in Alexandria, Gharbia, Beni Suf, Al Sharqia, Damietta, Suez and Menoufia, 100% of growers reported whiteflies and thrips as

important pests. In all Governorates , mites were the most common pest, with 93% of regions reporting problems with the arthropod. Common arthropod pests across all regions include whiteflies (91%), aphids (Hemiptera: Aphidoidea) (78%) and thrips (78%). All Governorates reported whiteflies, aphids, and spider mites (Trombidiformes: Tetranychidae) as common arthropod pests. *Tuta absoluta* (Meyrick) (Lepidoptera: Gelechiidae) (40.7%) and nematodes (39%) were fairly common among the regions. Other arthropod pests reported include jassid bug, *Amrasca biguttula* (Ishida) (Hemiptera: Cicadellidae), mealybugs (Hemiptera: Pseudococcidae) and leaf miners.

3. Diseases encountered:

The most important disease reported throughout all the regions was powdery mildew (Erysiphales: Erysiphaceae), with 80% of growers surveyed reporting it a problem (Table S3). Every grower surveyed in Gharbia, Dakahlia, Al Sharqia, Ismailia, Suez, Qalyubia, Menoufia, Faiyoum and Kafr El-Sheikh reported powdery mildew as a common disease in their crops. Other diseases reported include downy mildew (Erysiphales: Erysiphaceae), which was the most common in Qalyubia (100%) and Al Sharqia (75%) but relatively mild across all regions (29%) and grey mold (Helotiales: Sclerotiniaceae), which was reported by only 4% of growers surveyed. Growers also report problems with blight, white mold *Sclerotinia sclerotiorum* (Lib.) de Bary (Helotiales: Sclerotiniaceae), fusarium wilt, *Fusarium oxysporum* Schlecht (Hypocreales: Nectriaceae), stem rot and rust (Puccinales).

4. Scouting:

All growers surveyed report scouting their fields for pests (Table S4). Across all regions 78% report daily scouting and 18% report weekly scouting. Every grower surveyed in

Beni Suef, Ismailia, Damietta, Suez, Luxor, Qalyubia, Faiyoum and Kafr El-Sheikh report scouting daily. Only in Al Sharqia are growers more likely to report scouting weekly (62%) than daily (37%).

5. Soil fertility:

All growers identified at least one other production problem in their greenhouses (Table S5). Most growers report problems with soil fertility on their sites (83%). Soil fertility was a problem with 100% of growers in Alexandria, Ismailia, Suez, Luxor, Qalyubia and Menoufia. Across all Governorates 12% report high salt as a production problem. This was most common in Beheira (55%), Beni Suef (42%) and Faiyoum (50%).

6. Employees:

On average across all Governorates growers have 9 employees per site (Table S6). The most common number of employees in all Governorates was 6–10 (40%), followed by 1-5 employees (32%). Just 8.7% of growers surveyed had more than 20 employees. Smaller growers with 1-5 employees were common in Gharbia (77%) and Beni Suef (71%) and growers with 6-10 employees were common in Ismailia (100%), Damietta (62%), Suez (57%) and Kafr El-Sheikh (87%). Growers with more than 20 employees were uncommon across the region but made up 50% of growers surveyed in Faiyoum and 25% of growers in Qalyubia.

7. Greenhouses:

There is a mean of 50 greenhouses per site surveyed across all regions (Table S7). Among all Governorates 41% of growers have between 11-40 greenhouses and 41% of growers have between 41-100 greenhouses. Between 1-10 greenhouses was common at sites in Beheira (53%) and Ismailia (100%). Many growers in Beni Suef (85%), Gharbia (77%), Kafr El-Sheikh (77%)

and Qalyubia (100%) had between 11-40 greenhouses while many growers in Dakahlia (68%) and Damietta (75%) had between 41-100 greenhouses per site. In Al-Sharqia 37% of growers have more than 100 greenhouses, the highest percentage among all Governorates .

8. Marketing:

Most growers (76%) across all regions sell their crops to the local market (Table S8). Regions where growers reported growing vegetables for export include Beheira (44%), Beni Suef (42%), Ismailia (100%), Luxor (33%) and Qalyubia (50%).

9. Pesticides:

The most common forms of pest control across the Governorates are abamectin (56%), microbials (33%), thiamethoxam (27%) and copper/sulfur (24%). Less common pest control products include biological control (10%), spinosad (7%) and cypermethrin (6.5%). Biological control methods include using *Trichogramma* wasps (Hymenoptera: Trichogrammatidae), *Metarhizium anisopliae* (Metchnikoff) Sorokin (Hypocreales: Clavicipitaceae) fungus, the predatory mite *Phytoseiulus persimilis* Athios-Henriot (Mesostigmata: Phytoseiidae) and the predaceous lady beetle *Coccinella undecimpunctata* L. (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae).

It is concluded that growers list whiteflies and thrips as prominent pests in many regions of Egypt. A vast majority of growers also report powdery mildew as a problem in their crops. To battle pests growers often turn to abamectin, a highly toxic insecticide. Some components of IPM were reported, such as the use of biological control agents and frequent scouting for pests. However, frequent insecticide applications were common. More than 40% of those surveyed report applying insecticides more than once per week to crops including tomatoes, cucumbers and peppers. Insecticide resistance by

the major pests is common and growers desperately need alternative management options.

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Appendix 1

Table (S1): Crop type grown in greenhouses (% of survey responses).

	All	A.	B.	G.	Be.	D.	Al.	I.	D.	S.	L.	Q.	M.	F.	K.
Tomatoes	41.5	20	33.3	33.3	0	43.8	62.5	50	62.5	28.6	100	0	16.7	100	11.1
Eggplant	16.3	0	16.7	0	0	37.5	37.5	0	12.5	28.6	0	0	50	50	11.1
Peppers	36.6	30	55.6	33.3	57.1	12.5	62.5	0	37.5	28.6	0	0	50	100	88.9
Cucumbers	43.1	60	61.1	44.4	42.9	25	50	0	50	28.6	0	50	50	50	100
Melons	0.8	0	5.6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Ornamentals	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Other	14.6	0	38.9	0	0	0	0	50	0	0	0	50	0	100	55.6

A: Alexandria B. Beheira G. Gharbia Be. Beni Suef D. Dakahlia Al. Al Sharqia I. Ismailia D. Damietta S. Suez L. Luxor Q. Qalyubia M. Menoufia F. Faiyoum K. Kafr El-Sheikh.

Table (S2): Most important arthropod pests (% of survey responses)

	All	A.	B.	G.	Be.	D.	Al.	I.	D.	S.	L.	Q.	M.	F.	K.
Whitefly	91.1	100	77.8	100	100	62.5	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	100	88.9
Thrips	78	100	72.2	100	100	100	100	50	100	100	0	50	100	50	77.8
<i>Tuta absoluta</i>	40.7	0	33.3	33.3	0	56.3	62.5	50	62.5	28.6	100	0	16.7	100	0
Aphids	78.9	100	66.7	55.6	85.7	93.8	75	100	87.5	100	86.7	50	100	50	33.3
Spider mite	93.5	100	83.3	100	100	93.8	100	100	100	71.4	93.3	100	100	100	88.9
Other mite	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Nematode	39.0	20	61.1	100	0	87.5	37.5	50	12.5	42.9	0	50	0	50	0
Other	41.5	0	22.2	0	42.9	75	37.5	50	0	14.3	100	50	33.3	50	66.7

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Table (S3): Table (S3): Most important diseases (% of survey responses)

	All	A.	B.	G.	Be.	D.	Al.	I.	D.	S.	L.	Q.	M.	F.	K.
Powdery mildew	80.5	90	77.8	100	57.1	100	100	100	87.5	100	0	100	100	100	100
Grey mold	4.9	0	16.7	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	50	22.2
Downy mildew	29.3	10	44.4	0	42.9	6.3	75	50	37.5	57.1	0	100	0	0	44.4
Other	6.5	0	27.8	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	50	22.2

A: Alexandria B. Beheira G. Gharbia Be. Beni Suef D. Dakahlia Al. Al Sharqia I. Ismailia D. Damietta S. Suez L. Luxor Q. Qalyubia M. Menoufia F. Faiyoum K. Kafr El-Sheikh.

Table (S4): Frequency of scouting for pests (% of survey responses)

	All	A.	B.	G.	Be.	D.	Al.	I.	D.	S.	L.	Q.	M.	F.	K.
1-2 times over the season	0.8	0	5.6	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Daily	78	60	44.4	77.8	100	75	37.5	100	100	100	100	100	66.7	100	100
Weekly	18.7	40	33.3	22.2	0	25	62.5	0	0	0	0	0	33.3	0	0
Monthly	0.8	0	5.6	0.0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Never	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0

A: Alexandria B. Beheira G. Gharbia Be. Beni Suef D. Dakahlia Al. Al Sharqia I. Ismailia D. Damietta S. Suez L. Luxor Q. Qalyubia M. Menoufia F. Faiyoum K. Kafr El-Sheikh.

Table (S5): What other production problems are common (% of survey responses)?

	All	A.	B.	G.	Be.	D.	Al.	I.	D.	S.	L.	Q.	M.	F.	K.
High salt	12.2	0	55.6	0	42.9	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	50	11.1
Soil fertility	82.9	100	88.9	77.8	57.1	87.5	87.5	100	87.5	100	100	100	100	0	11.1

A: Alexandria B. Beheira G. Gharbia Be. Beni Suef D. Dakahlia Al. Al Sharqia I. Ismailia D. Damietta S. Suez L. Luxor Q. Qalyubia M. Menoufia F. Faiyoum K. Kafr El-Sheikh.

Table (S6): Employees per site (% of survey responses).

	All	A.	B.	G.	Be.	D.	Al.	I.	D.	S.	L.	Q.	M.	F.	K.
1-5 employees	32.5	40	44.4	77.8	71.4	37.5	12.5	0	25	42.9	40	25	16.7	0	0
6-10 employees	40.7	40	33.3	11.1	28.6	43.8	25	100	62.5	57.1	33.3	50	50	0	87.5
11-20 employees	17.1	20	11.1	11.1	0	18.8	50	0	12.5	0	26.7	25	33.3	50	12.5
>20 employees	8.7	0	11.1	0	0	0	12.5	0	0	0	0	25	0	50	0

A: Alexandria B. Beheira G. Gharbia Be. Beni Suef D. Dakahlia Al. Al Sharqia I. Ismailia D. Damietta S. Suez L. Luxor Q. Qalyubia M. Menoufia F. Faiyoum K. Kafr El-Sheikh.

Table (S7): Mean greenhouses per site (% of survey responses).

	All	A.	B.	G.	Be.	D.	Al.	I.	D.	S.	L.	Q.	M.	F.	K.
1-10 greenhouses	7.7	10	53.8	0	14.3	0	0	100	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
11-40 greenhouses	41	60	15.4	77.8	85.7	18.8	25	0	25	57.1	26.7	100	33.3	50	77.8
41-100 greenhouses	41	30	15.4	22.2	0	68.8	37.5	0	75	42.9	53.3	0	50	0	22.2
>100 greenhouses	10.3	0	15.4	0	0	12.5	37.5	0	0	0	20	0	16.7	0	0

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Table (S8): Market used for selling crops (% of survey responses).

	All	A.	B.	G.	Be.	D.	Al.	I.	D.	S.	L.	Q.	M.	F.	K.
Local market	76.4	100	44.4	100	100	100	100	0	100	100	66.7	50	100	50	22.2
Export market	17.9	0	44.4	0	42.9	0	0	100	0	0	33.3	50	0	0	0

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Grower survey:

Date: _____ **Governorate:** _____

Grower Name: _____

Grower Address: _____

How many greenhouses do you have?

How many square meters of greenhouse space do you have?

What crops do you grow?

Tomatoes	Melons
Eggplant	Ornamentals
Peppers	Other (Specify):
Cucumbers	

What are your major insect/mite pests?

Whitefly	Spider mite
Thrips	Other mites
Tuta absoluta	Other (Specify):

What are your major disease pests?

Powdery mildew	Downy mildew
Grey mold (Botrytis)	Other (Specify):

Other problems: High salts Soil Fertility

How often do you scout your crop?

Never	Weekly
1-2 times/growing season	Monthly
Daily	

How often do you apply chemical pesticides?

Never	1 time/month during the growing season
1-2 times/growing season	More than 1 time/week during the growing season

Do you ever use biological control?

If yes, what do you use?

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Preliminary tests for alternative low cost protein sources for the artificial larval diet of Mediterranean fruit flies *Ceratitidis capitata* (Diptera: Tephritidae)

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Abstract:

To reduce costs of artificial larval rearing diet of the Mediterranean fruit flies *Ceratitidis capitata* (Wiedemann) (Diptera: tephritidae) that used for different purposes, two low costs and locally available replacements for the dried sterile yeast that used as a source of protein, date seeds and poultry feed were used in a preliminary tests , comparing the efficiency of these alternatives (with the traditional yeast based diet) have been executed using quality control tests (Pupal weight, pupal size, emergence, deformity, sex ratio, flight and starvation). Results of the comparison revealed that artificial rearing of medfly on the traditional yeast based diet were very close to diets based on date seeds and poultry feed.

Introduction

Mediterranean fruit fly *Ceratitidis capitata* (Wiedemann) (Diptera: tephritidae), assumed to be the worst pest in agriculture, causing enormous threats to both production and international trade of fresh horticultural commodities (Klassen *et al.*, 1994 and Hendrichs, 1996), also, causes poverty and malnutrition in developing countries of tropical areas, where climatic conditions are suitable for fruit- and vegetable-based agro-industries (Allwood and Leblanc, 1996 and Allwood, 2000). Laboratory rearing of insects are useful for many purposes such as bioassays, physiological research, rearing of biological control agents, testing of postharvest treatments, SIT programs, etc. (Singh and Ashby, 1985). Low cost

but high quality sterile insects is main guarantee for a successful sterile insect technique programs. Proteins (yeast) products are the main nutritional ingredient used in mass-rearing diet for adults and larvae of fruit flies (Schroeder *et al.*, 1972; Cangussu and Zucoloto, 1992, 1997; Placido-Silva *et al.*, 1997; Aluja *et al.*, 2001 and Rohlf and Hoffmeister 2005).

Deficiency of any of nutritional ingredients will lead to reduction of fecundity and eclosion rates in fruit flies (Kaur and Srivastava, 1991). Drew and Yuval (2000) demonstrated that proteins are crucial for production of pheromones, secretions of male accessory gland, and spermatogenesis. In the nature, flies obtain protein or its precursors by feeding on protein-rich fruit (Such as figs), bird feces, or

colonies of bacteria found on leaf surfaces or on decomposing fruit (Hendrichs and Hendrichs, 1990 and Warburg and Yuval, 1997).

Protein-rich nutrition has great potential in promoting male sexual performance but might reduce the ability of males to endure starvation. Chan *et al.* (1990) studied different protein sources in the medfly larval diet such as: casein, corn hydrolyzate, soy protein, soy hydrolyzate, yeast hydrolyzate, lacto albumin hydrolyzate and wheat gluten as replacements for torula yeast. Also, Schroeder *et al.* (1972) studied other protein sources such as, torula yeast type 200, cottonseed protein, soybean protein, Jorgenson yeast combined with whey protein and torula yeast type B and found that only diets formulated with protein from yeast products were adequate nutritionally and physically. Al- Farsi *et al.* (2007) analyzed date seed chemically and reported that it contains protein (2.3–6.4%), fat (5.0–13.2), moisture (3.1–7.1%), phenolics (3102–4430 mg gallic acid equivalents/100 g), antioxidants (580–929 lm trolox equivalents/g) and 22.5–80.2% dietary fiber. Date seeds are potential sources of dietary fiber supplements (McKee and Latner, 2000). Also, other studies of the chemical composition and

nutritional quality revealed that date seeds contained crude protein 6.25, 10.4 % crude fat, 22.0 % crude fiber, 1.1 % ash and 60.0 % carbohydrates on dry weight basis (Chatfield and Adams, 1940; Dowson and Aten, 1962 and El-Shurafa *et al.*, 1982).

The aim of the present research paper is to study a preliminary test for alternative low cost protein sources for the artificial larval diet of *C. capitata*.

Materials and methods

1. Fly strain: Mediterranean fruit fly lab strain (Horticultural crops insects Department Laboratories - Plant Pprotection Research Institute).

The adult flies feed normally upon water, sugar and hydrolyzed protein (4:1). Date seeds toasted Grinded and sifted and added to the larval rearing diet replacing the yeast. Date seeds/ Poultry feed replacing the yeast by weight. Poultry feed ingredients: Yellow corn, Soybean meal 48%, sprouted Soybean seeds, Wheat bran, Mono calcium phosphate, Limestone powder, Table salt, A mixture of vitamins and mineral salts, L. lysis Hydrochloride, D.L. Methionin, Sodium bicarbonate and invertase enzyme. Poultry feed protein content 16 %, Crude fat 3.55 % and Crude fiber 2.7 (Table 1).

Table (1): Showed the composition of the Standard (Control), 100 % (Date seeds / Poultry feed), 75% (Date seeds / Poultry feed) and 50 % (Date seeds / Poultry feed).

	Standard (Control)	100 % (Date seeds / Poultry feed)	75% (Date seeds / Poultry feed)	50 % (Date seeds / Poultry feed)
Sugar	82	82	82	82
Protein	82 Dried sterile yeast	82 Date seeds/ Poultry feed	61.5 Date seeds/ Poultry feed + 20.5 yeast	41 Date seeds/ Poultry feed + 41 yeast
Wheat bran	330	330	330	330
Sodium benzoate	3	3	3	3
Citric acid	3	3	3	3
Water	500	500	500	500

2. Quality control tests: Experiments details:(IAEA, 2014):

2.1. Weight of pupae:

Record average weights of 10 pupae two days before emergence (Five replicates).

2.2. Size pupae:

Measured volumetrically by counting the number of pupae per one ml using graduated cylinder and record the average size per pupa (Five replicates).

2.3. Emergence percentage:

Calculate number of successfully emerged flies for each 100 pupae and estimate the emergence percentage (Five replicates).

2.4. Ratio of Deformed flies:

Calculate number of flies that failed to emerge, or emerge with deformation for each 100 pupae to estimate the Deformity percentage (Five replicates).

2.5. Sex ratio:

For each group of 100 emerged adult flies, The numbers of males and females are counted and recorded (five replicates).

2.6. Flight ability:

100 pupae for each treatment placed into one PVC cylinder coated internally by talcum powder and put inside a plastic transparent bag with metal frame inside to make it swallowed, on emergence, calculate the flies succeeded to fly and escape the cylinder to be the flier individuals (five replicates).

2.7. Survival under stress:

A number of 100 flies are caged separately (transparent cups with top with a fiber mesh top cover to supply aeration) without any feeding material or water and calculate how long the fly can persist alive without any nutrition.

Results and discussion

1. Date seeds:

1.1. Pupal weight:

Results in Table (2) revealed that control and 50 % pupae have the superior weight with mean of 11.12 mg/pupa and 11.56 mg/pupa respectively, but they differ significantly from 75 % and 100 % those came in the second order with mean weights of 8.4 mg/pupa and 7.5 mg/pupa respectively.

1.2. Pupal size:

Table (2) show that there was no significant difference between control pupae and 50 % date diet pupae with mean pupal size of 0.0205 ml/pupa and 0.0202 ml/pupa respectively while they differ significantly from 75 % and 100 % date diets pupae those have means of 0.0175 and 0.0165 ml/pupa respectively.

1.3. Emergence percentage:

The four diets have differed significantly from each other table (2), control diet has the superior emergence percentage with mean of 97 % followed by 50 % date seed diet with mean percentage of 95.2, then 75 % diet with mean of 91.2 and finally 100 % date seed diet as the least emergence percentage mean of 86.2.

1.4. Deformity percentage:

For the deformed adults up on emergence, results in table (2) revealed that there were no significant differences among the four diet, control, 50 %, 75 % and 100 % date seed diets with deformed adult flies means of 0.8 %, 0.4 %, 0.4 % and 0.6 % respectively.

1.5. Sex ratio:

Table (2) data showed that Sex ratios of adult flies results from the four diets came with means of, 48♂ : 52♀, 49♂ : 51♀, 55♂ : 45♀ and 52♂ : 48♀ for control, 50 %, 75 % and 100 % date seed diets respectively.

1.6. Flight ability:

Table (2) show that there was no significant difference between flight ability of the adult flies resulted from 50 % and 75 % date diet pupae with mean percent fliers of 70.8 % and 71.2 % respectively while they differ significantly from control and 100 % date diet pupae those have means of 66 % and 65.6 respectively.

1.7. Survival under Stress (Starvation):

The four diets have differed significantly among each other table

(2), 75 % date seed diet has the longest life span (life span without feeding as an indicator to the ability of the fly that survive under stress of food absence), with mean of 118 hour/adult fly, followed by 100 % date seed diet with

mean life span of 112.6 hour/fly, then control diet with mean of 107.6 hour/fly and finally 50 % date seed diet as the least life span with mean of 102.7 hour/fly.

Table (2) : Pupal weight, size, emergence, deformity, sex ratio, flight and starvation of medfly reared on standard, 50, 75 and 100 % date seed diets.

Treatment parameter	Control	50 %	75 %	100 %
Pupal weight	11.12 ± 0.053 a1	11.56 ± 0.024 a1	8.4 ± 0.122 b1	7.5 ± 0.049 b1
Pupal size	0.0205 ± 0.0002 a2	0.0202 ± 0.0002 a2	0.0175 ± 0.0003 b2	0.0165 ± 0.0004 b2
Emergence	97 ± 0.316 a3	95.2 ± 0.374 b3	91.2 ± 0.374 c3	86.2 ± 0.374 d3
Deformity	0.8 ± 0.374 a4	0.4 ± 0.245 a4	0.4 ± 0.245 a4	0.6 ± 0.245 a4
Sex ratio	48♂ : 52♀	49♂ : 51♀	55♂ : 45♀	52♂ : 48♀
Flight	66 ± 0.316 b5	70.8 ± 0.374 a5	71.2 ± 0.374 a5	65.6 ± 0.4 b5
Starvation	107.6 ± 0.510 c6	102.7 ± 0.422 d6	118 ± 0.286 a6	112.6 ± 0.504 b6

2. Poultry feed :

2.1. Pupal weight:

Results in Table (3) revealed that control has the superior weight with mean of 11.12 mg /pupa and differ significantly from the rest of the diets, followed by both 50 % and 100 % Poultry feed diet those have mean pupal weight of 9.24 and 9.0 mg /pupa respectively, but they differ significantly from 75 % which came with least mean weight of 8.52 mg/ y.

2.2. Pupal size:

Table (3) show that control pupae has the superior size with mean of 0.205 ml / pupa and differ significantly from the rest diets, followed by 50 % diet that has a mean of 0.193 ml/pupa , also, they differ significantly from the rest diets, finally, 75 % and 100 % there was no significant difference between control pupae and 50 % date diet pupae with mean pupal size of 0.0205 ml /pupa and 0.0202 ml/pupa respectively while they differ significantly from 75 % and 100 % Poultry feed diet pupae have no significant differences between them and have a mean pupal size of 0.0185 and 0.0189 ml/pupa respectively.

2.3. Emergence percentage:

Data in Table (3) show that control pupae has the largest percentage of emergence with mean of 96.45 % and differ significantly from the rest diets, followed by 50 % and 100 % diets with a mean emergence percentage of 95.05 % and 95.25 % ,with no significant difference between them, while 75 % came with the least percentage (mean of 90.9 %).

2.4. Deformity percentage:

Results in Table (3) revealed that there were no significant differences among the four diet, control, 50 % , 75 % and 100 % Poultry feed diets with deformed adult flies means of 0.6 % , 0.8 % , 0.5 % and 0.6 % respectively.

2.5. Sex ratio :

Table (3) data showed that Sex ratios of adult flies results from the four diets came with means of, 48♂ : 52♀, 52♂ : 48♀, 44♂ : 56♀ and 51♂ : 49♀ for control, 50 % , 75 % and 100 % Poultry feed diets respectively.

2.6. Flight ability:

Table (3) show that there were a significant difference among the flight ability of the adult flies resulted from the four diets, 100 % diet flies came as the first rank with mean of 74.6 % , followed by 75 % poultry feed diet

fliers with mean of 72.15 % then 50 % diet with mean of 68.25 % and finally, control diet with mean flier percentage of 66.4 %.

2.7. Survival under Stress (Starvation):

The four diets have differed significantly among each other Table

Table (3) : Pupal weight, size, emergence, deformity, sex ratio, flight and starvation of medfly reared on standard, 50, 75 and 100 % poultry feed diets.

Treatment parameter	Control	50 %	75 %	100 %
Pupal weight	11.12 ± 0.583 a1	9.24 ± 0.510 b1	8.52 ± 0.128 c1	9.0 ± 0.054 b1
Pupal size	0.205 ± 0.000 a2	0.193 ± 0.001 b2	0.0185 ± 0.001 c2	0.0189 ± 0.001 bc2
Emergence	96.45 ± 0.278 a3	95.05 ± 0.320 b3	90.9 ± 0.332 c3	95.25 ± 0.194 b3
Deformity	0.6 ± 0.245 a4	0.8 ± 0.374 a4	0.5 ± 0.289 a4	0.6 ± 0.4 a4
Sex ratio	48♂ : 52♀	52♂ : 48♀	44♂ : 56♀	51♂ : 49♀
Flight	66.4 ± 0.510 d5	68.25 ± 0.403 c5	72.15 ± 0.384 b5	74.6 ± 0.510 a5
Starvation	107.6 ± 0.510 b6	112.2 ± 0.374 a6	93.2 ± 0.564 c6	85.12 ± 0.393 d6

Results of quality control tests (Pupal weight, pupal size, emergence, deformity, sex ratio, flight and starvation - for both of the Mediterranean and Peach fruit flies) revealed that traditional wheat bran based artificial larval diet was very close to the new diets based on date seeds and poultry feed (Used as an alternative sources for proteins) in spite of the significant differences that showed through the statistical analysis of the results but these differences will compensated after successive generations reared upon the same new diets (Kamikado *et al.*, 1987; Souza *et al.*, 1988 and Economopoulos, 1992) whose demonstrated that adaptation of the fruit flies to the laboratory artificial diet for colonization need several generations.

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(3), 50 % poultry feed diet has the longest life span, with mean of 112.2 hour/adult fly, followed by control diet with mean life span of 107.6 hour/fly, then 75 % diet with mean of 93.2 hour/fly and finally 100 % poultry feed diet as the shortest life span with mean of 85.12 hour/fly.

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First record of *Cylindromyia (Conopisoma) rufipes* of subfamily Phasiinae (Tachinidae : Diptera) as facultative endoparasitoid of *Nezara millierei* (Pentatomidae: Hemiptera) in Egypt

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Abstract:

The present study reported the tachinidae fly *Cylindromyia (Conopisoma) rufipes* (Meigen) of subfamily Phasiinae (Tachinidae : Diptera) as an endoparasitoid attacking colony of the *Nezara millierei* Mulsant and Rey (Pentatomidae: Hemiptera) for the first time. This case of parasitism was observed inside rearing cages of the *N. millierei* at the Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University, Giza, Egypt in October 2020. We firstly identified adult individuals of *N. millierei* which were found moving erratically here and there within the cages using relevant identification keys. To verify that they are parasitized by the same parasitoid and no other parasitoids were detected, some of the parasitized bugs were transferred to a separate cages at the same laboratory conditions, and the developmental stages of the dipteran parasitoid were observed by the adult emerges. The present investigation reveals that *C. rufipes* could have a potentiality to control *N. millierei*, and further studies should be carried out to assess the effectiveness of this fly as a biocontrol agent.

Introduction

The stink bug *Nezara millierei* (*Acrosternum millierei*) (Meigen, 1824) (Hemiptera: Pentatomidae) is belonging to sucking insect, they attack all parts of the plants and prefers growing shoots and developing fruits. They are fed by injecting water; saliva containing digestive enzymes and suck out liquefied contents. Also, this insect causes indirect damage to plants by providing an entry slot for pathogenic and decaying organisms at the feeding punctures (Panizzi, 1997).

Gözüaçık (2018) detailed that *N. millierei* was invasion caper plants amid the dry period. Sucking show up

on bud and natural products of capers amid this time. Bud deformation due the spots shaped the sucking and the color alter caused by the proteins emitted and drop therefore, diminished the natural product quality in this way diminished the financial esteem of the editors. In Egypt, Linnavuori (1964) listed that, *N. millierei* (*A. millierei*) collected from Cairo, Suez desert road and Kharga on cultivated field in 1962. Later, Linnavuori (1993) recorded that *N. millierei* distributed in Iraq and had a wide range in the Middle East and the Ethiopian region.

Rabitsch (2008) reported that a single example of this Mediterranean

species expanding to tropical Africa was captured in a light trap in 2004 in Zala County and in Hungary (Kondorosy, 2005). This status merited further consideration because it may get to be setup beneath current climatic condition in mild Europe as watched for *Nezara*.

Ghahari *et al.* (2014) reported that *N. millierei* (*A. millierei*) is widely distributed in Iran and have many plant hosts. According to Ribes and Pagola-Carte (2013) *N. millierei* lives on or under a great number of plants belonging to Pinaceae, Cupressaceae, Euphorbiaceae, Anacardiaceae, Fagaceae, Araliaceae, Ranunculaceae, Fabaceae, Poaceae, Cistaceae, Oleaceae; these authors recall that in Saudi Arabia *N. millierei* lives in deserts biotopes but that in Israel it has been collected in cool places. *N. millierei* is the vector of *Nematospora coryli* as plant pathogen to pistachio trees (Safavi, 1974). Also, an unknown species, *Acrosternum* sp., were

Phasiinae (Dupuis, 1963). There are four subfamilies traditionally recognized in the family Tachinidae, namely, Dexiinae, Exoristinae, Phasiinae, and Tachininae (El-Hawagry, 2018). The subfamily Phasiinae are the smallest species (O'Hara and Wood, 2004). Phasiinae vary significantly in size (2 –17mm) and brightly colored fly with a red to orange abdomen often accented by various black markings (Blaschke *et al.*, 2019). They have specialized antennal receptors that are extremely sensitive to the host pheromones (Aldrich *et al.*, 2006). The subfamily Phasiinae is known as specialist to comprise species which attack true bugs (Heteroptera) (Arnaud, 1978). Blaschke *et al.* (2019) reported that phasiines are parasitize assortment of species from miniature discolored plant bugs (*Lygus* Hahn spp.) to leaf-footed bugs (*Leptoglossus* Guérin – Méneville

recorded by Hashemi Rad *et al.* (2000 and 2002) from Kerman as the pest of pistachio which we suspect that it was *N. millierei* Tachinid family is the second largest family in order Diptera and include approximately 8500 species. Their larvae are endoparasite of arthropods and some species their flies lay a role as pollinators (Tooker *et al.*, 2005; Al-Dobai *et al.*, 2012 and Blaschke *et al.*, 2019).

Most tachinid flies are larger than a house fly and noticeably bristlier, but they range in size from 2-20 mm. and between the family there is a huge difference of form, colors and degree of bristling. All tachinid flies are parasitoids in their larval stage and their hosts all belong to the Arthropoda, almost exclusively the Insecta. Tachinids select as their hosts larval and adult Coleoptera, Orthoptera and Hemiptera, the last one order described as a main host by several species of the subfamily

spp.) including several important invasive agricultural pests as *Nezara viridula* L., *Halyomorpha halys* Stål and *Megacopta cribraria* Fabricius. Adults of Phasiinae mostly are nectar feeders. Larvae overwinter within the host bug and emerge in the following late spring or early summer (Worthley, 1924).

In Egypt, the subfamily Phasiinae is known as comprising only seven species in three tribes, namely, Cylindromyiini, Leucostomatini, and Phasiini (El-Hawagry, 2018). The first detected and Identified the species of *C. rufipes* by (Ayman and Hany, 2010), there are 3 specimens as source material which found in Ministry of Agriculture Collection, Plant Protection Research Institute, Taxonomy Department, these specimens collected from Mansouriah. by one method (Sweeping net) at 28-08-1935, from which 2 females and 1 male, in addition to the specimens were

collected recently from Western desert (El-Kharga Oasis) by sweeping net at 80-2007. The species *C. rufipes*, since that date, which was recorded in Egypt, has not been reported by anyone as a parasite on bug specially *N. millierei*.

Therefore, the present work records for the first time the presence of tachinidae fly *C. rufipes* as a facultative endoparasitoid of stink bug *N. millierei* from Egypt and includes a description of its morphology and biology.

Materials and methods

1. Collected sample of insect:

During the gathering of the green bug *N. millierei* were different methods were used to collect insects, by hand, a sweeping net or sheet-screen, (Sheet screen traps are used prior to collection to determine which types of bugs are most prevalent) in the month of October from the soya bean plant *Glycine max* from the farm of the Faculty of Agriculture at Cairo University in order to raise it to do some experiments on entomopathogenic fungi on it, where more green bugs *N. millierei* are done to do experiments to combat the fungi that pathogen to insects on that bug.

2. Rearing of green bug *Nezara millierei*:

Collected adult were maintained on plastic cage (30X12 cm) and covered with muslin. Fresh green beans *Phaseolus vulgaris* L. were supplemented for green bug feeding, which renewed every two day intervals. Sheets papers were added to lay eggs and the deposited egg-masses were daily collected and placed in petri-dish containing a pieces of moistened cotton wool and supplemented with fresh green beans until hatching. After hatching Nymphs were transferred to another rearing box. Adult were collected and put in new rearing boxes for breeding (Francati *et al.*, 2019).

3. Rearing of *Cylindromyia rufipes*:

We noticed that some of the green bugs With little activity, they were isolated in empty breeding cages and monitored daily, and after 6 days, pupa was seen sticking to the green bug from the back and on the rearing cages. Pupae were collected individually in plastic cups 5cm in diameter supplement with sawdust at 25±2 °C and 16:8h (L:D) photoperiod. Giangiuliani and Farinelli (1995) indicate that in order to be able pupae of *Trichopoda pennis* (Phasiini) to emerge into adults they must retain in high humidity. Whereas, , in this study, we found that all pupae were dying when we used this process, so we put them in sawdust. Adult flies were collected after 2 weeks and maintained in rearing cages which supplemented with a hanged cotton ball soaked with honey solution (10%) for their feeding. Some of the flies emerged send to the Department of Insect survey and Classification Research at the Plant Protection Research Institute at the Agricultural Research Center, to scientific examination. Adult of stink bugs *N. millierei* were exposed to parasitoid cages and check daily for collection when they had parasitoid egg. Exposed bugs were transferred to the rearing cage as previous methods and notes daily until they die and collected parasite puparium (Francati *et al.*, 2019). The collected adult flies emerged were taken again to the Survey and Classification Research Department of the Plant Protection Research Institute to confirm the identification, and after a scientific examination of the flies, make sure that they are of the same type that was defined before. The parasitoid adults, and the parasitized hosts were photographed. The drawings were made directly from specimens by using USB digital Microscope and original binuclear microscope by (25X measure). Four adult individuals (two

males and two females) of *C. rufipes* were deposited in the collection of the Survey and Classification Research Department, (first floor, room No. 36A) of the Plant Protection Research Institute Ministry of Agriculture Collection, Dokki, Giza.

Results and discussion

1. Taxonomy of *Nezara millierei* (Figure 1) :

Confirmation specimens : (2 males and 1 female) as a source material collected at 28-08-1935 from Mansouriah, and other specimens (3 males and 1 female) were collected from Western Desert (El-Kharga Oasis) at 80-2007.

Synonym:

Acrosternum millierei (Mulsant and Rey, 1866)

This genus *Acrosternum* has had a confusing taxonomic history. Many of the species were described or placed in the genus *Nezara* at one time or another. Also, at one time, many more species were included in *Acrosternum*; these were transferred to *Nezara*, then moved back to *Acrosternum*, and more

recently have been moved back to *Nezara*. In general, species of *Acrosternum* are smaller, more pale green in color, and usually occur in dryer, more arid regions; *Nezara* species tend to be larger, more bright or vivid green, and they usually occur in more tropical or temperate areas. All pentatomids have 5-segmented antennae, and 3 tarsal segments on each foot. They generally have a large triangular scutellum in the center of the back. The body shape of adult pentatomids is generally "shieldlike," when viewed from above, but this varies between species, and is not true for the immature nymphal stages. The forewings of stink bugs are called hemelytra, with the basal half thickened while the apex is membranous. At rest, the wings are laid across the back of the insect, with the membranous wingtips overlapping. The hindwings are entirely membranous (Figure 1).

Figure (1): Adult of *Nezara millierei*

2. Taxonomy of *Cylindromyia rufipes*:

Subfamily: Phasiinae

Tribe: Cylindromyiini

Genus: *Cylindromyia* Meigen

Cylindromyia Meigen, 1803: 279. Type species: *Musca brassicaria* Fabricius, 1775, by monotypy.

Ocyptera Latreille, 1804: 195. Type species: *Musca brassicaria* Fabricius, 1775, by subsequent designation of Curtis (1837: 629).

Exogaster Rondani, 1856: 78. Type species: *Exogaster carinatus* Rondani, 1856 (= *Ocyptera*

rufifrons Loew, 1844), by original designation.

Ocypterula Rondani, 1856: 78. Type species: *Ocyptera*

pusilla Meigen, 1824, by original designation.

Plesiocyptera Brauer and Bergenstamm, 1893: 56. Type species: *Ocyptera*

bicolor Wiedemann, 1819, by monotypy.

Conopisoma Speiser, 1910: 144. Type species: *Conopisoma*

miraculum Speiser, 1910, by original designation.

Formicocyptera Townsend, 1933: 451. Type species: *Ocyptera*

atrata Fabricius, 1805, by original designation.

Diagnosis:

The genus *Cylindromyia* differs from other Phasiinae genera by combination of the following characters: Palpus strongly reduced or absent; lower facial margin visible in lateral view; prementum at least 4 times as long as wide; parafacial bare; ocellar setae proclinate; occiput with white setulae, sometimes with a few dorsal black setulae. Scutellum with 1–3 pairs of marginal setae; postmetacoxal area sclerotized. Wing cell r4+5 closed; second costal section bare ventrally. Preapical anterodorsal seta on fore tibia visibly longer than preapical dorsal seta; preapical posteroventral seta on hind tibia present. Abdominal sternites concealed by margins of abdominal

tergites; tergite and sternite 7 . Female fused as a hook-like complex

***Cylindromyia rufipes* (Meigen, 1824) (Figure 2)**

Ocyptera rufipes Meigen, 1824: 215. Lectotype male (MNHN). France.

Distribution: AF: U.A. Emirates. OR: India, Pakistan. PA: Egypt, all Europe (except British Is., Scand.), Pakistan, Russia (W. Russia), Saudi Arabia, Transcaucasia, Ukraine.

Egyptian localities: Mansouriah, Western Desert (El-Kharga Oasis) and Giza.

Dates of collection: October to December.

Diagnosis:

Head: Surrounded by postocular row of setae; compound eyes bare, not hairy, they occupy a big part of the head, they are similar in both sexes; Antenna characterized all species of genus *Cylindromyia* which elongate in forms and flattened where the third segment is truncate apically, about 5 times as long as the second provided with numerous sensorial, the first and second segment is short, the arista very long, thickened apically and tapering toward the edge (Whip-like), the antennae situated in a groove, concave in form is a frons which surrounded by a facial edge, the later have a series of few small bristles extending on either side of the face external to the antennae and above the vibrissa, there are 7 bristles in row on each side on the frontal stripe, descending to the base of the antennae (Figure 3).

Figure (2): Adult of *Cylindromyia rufipes*

Figure (3): Head of *Cylindromyia rufipes*

Thorax: Proepisternum bare; scutellum black, with 3 pairs of marginal setae; posterior supra-alar seta present; katepisternum with 2 setae; basicosta yellowish-brown; legs dark yellow; mid tibia with 2 anterodorsal setae; hind tibia without posteroventral setae; hind femur and tibia with long setulae in posterior and ventral portion; wings, basicosta brown, bend of m narrowly rounded obtuse, the apical cross-vein more or less sinuate behind the bend, forming an obtuse angle with m, R2+3 and R4+5 nearly straight, R4+5 up curved toward Sc margin M1+2 not completed with disappeared before ending of Sc, basal node of R4+5 branches at the distance of reaching Sc with costa (Figure 4) .

Abdomin: Long and narrow, subcylindrical or slightly clavate, constricted at the base, the terminalia of males and females not forcipate but large and doubled back on ventral surface of abdomen, there are two white rings surrounding the abdominal tergite

at 3th and 5th segments, all of tergites carry a two strong setae (Figures 5 and 6).

Material examined: (1 male and 2 females) 16-10-2018 Giza; (3 Males) 03-11-2018 Giza.

The female glues at least one whitish plano-convex, -un brooded eggs on to the host body of the adult, or occasionally on late nymphal instar of the bug, and attach these eggs firmly to the body wall. The majority of the eggs are found on the sides of the thorax. Each female produces several hundred eggs during its lifespan. After hatching, newborn larva bores the host bug tegument entering its body and feeds on its body fluids for about 2 weeks. The host bug usually dies after the infection, and the larvae develop through 3 instars. Then, mature larvae emerge through its anal extremity and enter the upper soil layer to form a dark-brownish puparium (Worthley, 1924). Pupation usually requires about 2–4 weeks (Figure 7).

Figure (4): Thorax of *Cyldromyia rufipes*

Figure (5): Abdomin of *Cyldromyia rufipes*

Figure (6): *Cylindromyia rufipes* : (1) Head capsule, Anterior view. (2) Head capsule, lateral view. (3) Wing venation. (4) Mid tibia. (5) Thorax, dorsal view. (6) Male sternite. (7) Dorsolateral view of abdominal segments.

Figure (7): Life cycle of *Cyindromyia rufipes* as endoparasite of *Nezara millierei*

Our resulting agreement with other studies in *Trichopoda pennipes* (Tachinidae: Phasiinae) which have the same lifespan periods (Worthley, 1924; Salerno *et al.*, 2002; Cargnus *et al.*, 2011; Pétremand *et al.*, 2015 and El-Hawagry *et al.*, 2020). Several stink bugs and shield bugs are considered agricultural pests, because they can grow into large populations that feed on crops, damaging production, and they are resistant to many pesticides. They are a threat to cotton, corn, sorghum, soybeans, native and ornamental trees, shrubs, vines, weeds, and many cultivated crops. Though that the effective means of reducing or mitigating green bugs *N. millierei* pests effects through the use of natural enemies as *C. rufipes*.

From the beginning of this century, tachinid flies have been involved in many operations of applied biological control against different insect pests. A review is done about utilization of Tachinidae all over the world. These parasitoid insects were used by inoculative, augmentative or inundative releases. Most of the operations were accomplished in the nearctic and neotropical regions. Sometimes great successes were obtained especially in North America and in tropical areas. Success or failure of release processes may be explained by different ways shortly analyzed.

Egypt, as a part of the Great Desert Belt, is characterized by a warm and almost rainless climate and has a greater affiliation to the Palearctic region except for the Gebel Elba, its southeastern triangle, which has a greater affiliation to the Afrotropical region (El-Hawagry and Gilbert, 2014; El-Hawagry, 2017 and El-Hawagry *et al.*, 2020). However, and according to the present study *C. rufipes* seems to be established in Egypt.

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Influence of storage thermal on some fungicide compounds and their impurities

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Storage thermal,
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Abstract:

The present work was carried out to study the effect of storage under high temperature fungicides of mancosil plas (Metallic copper + metalaxyl)50 %WP and mancosil (Mencozeb and metalaxyl) 70 % WP. The stability of active ingredient of the tested pesticides under storage 54 °C for 28 days and influence UV ray were studied . The active ingredient was metallic copper active ingredient 35.11 before storage become after storage the end experiment 33.81% for 28 days stability of metallic copper active ingredient was 35.59 before storage UV 36 and 48 hours become after influence UV 33.56 and 33.32, respectively . Also, the effect of the influence UV ray on the stability of mancozeb active ingredient (a.i) in mancosil formulation 72 % , The active ingredient of mancozeb was before 64.94 % become after influence UV ray 58,33% and 58.21% at 36 and 48 hours respectively. Cadmium has not detected in both mancosil plas , also showed decreased the amount of lead and arsenic (mg/kg)in mancosil plas 50 % , whereas the percentage loss of lead , and arsenic were 153% and 3.11% respectively, for storage 28 days on 54°C. Also, show that the impurities ethylene thiourea (ETU) and 2,6 dimethyl aniline of mancozeb 72 % WP before storage were 0.09 and 0.0041, respectively , before an influence UV ray become 0.49% and 0.069 % after influence UV ray 48 hrs.

Introduction

Fungicides are useful and important in agricultural production despite the increasing interest of the new concept called biological agriculture. This practice is not without risk on animal and human health and, in wide consideration, on environmental conditions due to the residues of fungicides that may persist many weeks or months after application

(Sparling *et al.*, 2001). Mancozeb (Ethylene bis-dithiocarbamate fungicide (EBCD)) was first registered in the United States in 1948 (Runkle *et al.*, 2017) and introduced in the global fungicide market in 1962 (Palmerini *et al.*, 2018). Mancozeb fungicidal efficacy has been applied in different agricultural and industrial contexts, for example, in major agricultural crops (Potato, tomato and grapevine), and its

use will likely increase by the 2020s due to its low price, global demand for vegetables and fruits, and non-selective fungicidal efficacy (Runkle *et al.*, 2017). Mancozeb influence induces a wide range of environmental hazard, such as, thyroid hormone dysfunctions, Parkinson-like symptoms and defects in fetal development (Goldner *et al.*, 2010 and Runkle *et al.*, 2017) . The aim of this work to determine (Mencosil plus

Table (1): The formulation of pesticides.

Trade name	Formulation types	Active ingredient	Impurities
Mancosil plus 72 %	WP	Mixture metalaxyl + Cupper oxychloride	2,6 dimethyl analine in metalaxyl + AS,Cd, Pb in cupper
Mencosil 50 %	WP	Mixture metalaxyl + Mencozeb	2,6 dimethyl analine in metalaxyl +Ethylen thiourea (ETU) in mencozeb

2. Sample preparation for tested pesticides:

Accurately weighed enough samples formulation equivalent to 10 mg of standard in a different 25 ml volumetric flask for each sample, and slowly mixed with methanol and the volume was completed with methanol.

3. Sample preparation for impurities:

1 g tested formulation samples in 25 ml volumetric flask for each sample were prepared and slowly mixed with methanol and the volume was completed with methanol .

4. Storage conditions:

The tested fungicide formulation was stored at 54°C for 14 days according to FAO (1989 and 1998). During the storage period , samples were taken at 1,3,7, 14 , 21 and 28 days to determine the active ingredient and their impurities content for the tested formulations under testes .

5. Influence of UV ray :

The pesticides mencosil plus 50 %WP and mancossil WP 72 %) formulation were influence of direct UV ray .The samples were taken at 0,

50 % and mancossil 70 %) active ingredient and the impurities heavy metal , ethylen thiourea and 2,6 dimethyl analine content through storage at 54°C for 28 days .

Materials and methods

1. Source of Sample: Center Agric. Pesticides Laboratory. Table (1) showed that the formulation of pesticides used.

1,5 ,12 , 24 , 36 and 48 hours from influence direct UV to determine the active ingredient and impurities content for formulation under testes.

6. Determination of impurities heavy metal:

The cadmium, lead and Arsenic were determined before and after storage according to **CIPAC (1970)** Thermo element (Atomic absorption spectra photometric (Model 4200 MP - AES) was used for all the measurement

7. Determination of metallic copper:

The metallic copper percentage was determined before and after storage according to **CIPAC E 44/TC/M3.1p.42.**

8. Determination of mencozeb :

The active ingredient percentage was determined before and after storage according to (**CIPAC . IA;34/3/M/6.3).**

9. Determination of 2, 6 dimethyl analine and ETU by HPLC :

The Impurities for ETU were evaluated by HPLC apparatus according to the method of Luke *et al.* (1981). A revise phase high-

performance liquid chromatographic was used for quantitative analysis . Aglient technologies 1200 series HPLC in student equipped with degasser , quaternary pump, photodiode array detector connected with injection system and computer (Model vectra was used for analysis . The stationary phase consisted of lichrosphere on Rp-8 packed stainless steel column (15 cm X4.6 mm id)

Results and discussion

1. Effect of storage thermal stability mancosil plas 35 %WP and mancosil 72 %WP at 54°C.:

Date in Table (2) showed that stability of metallic copper active ingredient 35.11 % before storage become after storage the end experiment 33.81% for 28 days .these results indicated that all test copper formulation was passed successfully and comply with FAO Specification (1989 and 1998) . These results are similar obtained by Abd El-Aal *et al.*, 1993 and El-Deep *et al.*, 1991), who report the correlation between temperature and storage temperature and decomposition of patricides formulation. Also, the effect

Table (2): Effect of storage thermal stability mancosil plas 35 %WP and mancosil 72 %WP at 54°C.

Storage period days	Mancosil plas 50%				Mencosil 70 %			
	Metallic Copper 35 %	Loss %	Metalaxyl 15 %	Loss %	Mencozeb 64 %	Loss %	Metalaxyl 8%	Loss %
0	35.11	00	15.44	0	64.34	00	8.59	00
1	35.11	00	15.31	0.84	64.34	0.01	8.51	1.04
3	35.00	0.31	15.01	0.90	63.88	0.52	8.09	5.82
7	35.00	0.31	14.60	2.78	63.03	0.730	7.82	8.96
14	34.81	0.85	13.89	5.44	62.92	2.05	7.55	12.10
21	34.00	3.16	13.59	10.03	61.56	2.22	6.99	18.62
28	33.81	3.70	12.55	18.71	59.33	8.40	6.64	22.70

0* one hour before exposure to storage

2. Effect of influence UV ray stability mancosil plas 35 %and mancosil 72 % at UV ray :

Data in Table (3) stability of metallic copper active ingredient were 35.59 before storage UV 36 and 48 hours become after influence UV 33.56

of storage at 54°C on the stability of Mancozeb active ingredient (a.i) in mencosil formulation 72 % . The active ingredient of Mancozeb was before storage 64.35% at become after storage 62.92% after 14 days of storage at 54°C .According to this results FAO specification (1992) but decreasing 28 days become after storage 59.33 % . The primary source of these exposure is the use of ethylene bisdithio carbamate (EBDCs) fungicides of which ethylenethiourea is an environmental degradation product, metabolite and impurity. Ethylenthiourea content in (EBDCs) fungicides formulation depend on the pesticides storage conditions and increased by increasing temperature , a moisture and length of storage period Comoni *et al.* (1988) and Sue Xu (2000) . The stability of metalaxyl active ingredient were 15.44 and 8.59 before storage 54 °C all mencosil plas and mancosil become after thermal storage 54 °C at the end of experiment 12.55% and 6.64% for 28 days There obtained result were agreement with (Khozimy and Ramdan , 2018) .

and 33.32respectively . Also, the effect of influence UV ray on the stability of mancozeb active ingredient (a.i) in mencosil formulation 72 % , The active ingredient of mancozeb was before 64.94 % become after influence UV ray 58,33% and 58.21% at 36 and 48

hours, respectively. The stability of metalaxyl active ingredient were 15.44 and 8.59 before influence UV ray all mencosil plas and mancasil become

after influence UV ray 54 °C at the end of experiment 12.32 % and 6.34 % for 48 hours.

Table (3): Effect of influence UV ray stability mancasil plas 50 % and mancasil 72 % at UV ray .

Storage period hours	Mancosil plas 50 Metallic cupper + metalaxyl				Mencosil 70 % Mencozeb + metalaxyl			
	Metallic cupper 35 %	Loss %	Metalaxyl 15 %	Loss %	Mencozeb 64 %	Loss %	Metalaxyl 8%	Loss %
0	35.59	00	15.44	00	64.94	00	8.59	00
1	35.59	00	15.44	00	64.94	00	8.20	4.54
5	35.00	1.66	15.00	2.93	64.55	0.54	8.00	6.94
8	34.85	2.00	14.78	4.27	64.31	0.97	7.98	18.26
12	34.11	4.10	14.78	4.27	62.55	3.68	7.88	18.16
24	33.56	5.70	14.50	6.08	60.25	7.22	7.03	22.19
36	33.56	5.8	13.91	9.90	58.33	10.18	6.95	19.09
48	33.32	6.37	12.32	20.20	58.21	10.36	6.34	26.19

0* one hour before exposure to storage

3. Effect of storage at 54 °C on level impurities mancasil plas 50% and mancasil 72 % :

The Data illustrate in Table (4) show the effect of storage at 54 c on the level Cadmium and arsenic mg/kg in testes copper products. Cadmium not detected in both mencosil plas , also showed decrease the amount of Lead and Arsenic (mg/kg)in im mencosil plas 50 % , whereas the percentage loss of Lead , and Arsenic were 153 and 3.11%, respectively, for storage 28 days on 54°C . Some pesticides are suspected carcinogenic properties . The trace element can be associated with ligaud , colloids or particles of organic and inorganic forms according to their chemical structure Digild and Best (1994) .

Although it is probable that the final product is not only affected by the source of primary minerals but also by trace elements introduce during pesticides production. Of the other

important use of mercury and Arsenic include manufacture of pesticides (Hutton and Symon , 1986). show that the impurities of Mancozeb 72 % WP before storage were 0.09 and % (ETU) Ethylen thio urea and 2, 6 dimethyl analine respectively, Become after storage, 1.10 and 0.04 % after 28 days from storage at 54 °C respectively.

There obtained result were agreement with Suzanne (1980) . According to FAO specifications (1992) which reported that maximum limit of 2, 6- dimethylaniline and Ethulenthourea (ETU) as relevant impurities are 0.1 % and 0.5 %)of the metalaxyl content the tested fungicide percentage became higher than FAO specification limit after 10 days of storage and tested fungicide became non conformity with FAO specifications when stored for 14 days at 54±2°C (Khozimy and Ramdan ,2018) .

Table (4): Effect of storage at 54 °C on level impurities mancosil plas 50% and mancosil 72 % .

Storage period days	Mancosil plas 50						Mencosil 70 %	
	Impurities Copper + metalaxyl						Impurities Mancozeb + metalaxyl	
	Cd Ppm	Pb Ppm	FAO Maximum g/kg	As	FAO Maximum g/kg	2, 6 dimethyl aniline	ETU	2, 6 dimethyl aniline
0	UND	134.11	175.55	2.34	35.11	00.00	0.09	0.0043
1	UND	134.11	175.55	2.35	35.11	00.00	0.09	0.0034
3	UND	151.00	175.00	2.31	35.00	0.0054	0.11	0.0076
7	UND	149.09	175.00	3.51	35.00	0.0068	0.11	0.0085
14	UND	153.08	174.05	3.43	34.81	0.079	0.27	0.0089
21	UND	154.00	170.00	3.55	34.00	0.080	0.35	0.0290
28	UND	153.00	169.05	3.11	33.81	0.089	0.46	0.040

FAO maximum(Cd) = 0.1 x b mg/dl where b copper content by g/kg.

FAO maximum(As) = 0.1 x b mg/dl where b copper content by g/kg.

FAO maximum(pb) = 0.5x b mg/dl where b copper content by g/k.

4. Effect of influence UV ray on level impurities mancosil plas 50% WP and mancosil 72 % WP :

The Data illustrate in Table (5) show the effect of influence UV ray on the level Cadmium lead and arsenic mg/kg in testes copper products. Cadmium not detected in both mancosil plas , also showed decrease the amount of Lead and Arsenic 154 and 3.34 (mg/kg) respectively in mancosil plas 50

, whereas the percentage loss of Lead , and Arsenic were 153% and 3.11 respectively, for influence UV ray 48 hours. Also show that the impurities ethylene thio urea (ETU and 2,6 dimethyl aniline of Mancozeb 72 % WP before storage were 0.09 and 0.0041 respectively , before influence UV ray become 0.49 % and 0.069 after influence UV ray 48 hrs.

Table (5): Effect of influence UV ray on level impurities mancosil plas 50% WP and mancosil 72 % WP.

Storage period hours	Mancosil plas 50%						Mencosil 70 %	
	Copper + metalaxyl						Mancozeb + metalaxyl	
	Impurities						Impurities	
	Cd	Pb	FAO Maximum g/kg	As	FAO Maximum g/kg	2, 6 dimethyl aniline	ETU	2, 6 dimethyl aniline
0	UND	134.11	177.95	2.89	35.59	00.00	0.09	0.0043
1	UND	134.11	177.95	2.43	35.59	0.0043	0.09	0.0043
5	UND	151.00	175.00	2.99	35.00	0.0067	0.09	0.0067
8	UND	149.09	174.25	3.31	34.85	0.0076	0.12	0.0076
12	UND	153.08	170.55	3.11	34.11	0.0079	0.21	0.0079
24	UND	154.00	167.80	3.34	33.56	0.045	0.29	0.045
36	UND	153.00	167.8	3.34	33.56	0.055	0.35	0.055
48	UND	154.00	166.60	3.34	33.32	0.069	0.49	0.069

FAO maximum (Cd) = 0.1 x b mg/dl where b copper content by g/kg.

FAO maximum (As) = 0.1 x b mg/dl where b copper content by g/kg.

FAO maximum (Pb) = 0.5x b mg/dl where b copper content by g/k.

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Potential of *Megaselia scalaris* (Diptera: Phoridae), as biocontrol agent of
Eobania vermiculata under semi field conditions

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Abstract:

Terrestrial gastropods are economic important pests that distributed in many Governments in Egypt causing severe damage to different important plants. The overuse of molluscicides against these destructive pests leads to more environmental pollution. So, searching for biological control agent became necessary to avoid the hazard of molluscicides. *Megaselia scalaris* (Lowe) (Diptera: Phoridae) has a potential to become a biocontrol agent of terrestrial snail *Bradybaena similaris* (Ferussac). This study aimed to shed light on the role of malacophagous insect *M. scalaris* in controlling terrestrial snails *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) (Gastropoda: Helicidae) under semi field conditions. Results of releasing *M. Scalaris* within *E.vermiculata* plots indicate an extrusive relation between time and mortality rates either of juvenile or mature snails and time needed for total mortality was reported significantly longer period in mature snails than juvenile snails. It could be concluded that *M. scalaris* may play an important role in controlling terrestrial gastropods.

Keywords

Gastropods, *Eobania vermiculata*, malacophagous insects, *Megaselia scalaris*, biological control and semi field.

Introduction

Terrestrial gastropods are economic important pests that distributed in many Governments in Egypt causing severe damage to different important plants (Desoky, 2018; Azzam and Abd El-Hady, 2018). The overuse of molluscicides against these destructive pests leads to more environmental pollution (Godan, 1983). So, searching for biological control agent became necessary. Azzam and Tawfik (2005) recorded the existence of 16 species of terrestrial malacophagous insects, including four sarcophagid species of which *Wohlfartia* sp. was reported only on slugs. Two drosophilid species and two sphaerocerid and four

Phorid were also reported. Zaki *et al.* (2019) carried out a survey of aquatic and terrestrial malacophagous insects associated with snails during 2016-2018 in Sharquia Governorate. The survey revealed the existence of four terrestrial and three aquatic snail species associated with three aquatic and three terrestrial malacophagous insect species including *Megaselia scalaris* (Loew) and *Petrostecus barbarous*. Phorids are amongst the most biologically diverse families of insects (Brown, 2018). Many phorid flies are parasitoids of injured hosts, (Brown, 2000 and Hash, 2014).

The definition of a scavenger is an organism that consumes dead or

decaying organic material (Lincoln *et al.*, 1998), whereas a parasitoid is one that feeds on a single host, ultimately causing its death (As opposed to predators that feed on more than one host or true parasites that feed on a host, but do not kill it (Godfray, 1994). Females of the phorid fly *Megaselia steptoeae* Hartop *et al.* (Diptera: Phoridae) were found to be quickly attracted to crushed glass snails of the species *Oxychilus draparnaudi* (Beck) (Gastropoda: Oxychilidae) (Brown and Vendetti, 2020). *M. scalaris* was recorded to parasitize only certain species of adult insect or larvae and snails (Ahmad and Ho, 1980; Robinson, 1975 and Idris and Abdullah, 1997). Idris and Abdullah (1997) found in laboratory studies that *M. scalaris* has a potential to become a biocontrol agent of *Bradybaena similis* (Ferussac). They reported that 55% of *B. similis* ,exposed to *M. scalaris* was parasitized. However, percent parasitism of the snail in the field is ranged between 10 and 35%. Lower parasitism rate was probably due to low parasitoid population in the field as a result of heavy use of pesticides. The larval developmental time was significantly longer ($p < 0.05$) when larvae were fed on live *B. similis* than on its tissue extract (Idris *et al.*, 2001). Disney (1994) reported that the development of *M. scalaris* larva and its parasitism rate is quite dependent on host species, temperature and nutrient provided by the host. Bohart and Gressitt (1951) recorded nine species of *Megaselia* including *M. scalaris* as a snail predator in larval stage. Tawfik *et al.* (1999) studied the biology of *M. scalaris* by feeding on three terrestrial snail species ,as malacophagous insects through its larval stages which predate many snails through each larval instar in gregarious behavior . Rare investigation in the role of

malacophagous insects in semi field conditions.

Therefore, this study aimed to shed light on the role of malacophagous insect *M. scalaris* in controlling terrestrial snails *Eobania vermiculata* (Müller) under semi field conditions to reduce the overuse of pesticides which increase the environmental pollution .

Materials and methods

1. Samples collection:

Samples of terrestrial snails were collected from infested plants by hand picking from Great Cairo, Egypt during 2016 -2019 .Snails and slugs were identified according to Godan (1983); Cowie (2002); Auffenberg and Stange (2009) and Baker (2009) .

2. Rearing of predator:

Rearing of *M. scalaris* started with collecting the larvae attacking snails from natural habitats. When the larvae pupated, the pupae were transferred individually into test tubes covered with piece of cotton. Emerged flies were confined as coupled in similar test tubes .Small ribbon of rice paper soaked with sucrose solution was hanging down in the tube as a source of sucrose ,one small crushed snail was added to each tube as a source of protein.

3. Rearing of gastropods:

After collecting and identification gastropods, they washed thoroughly in fine metallic net under strong stream of tap water then washed by distilled water, take some individuals in petri-dish with distilled water and examined it under research microscope to check the presence of microorganisms . This process repeated several times until look remove all external associated organisms.

Rearing of *E. vermiculata* snail was carried out by placing the examined individuals in plastic cages after sterilizing it by ethanol alcohol and substrates with sterilized clay and

irrigated with distilled water. After egg laying, the eggs were washed gently by distilled water and transfers to sterilize petri dishes contained sterilized clay. The petri dishes were then placed in dark place until hatching. The newly hatched snails were transferred gently to new sterilized cages as mentioned above and supplied with some lettuce leaves after washing it thoroughly by strong stream of tape water to remove associated organisms then wash with distilled water and introduced to the newly hatching snails.

4. Experimental test:

Twelve transparence plastic boxes, each measured (50 x25x20 cm) were used as mini plot experiments. Each box was sterilized by ethanol alcohol 70% and substrates with sterilized clay (5cm height), moisten with dechlorinated water. Six of these boxes were provided with 100 mature snails of *E. vermiculata* for each, while the other six boxes provide with 100 juvenile snails per box from the same species. Some lettuce leaves were added to every plot as a source of food .Every plot was covered with perlon gauze and confirmed by rubber band. 100 couples (Male and female) of *M. scalaris* flies were confined in ten plastic test tubes(10 males and females /tube) ,partially covered with piece of cotton and contained mall ribbon of rice paper soaked with sucrose solution as source of food for flies .One tube was added to every cage from five plots for both mature and juvenile snails. The sixth box from mature and juvenile snails was left without adding the tube contained flies, as a control treatment. Through the first five days the mini plots were observed from the transparence wall boxes to avoid escaping of the flies before mating and oviposition which take 1-4 days (Tawfik *et al.*,1999), and dead snails were recorded.

After five days mini plots began examined daily and number of dead snails was recorded and collected at the corner of plots without removing it from the cages to excuse propagation of the flies and gave chance to larvae to attack another snails. Escaping flies during cages examination was neglected to imitate that was occur in nature .

5. Statistical Analysis:

Differences between mortality rates for mature and juvenile snails were analyzed by ANOVA and T test value using PSPP program and time needed for mortality analyzed by Qui square test using Ldp line program .

Results and discussion

Mortality of both juvenile and mature stages of *E. vermiculata* snail was summarized in Table (1). As seen in this table, high extrusive relation between time and mortality rates either of juvenile or mature snails. It was noticed that the first three and four days for juvenile or mature snails respectively, have no mortality this was maybe due to lacking larvae which predate the snails where pre oviposition period and incubation period of eggs take from 1-4 days (Tawfik *et al.*, 1999) . Table (1) showed also that time needed for total mortality was reported longer period in mature snails than juvenile snails. This is because larvae consumed a greater number of small snails than large or mature snails. Tawfik *et al.* (1999) reported high consumption rate of *M .scalaris* on *E. vermiculata* immature snails than mature snails and also on other snails that were smallest in size than *E. vermiculata* snail . Disney (1994) reported that the development of *M. scalaris* larva and its parasitism rate is quite dependent on host species, and nutrient provided by the host. It was noticed also that daily mortality rate increase day after day due to progress of larval development that predate a greater number of snails

through late instars than early instars . Tawfik *et al.* (1999), mentioned that daily consumption of different larval instars of *M. scalaris* *E. vermiculata* increase as the larval predator develops to reach the maximum in the mature larva. Idris and Abdullah, 1997, found in laboratory studies that *M. scalaris* has a potential to become a biocontrol agent of *Bradybaena similaris* (Fer.).

$r=0.9$ and 0.72 for both juvenile and mature snails respectively. Lt 25, 50, 75, and 99 were significantly longer in mature snails than in juvenile snails. Sallam and El-Wakeil (2012) mentioned that juvenile snail stages were more vulnerable for predator attacking, than adults .

Table (2) showed high correlation between time and mortality

Table (1): Daily and accumulation mortality rate of *Eobania* predating by *Megaselia scalaris* under semi field conditions .

Time /day	Mortality of <i>Eobania vermiculata</i>			
	Juvenile snail		Mature snails	
	Rate % of dead snails in day	Rate % of accumulated dead snails in day	Rate % of dead snails in day	Rate % of Accumulated dead snails Consumption in day
1	0	0	0	0
2	0	0	0	0
3	0	0	0	0
4	5.67	5.67	0	0
5	6.5	12.165	3	3
6	11.335	23.5	4.165	7.165
7	15.835	39.335	5.665	12.835
8	21.67	61	7.165	19.99
9	22.5	83.5	9	28.995
10	16,5	100	10.835	39.835
11			13.335	53.165
12			15.335	68.5
13			17.5	86
14			11	97
15			3	100

Table (2): Time mortality relationship of *Eobania vermiculata* snail predating by *Megaselia scalaris* under semi field conditions .

Mortality ratios %	Probit linear of time in days needed for <i>Eobania</i> snail mortality of			
	Juvenile snails		Mature snails	
25	5.8677		8.3104	
50	7.0361		11.6415	
75	8.4371		16.3079	
99	13.1619		37.2295	
Slope	8.5530		4.6077	
P	0.0008		00000	
	Calculated	Tabulated	Calculated	Tabulated
X ²	26.7837	15.5	3203223	22.35
R	0.8969 (0.09)	0.632	0.7174 (0.72)	0.514

It could be concluded that *M. scalaris* may play an important role in controlling terrestrial gastropods. However, further study needs to be carried out before any decision can be made regarding for using in field application of gastropod control. Such studies may probably on the safety for useful organisms. These studies should be done in laboratory before field-testing is conducted in fields.

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Population species diversity of soil fauna is influenced by agricultural practices

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Abstract:

The study was carried out in different soil occupation systems: Tomato and maize, comparing with fallow using pitfall traps installed per treatment. The captured surface soil fauna was listed according to the Ascending Hierarchic classification (AHC) (Roux,1985). Fauna were classified into the five main functional group, herbivores, detrivores , carnivores , parasitoids and pollen grain transmitters. The community composition in the period of this study was determined using the Shannon-Wiener and Simpson indices of diversity, slight difference in the species diversities among the two cover of cultivation was observed comparing with fallow. The highest abundance was found under maize growing conditions (533 individuals), the number decreased to (357) under tomato and the lowest abundance values were found in fallow (213 individuals). The different systems of soil occupation showed different abundance and diversity, demonstrating how soil occupation interferes with the dynamics of the invertebrate soil fauna.

Introduction

Soil fauna are very sensitive to agricultural practices, with their numbers and diversity becoming severely reduced in intensively cultivated soils. Consequently, natural systems usually contain richer communities than managed ones. No-tillage environment can have a positive, negative or neutral effect on pest-, crop-, and biological control interaction.

Population species diversity of soil fauna is influenced by agricultural practices (Wallwork, 1976). The practices that adversely affect fauna population include mechanized land clearing and ploughing (Bigler *et al.*,

1995a and 1995b). On the other hand, soil- and crop-management techniques that favor and enhance the activity of soil fauna include mulch farming (Maia *et al.*, 1991), no-tillage (Rizk and Mikhail, 1999), cover crops, agroforestry and other ecologically compatible farming systems (Lee, 1995). On the other hand, population densities of soil animals and their functional (Trophic) groups are responsible to a great extent for N mineralization in such agro-ecosystem (Persson, 1989). Most of this mineralization is affected by bacterivores, fungivores and herbivores, that feed on N-poor food,

have little influence on N mineralization.

The aim of the present study is to investigate the effect of no-tillage and conventional tillage practices and the type of cover crops as well seasonal variations, on the activity density of soil fauna taxa in El-Marazeeq village, Giza Governorate.

Materials and methods

1. Study area :

The experiment was conducted at village of El- Marazeeq - Giza Governorate during the period between September 2014 and October 2015 . The study area consists of 1/3 feddan (1 feddan = 4200 m²). The area was cultivated with tomato and rotation with cultivated maize and between two cultivated leave the land fallow. The aim of this study was to investigate the effect of crop type, crop rotation, the effect of tillage for preparing for cultivated crop and different fertilizing used in different crop type on the activity density of arthropods and the most characteristic taxa in both plantations.

To cultivated tomato used as the normal cultivation treatment. Also, normal agricultural practices were followed in the same plot to cultivated maize, including the addition of N-chemical fertilizer (Table 1).

2. Method of sampling soil mesofauna:

Different cultivated systems were compared using pitfall traps method as described by Southwood (1978) , Slingsby and Cook (1986) and Southwood and Henderson (2000), pitfall traps are cups sunk into the ground flush with the soil surface which collect organisms that fall into them. In this method the number of individuals trapped is primarily dependent on their locomotion activity and these are therefore called activity-density rather than population- density (Kromp, 1990) and Mikhail, 1993). The activity-

density cannot be related to the abundance per unit area (Kromp,1990) but, is taken as number per trap, (Mikhail,1993).

This experiment continued for 13 months, ten pitfall traps were distributed in each plot of the mentioned field, cultivated with different cover crop and when its fallow; samples were taken at every two weeks intervals from each cultivation and fallow, samples were taken by setting the traps for 24 hours .The contents of the pitfall traps were then transferred to the laboratory where the captured arthropods identified and counted for each treatment.

3.Treatment of data:

The captured surface soil fauna was listed according to the Ascending Hierarchic Classification (AHC) (Roux,1985).

4. Functional groups:

The breakdown of trophic group based on feeding strategies and method of locomotion in the soil (**Wallwork, 1976**); as soil arthropods eat their food and mix up the soil.

5. The abundance:

The frequency values of the most abundant species were classified into three classes according to the system adopted by Weis Fogh (1984);" Constant species "were considered as those found in more than 50 % of the sample, "accessory species" were those found in 25-50 % of samples and "accidental species" were those found less than 25% of the samples. On the other hand, the classification of dominance values were done according to Weigmann (1973) system and El-Shahawy and El-Basheer (1992) in which the species were divided into five groups based on the values of dominance in the samples; eudominant species (>30% individuals), dominant species (>10-30% individuals), subdominant species (5-10% individuals), resident species (1-5%

individuals) and sub-resident species (1% individuals).

6. Species diversity:

The biodiversity of soil fauna collected were estimated by using equilibrium. Diversity of collected arthropods was determined for samples pooled over one different patterns of cover cultivation crop. It was measured by diversity indices that reflect the number of species (richness) in the samples.

Two common indices were computed, the Shannon-Wiener (1963) (Shannon and Wiener index "H" and the Simpson (1949) index "S". They were calculated as described by Ludwig and Reynolds (1988).

$$H' = -\sum (ni/n) \ln (ni/n) \text{ and } S = \sum (ni/n)^2$$

Where "ni" is the number of individuals belonging to the ith of "S" taxa in the sample and "n" is the total number of individuals in the sample ; "H" is more sensitive to changes in rare taxa , while "S" is more responsive to changes in the most dominant species (Ludwig and Reynolds, 1988).

Results and discussion

1. Arthropods collected by pitfall traps from tomato, maize and fallow during 2014 / 2015:

As shown in Table (2) arthropods captured by pitfall – trap method belonging to 12 orders , 8 of them are insect orders (Coleoptera , Collembola , Dermaptera , Diptera , Hemiptera , Hymenoptera , Lepidoptera and Orthoptera and other for groups : Isopoda, soil mites , Acari and Snails. The total population of all surveyed arthropods reached 1103 individuals some of these arthropods considered parameters which determine the differentiation between both covering crops, the most important parameter is collembola , which among the most abundant soil – dwelling arthropods. In present study, arthropods collected by pitfall traps from maize was more than

in tomato and fallow. The increasing N rat causing increased the fauna population (Sharshir, 1998) as in the Maize crop which received N-chemical fertilizer. The maize cultivation was characterized by the abundance of collembolan, a detritivores soil fauna which were greatest in soils treated with mineral fertilizer plus mulch (Sisti *et al.*, 2004).

In the present study, the number of collembolan obtained in maize was higher (138 individuals) than in tomato (73 individuals), this number decreased to (51 individuals) at fallow. Collembolan was accounted for 23.75% and considered as accidental species according to system adapted by Weis Fogh (1984) and it was dominant species (10-30% individual) as shown the classification of dominance values which was done by (Weigmann, 1973). Abd El-Karim *et al.* (2016) indicated that the most important parameter is collembola which among the most abundant of all soil – dwelling arthropods and represent the greater fraction of biomass of invertebrates in the considered soil (as soil macro fauna) and play a vital role in soil solvation and hence they can be as indicators for soil fertility. Also, Ghallab *et al.* (2007), agree that, Collembola abundance serve as good indicators of soil health. It has been shown that collembolans prefer high soil moisture (Rodgers, 1997) . This suggests that the greater abundance of collembolans was a result of the greater quality and quantity of litter in the vegetation plots. Collembola play a significant role in various soil processes such as decomposition, soil formation and nutrient cycling (Behan-Pelletier, 2003).

Also, in the present study, Table (2) showed that, spiders were found with highest number at maize (105 individuals) decreased to (36 individuals) at tomato but more found at

fallow (65 individuals). True spider was accounted for 18.68% and considered as accidental species according to system adapted by Weis Fogh (1984) and it was dominant species (10-30% individual) as shown the classification of dominance values which was done by (Weigmann, 1973). Spiders were more in the maize plots than tomato plots. This result indicated that vegetation type may be influenced spider abundance. This result indicated that vegetation type may be influenced spider abundance. Tahir and Butt (2009) indicated that, the spider densities vary with phenology of crops. Also, (Liu *et al.*, 2003) indicated that, the density of the spiders in the fields increase with the increase in plant size and complexity, then smaller plant host fewer spider than tall ones. Also, Bardwell and Averill (1997) and Malony *et al.* (2003) showed spiders preyed upon collembolan and small dipterous larvae located in the ground.

Diptera was represented by four families; Muscidae, Fannidae (ditrevars), Syrphidae (carnivores) and Bombyliidae *Lucilla* sp. (parasite). Muscidae was the highest number (25 individuals) at tomato cultivation decreased to (9 individuals) in maize cultivation. Also, Fannidae was the highest number (10 individuals) at tomato. Hymenoptera was represented by Apidae (pollinators), its highest at tomato (5 individuals), decreased to (2 individuals) at maize. Also, Formicidae, these insects were found in tomato and maize more than in fallow. But, the beneficial Formicidae represented by, (*Componontus maculatus*, *Monomarium* sp. and *Pheidole* sp.). The largest number of Hymenoptera was obtained in the tomato cultivation (112 individuals) decreased to (102 individuals) in maize cultivation and the lowest number (21 individuals) in fallow. *Monomarium* sp. was a

as accidental species according to system adapted by Weis Fogh (1984) and it was dominant species (10-30% individual) as shown the classification of dominance values which was done by (Weigmann, 1973).

Also, Hemiptera represented by two herbivorous families, Aphididae and Cicadellidae. *Aphis* sp. recorded at the highest number (5 individuals) in the tomato cultivation but Cicadellidae recorded the highest number (18 individuals) in the maize cultivation. Carabidae and Staphilinidae were found in tomato cultivation with more numbers than the numbers recorded in maize cultivation and fallow. But mite found at tomato and decreased in maize cultivation. The activity- density of soil mites revealed differences between tomato, maize and fallow. The highest number found in tomato cultivation (6 individuals) decreased to (2,1 individuals) in fallow and maize, respectively. Soil mites accounted for (0.82%) of the total captured fauna and considered as accidental and there for they were subrecent (>1% individuals) population. The number of Oribatid mites was correlated with the concentration of nitrate nitrogen regardless of the soil types. This fact may indicate that the determination of the number of oribatid mites is a useful, indicator of the amount of nitrogen mineralized from organic matter, Enami *et al.* (1999). For other arthropods namely isopoda was found at maize cultivation more than tomato and fallow. *Anthicus* sp., *Tropinota squalida*, Staphilinidae, *Labidura confuse*, *Labidura riparia*, Diptera, (Fanniidae, Muscidae), Lepidoptera, Orthoptera, *Gryllus domesticus*, were accounted (1.90,1.27,1.18,"4.35,1.63",2.45"1.36, 3.72",1.18,1.18,1.18), respectively and considered as accidental species and they were accidental according to Weis Fogh (1984) abundance (>25%) and it

was Recedent (R) (1-5%) dominant value (Weigmann, 1973).

Tables (1 and 2) showed that, the fallow plot had low numbers of soil fauna (64 individuals) in September 2014, and they become higher (180 individuals) in October 2014 when organic manure was added to cultivated tomato. Also, increasing N rate in Jun 2015 to cultivated maize, causing to increased population from (44 individuals) in Jun to (134 individuals) in July, (Sisti *et al.* (2004) approved this result, that plot which received N –chemical fertilizer increasing the fauna. Soil organisms are not uniformly distributed throughout the soil habitat.

They tend to be patchy in distribution and concentrated in areas that provide space (between soil particles), moisture and resources such as food (Ettema and Wardle, 2002). Collection of soil fauna from the two crops cover cultivation as well as the fallow, of the present study, gives an idea about the perturbation of community structure of soil fauna under such different treatments. The most pronounced differences were those associated with the total number of individuals as well as the variation between the fallow treatment on one hand, and each of the cultivation treatments, (Tomato, maize). Microclimate modification, food resource availability, and land management practices (e.g., tillage, organic resource use, crop rotation, and application of agrochemicals such as pesticides, herbicides, and inorganic fertilizers) are known to either positively or negatively influence the diversity and abundance of soil fauna communities (Nhamo, 2007 and Gianessi, 2010).

The activity and diversity of soil organisms are directly affected by the reduction of soil organic matter content, and indirectly by the reduction in plant

diversity and productivity. Also, Table (2) show that, Formicidae, collembola, spiders and Diptera are the most dominant taxa in the catches of the pitfall traps. Collembolans were the dominant category using the pitfall trap method. This study has shown that collembolans were one of the more abundant orders found in cultivation (Maize and tomato). There were more twice as many collembolans found in the vegetation than in the fallow.

2. Monthly Variation in numbers of individuals and taxa :

Most of the micro arthropod groups showed higher abundance on early sampling dates (October, 180 individual) and on later sampling dates (July, August and September) (134, 149 and 147 individual) respectively in both growing crops. A similar observation in micro arthropod abundance fluctuations has been noted in studies conducted in warm season crops (Schrader and Lingnau, 1997).

The main results of this study population density of Acarina, Collembola, ants were affected with temperature. Rizk *et al.* (2000) indicated that the variations in numbers of the collembolan closely follow the elevation of temperature from December to April which are the hottest months. Vats and Narula (1993), and Rizk (2002) found that population density of Acarina was positively correlated with temperature.

Van der Putten (2010) the main abiotic factors are climate, including temperature and moisture, soil texture and soil structure, salinity and pH. Overall, climate influences the physiology of soil organisms, such that their activity and growth increases at higher temperatures and soil moistures. As climate conditions differ across the globe and also, in the same places, between seasons, the climatic conditions to which soil organisms are exposed vary strongly. Soil organisms

vary in their optimal temperature and moisture ranges, and this variation is life-stage specific, e.g. larvae may prefer other optima than adults.

3. Functional group:

Ghabbour (1991) pointed out that soil fauna can be divided into trophic groups in different ecosystems. These trophic groups are herbivores (harmful potential agricultural pests), carnivores (Beneficial, natural enemies of herbivores) and detritivores (Essential to soil fertility and are well representable under all crops) (Hussein and Mikhail 1998). Rizk *et al.* (2000) show that soil fauna breakdown into the three mains functional (Trophic) group carnivores, herbivores and Detritivores, under different treatment. Table (3) and Figure (1) show the results of the breakdown of the surface soil fauna in the different cultivation and follow into the main functional groups : Herbivores , detrivores , predators” Carnivores” , parasites and pollen grain transmitters.

3.1. Detrivores group:

The collembolans, ants and dipteran were the main groups of arthropods found in the soils numbers of these groups were higher when maize cultivation than tomato cultivation but the lowest number on fallow . Generally, the detrivores are the most abundant group or recorded 57.12 % of the total pitfall trap catches.

3.2. Carnivores or predators group:

Recorded 30.55 % and represented by true spiders , robben flies *Syrphus corollae* (Diptera : Syrphidae) , *Ciccendela aulica* and *Ciccendela melanocholica* (Coleoptera: Ciccendelidae) , *Anthicus* sp. (Coleoptera : Anthicidae) and beetles (Coleoptera: Carabidae). The true spiders are the more abundant than other predators. This group was found in high population in the plot when cultivated with maize (186 individuals) decreased to (64 individuals) when plot

cultivated with tomato increased to (87 individuals) when plots was followed.

3.3. Herbivores group:

Represented by aphid , leaf hoppers , grass hoppers , Lepidoptera , Acrididae and Gryllidae accounted for 9.16 % . Maize received the highest population of herbivores (43 individuals) decreased to (33 individuals) when tomato was cultivated.

3.4. Parasitoids group:

Recorded by 1.09 % found in high population in the maize cultivation (9 individuals) and the (2 individuals) at fallow but decreased to (1 individuals) when tomato was cultivated.

3.5. The pollen grain transmitters:

Recorded by 2.09 % and represented by bee, Apidae (*Apis mellifera*) Hymenoptera , collected in tomato cultivation (15 individuals) decreased to (5 individuals) in maize cultivation. Scherer–Loenzen (2005) indicated that the diversity of functional groups in general had more pronounced effects than the numbers of species, emphasizing the importance of functional traits of species. This study indicated that the activity – density of predator (true spiders and collembola were greatly higher in maize cultivation could be a result of the highest numbers of hobivares and detrivares groups , this deduction is supported with Malony *et al.* (2003) and Rizk *et al.* (2009) who showed that spiders preyed upon collembola and small dipterous larvae located in the ground. Also, we found that the abundance of herbivores on maize more than in tomato and fallow.

In this study found that Detritivores were abundant in cultivation more than fallow plot due to the surplus amount of water used and subsequent increase in soil humidity as well as the higher availability of organic matter (Rizk, 2002 and Rizk, *et al.* 2006) approved this result. The tomato

plots recorded the highest of Detritivores due to the highest available of organic matter and the increase of soil humidity in tomato plots, consequently, population of ants and collembolan increased twice.

Also, our results reveal that the pollen grain transmitters recorded the highest numbers when tomato cultivated because it is more flowering than maize. The use of different flowering plants can produce diverse effects on agro ecosystem management: for example, the nutritional value of

pollen and nectar can be largely different, strongly affecting food supplied to beneficial parasitoids (Lu *et al.*, 2014). In natural ecosystems, spiders constitute the main invertebrate predatory group hence play an important ecological function in pest control. Araneae being mostly polyphagous predators, can significantly affect the population dynamics of many phytophagous and saprophagous invertebrates (Ekschmitt *et al.*, 1997 and Ziesche and Roth, 2008).

Table (1): Crops cultivated and agricultural practices in the study area during the study period between September 2014 and October 2015.

Months	Crop Type	Agricultural Practices
September 2014	Fallow	Ploughing + organic manure at the recommended rates + irrigation
October	Tomato	The field which will receive the seedling must be humid and holes must be made in order to deposit the seedling. Tomato plants were transplanted at both sides of the terraces in hills of 40 cm.
November	Tomato	Fertilization sulfur + super phosphate before transplantation and second, 60 days + irrigation
December	Tomato	Third after 100 days + irrigation + sulfur + super phosphate
January 2015	Tomato	Added different fertilization sulfur and Potassium + irrigation
February	Tomato	Crop collection + sulfur super
March	Fallow	Crop collection
April	Fallow	Maize were sown in rows over the terraces in ridges 15 cm apart N-chemical fertilizer
May	Maize	Ploughing + Irrigation
June	Maize	Super + Nitrogen 33
July	Maize	Nitrogen 33 + Potassium (2200) + Nitrate (700)
August	Maize	120 days collected
September	Maize	After crop collection + the collected Hoeing
October	Fallow	Follow

Table (2): Diversity between soil/litter and fauna at maize, tomato cultivation and fallow

Taxa	F	M	T	Total	Frequency and Dominance %
Isopoda	1	5	0	6	0.54 (A, Sr)
Soil Mites	2	1	6	9	0.82 (A, Sr)
Snails	0	0	1	1	0.09 (A, Sr)
Spider	65	105	36	206	18.68 (A, D)
Coleoptera	0	7	0	7	0.63 (A, Sr)
Anthicidae					
<i>Anthicus sp.</i>	2	13	6	21	1.90 (A, R)
Carabidae	1	1	2	4	0.36 (A, Sr)
Cicindelidae	0	3	0	3	0.27 (A, Sr)
<i>Ciccendela aulica</i>	0	7	0	7	0.63 (A, Sr)
<i>Ciccendela melanocholica</i>	0	2	0	2	0.18 (A, Sr)
Elateridae	0	3	0	3	0.27 (A, Sr)
Scarabaeidae	1	0	0	1	0.09 (A, Sr)
<i>Aphodius sp.</i>	3	2	0	5	0.45 (A, Sr)
<i>Tropinata squalida</i>	3	0	11	14	1.27 (A, R)
Staphilinidae	3	3	7	13	1.18 (A, R)
<i>Paedrus affierii</i>	0	1	0	1	0.09 (A, Sr)
<i>Atheta sp.</i>	0	1	0	1	0.09 (A, Sr)
Collembola	51	138	73	262	23.75 (A, D)
Dermoptera	2	0	1	3	0.27 (A, Sr)
Labiduridae					
<i>Labidura confuse</i>	13	26	9	48	4.35 (A, R)
<i>Labidura riparia</i>	1	17	0	18	1.63 (A, R)
Diptera	7	9	11	27	2.45 (A, R)
<i>Lucilia sp.</i>	0	7	0	7	0.63 (A, Sr)
Faniidae	2	3	10	15	1.36 (A, R)
Muscidae	7	9	25	41	3.72 (A, R)
<i>Musca domestica</i>	1	6	6	13	1.18 (A, R)
Syrphidae					
<i>Syrphus corollae</i>	0	0	3	3	0.27 (A, Sr)
Embioptera	0	0	1	1	0.09 (A, Sr)
<i>Geotomus intrusus</i>	0	1	0	1	0.09 (A, Sr)
Lygaeidae	0	1	1	2	0.18 (A, Sr)
Hemiptera					
<i>Aphis sp.</i>	2	1	5	8	0.73 (A, Sr)
Cicadellidae	2	18	3	23	2.09 (A, A)
Hymenoptera	1	2	5	8	0.73 (A, Sr)
Apidae	1	2	5	8	0.73 (A, Sr)
<i>Apis mellifera</i>	1	1	5	7	0.63 (A, Sr)
Braconidae	2	2	1	5	0.45 (A, Sr)
Formicidae	1	4	0	5	0.45 (A, Sr)
<i>Camponotus maculatus</i>	1	4	0	5	0.45 (A, Sr)
<i>Monomorium sp.</i>	21	102	112	235	21.31 (A, D)
<i>Pheidole sp.</i>	0	6	7	13	1.18 (A, R)
Lepidoptera	1	0	1	2	1.18 (A, R)
Orthoptera	0	2	0	2	1.18 (A, R)
Acrididae	2	5	1	8	0.73 (A, Sr)
<i>Aiolopus sp.</i>	7	3	1	11	1.00 (A, R)
Gryllidae	1	2	1	4	0.36 (A, Sr)
<i>Gryllus domesticus</i>	5	7	1	13	1.18 (A, R)
<i>Gryllus bimaculatus</i>	0	1	0	1	0.09 (A, Sr)
	213	533	357	1103	

Frequency (abundance), by Weis Fog , Dominance, by Weigmann, > 50 % = Constant (C)

> 30 % = Eudominant (E) 1 - 5 % Recedent (R) , 25 - 50 % = Accessory (ac)

10 - 30 % =

Dominant (D) > 1 % = Subrecedent (Sr) , > 25 % = Accidental (A)

5 - 10 % =

Subdominant (sd)

Table (3): Breakdown of surface soil fauna into trophic group in different cover cultivation from September 2014 to October 2015 .

Functional Group	Fallow	Maize	Tomato	Total	Dominance%
Detrivores	96	290	244	630	57.12
Herbivores	25	43	33	101	9.16
Parasitoids	2	9	1	12	1.09
Predators	87	186	64	327	30.55
Poll. Gr.Trans.	3	5	15	23	2.09
Total	213	533	357	1103	

Figure (1): Breakdown of surface soil fauna into trophic group in different cover cultivation from September 2014 to October 2015.

4. Species composition , species richness and species abundance :

The collected arthropods were summarized by orders in Table (4) and show their abundance, frequency (richness) and dominance. As shown in Table (4) and Figures (2 and 3) members of Hymenoptera involved the greatest numbers of soil fauna. This order Hymenoptera accounted for 25.93 % of the total captured arthropods. The largest numbers of Hymenoptera was obtained in the tomato cultivation (135 individuals) decreased to (123 individuals) in maize cultivation. In general ant populations are the highest members of this order, they are responsive to change environmental conditions of soil. This result approved by Ghallab *et al.* (2007), she found that the highest number of ants in the tomato cultivation. Adopted by Weis Fogh (1984) and it was dominant species (>30% individuals). Presence of ants could be due to the soil type which is based on the nutrients and a wide variety of decaying organic

materials,(Wallwork, 1976). The Hymenoptera considered as accessory species according to system.

The beneficial collembola represented by 23.75 % of the total cached soil fauna. Table (4) show that collembolan was considered as Dominant species (>30% individual) as shown the classification of dominance values which was done by (Weigmann, 1973). This result is in good accordance with Fountain and Hopken (2004), who showed that collembolan (springtails) are abundant and widespread in soil ecosystems and are important members of the composer community. Rizk *et al.* (2009) indicated that their abundance serves as good indicators of soil health. Number of collembolan was increased in maize cultivated as planted in hot month's this result approved by (Rizk *et al.*, 2000).The variation in numbers of the collembolan closely follow the elevation of temperature from December to April which there was hottest month's. Also, Table (4) show

the frequency of true spiders constitute high degree in abundance in the maize cultivation (105 individuals) while tomato received the lowest numbers (36 individuals).

Spider was considered as dominant species (18.68 %). The order Diptera followed in the abundance, accounted for 9.97 % of the total captured arthropod. Diptera was considered as accidental species (>25%) and it was subdominant (5– 10 %). The highest number found tomato cultivation (57 individual) decreased to (36 individual) in the maize cultivation. Order Hemiptera was considered as Resident species (1 – 5 % Resident) ,

the abundance of their individuals accounted to 2.81 % of the total arthropods . It includes the major piercing sucking pests causing economic damage to the plant host, they represented by two species belonging to two families, they are *Aphis gossypii* (Aphidae) and *Agallia aegyptiaca* (Cicadellidae). Members of Acarina , Lepidoptera snail and isopoda are the lowest frequent taxa among the soil fauna recorded and they were accounted for (0.82 , 0.18 , 0.09 and 0.54%) respectively , and considered as accidental species and therefore they were subresident (>1% individuals).

Table (4): Species composition, species richness and species abundance.

Order	Fallow	Maize	Tomato	Total	Frequency and Dominance %
Isopoda	1	5	0	6	0.54 (a/ Sr)
Acarina	2	1	6	9	0.82 (a/ Sr)
Snails	0	0	1	1	0.09 (a/ Sr)
Araneae	65	105	36	206	18.68 (a/D)
Collembola	51	138	73	262	23.75 (a/D)
Coleoptera	13	43	26	82	7.43 (a/ sd)
Dermaptera	16	43	10	69	6.26 (a/ sd)
Diptera	17	36	57	110	9.97 (a/ sd)
Hemiptera	4	19	8	31	2.81 (a/ R)
Hymenoptera	28	123	135	286	25.93 (A/ D)
Lepidoptera	1	0	1	2	0.18 (a/ sr)
Orthoptera	15	20	4	39	3.54 (a/ R)
Total	213	533	357	1103	

Figure (2): Species composition, species richness and species abundance.

Figure (3): Species composition, species richness and species abundance.

5. Variation in each of numbers of species and/or higher taxa and number of individuals and each of Simpson (S) and Shannon Weiner (H) indices of diversity under different crop and fallow :

Also, Table (5) and Figure (4) showed, each of Simpson and Shannon – Weiner indices of diversity in different cover crop (Tomato and maize) comparing with fallow. The diversity is minimum in two cultivation and being (0.01 Simpson index), while Shannon – winter has 0.19 in maize, increased to 0.21 in tomato. But these two indices are higher in fallow, Simpson index has value 0.02, while Shannon – Weiner has 0.28. Cover plants strongly affected the soil invertebrate assemblages. The biodiversity of the soil arthropods in the different cultivation, by using Shannon and Wiener (1963) “H” and Simpson

(1949) “S” Indices of diversity. From this study we can be concluded the species diversity was nearly similar to some extent in different vegetation types. Similar results have been reported by (Al-Assiuty *et al.*, 1993 and Rizk *et al.* 2009). Different plant species used as cover plants seem to have different effects on beneficial fauna. Crop rotations are fundamental to sustainable cropping systems. As well a designed crop creates diversity and improves soil condition also generate biodiversity of soil form and soil fatality, (Rizk *et al.*, 2006). Also, Sommaggio *et al.* (2018) indicated that, cover plants strongly affected the soil invertebrate assemblages. We speculate that higher soil fauna taxonomic richness in the medium and long-term trials could be due to long-term build-up of soil organic matter as food for the soil fauna groups.

Table (5): Species diversity of fauna collected from fallow, maize and tomato by using Shannon-Weiner and simpson indices during 2014-2015.

Season	Fallow	Maize	Tomato	Total
Taxa	31	40	30	101
Individuals	213	533	357	1103
Shannon	0.28	0.19	0.21	0.22
Simpson	0.02	0.01	0.01	0.01

Figure (4): Species diversity of fauna collected from fallow, maize and tomato.

Our results indicated that each of the two different cropping plantations could affect the population of the mesofauna. Finally, we think that the soil organisms of rotary cultivated plots are greater with maize than vegetable crops (Tomato) . We can say that , the rotary cultivation plots had more soil animals than the fallow. Continued long term studies on the effect of tillage on soil dwelling micro arthropods, are needed to fully understand the dynamics of these populations relative to disturbance. Increased awareness of how tillage affects the soil community may aid in the development of sustainable agricultural. Finally, it can be recommended that both cultivation (tomato and maize) or crop rotation and conventional farming system are necessary to know the incidence, abundance and diversity of pests and how to monitor them, as well as to identify beneficial arthropod, especially spiders, to effectively manage pests in these two plants covering crops. More researches should be carried out to understand the impact of differ and type of fertilization and tillage or no tillage on the surface soil fauna. Entomologist should play on important role in such efforts in the future.

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Evaluation of insecticidal and biochemical efficacy of *Ficus nitida* and *Eichhornia crassipes* leaf extracts on *Galleria mellonella* (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae)

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Abstract:

The greater wax moth *Galleria mellonella* (L.) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae) is widely distributed throughout the world. It is an economically important pest of wax combs of the honeybee. The present work was carried out to study the insecticidal and biochemical effects of *Ficus nitida* and *Eichhornia crassipes* leaf extracts by different solvents: petroleum ether, acetone, ethanol, chloroform and water on 4th instar larvae of *G. mellonella*. The LC₅₀ of *F. nitida* extracts were 5.638, 10.312, 2.440, 13.359 and 4.394 % for petroleum ether, acetone, ethanol, chloroform and water, respectively. And for *E. crassipes* extracts were 4.803, 1.860, 2.550, 12.067 and 3.864 % for the same solvent order, respectively. The data showed that *F. nitida* ethanol extract and *E. crassipes* acetone extract caused reduction in pupal weight and pupation percentage and also increasing in larval duration days compared with control. The data showed that, the two extracts had a significant inhibitory effect on α -amylase, while alkaline phosphatase showed significant increase in activity. The overall effects of *F. nitida* and *E. crassipes* leaf extracts on *G. mellonella* larvae may have led us to a selective natural product that can be employed in integrated pest management strategies.

Introduction

In recent years, the application of several botanical products has drawn much attention as effective alternatives to the synthetic pesticides and chemical fertilizers. These plant products are reported to be more effective, less expensive, biodegradable and safe for mankind and environment, than their synthetic counterparts, which are environmentally persistent and toxic to non-target organisms including humans eliciting many unidentified diseases after bioaccumulation. Therefore, alternatives to conventional pesticides

are required to be developed from the active ingredients of plant origin. These compounds have been shown to affect insect populations by reducing their developmental, survival and reproductive rate. The present study aims to evolve an environmentally safe, economical and effective botanical insecticide for the control of *Galleria mellonella* (L.) (Lepidoptera: Pyralidae), it considers as a serious pest of beehives and stored bee wax (Fathy *et al.*, 2017). This investigation is expected to yield interesting results

which may be useful for the protection of *G. mellonella*.

The aim of the present work is to study the insecticidal and biochemical effects of *Ficus nitida* and *Eichhornia crassipes* leaf extracts on 4th instar larvae of *G. mellonella*

Materials and methods

The greater wax moth *G. mellonella* larvae were obtained from infested hives and reared at the laboratory under controlled conditions (25 ± 2 °C, $60 \pm 10\%$ RH) according to method of Birah *et al.* (2008) and fed on diet composed according to Metwally *et al.* (2012). *F. nitida* leaves were collected according to the method of Sawidis *et al.* (2011). *E. Crassipes* were collected from the River Nile at the El-Dahab Island (Giza), Egypt.

1. Extraction method:

F. nitida and *E. crassipes* collected leaves were washed thoroughly with water to remove dirt, if any and chopped into small pieces with a sharp knife. Chopped pieces were crushed into a fine paste with the help of a pestle and mortar. The solvents: petroleum ether, acetone, ethanol, chloroform and water were used at a rate of 500ml/200gm pasted leaves, were soaked for 72 h., was shaken daily for one hour, and its contents were filtered through Whatman no.1 filter paper over anhydrous sodium sulphate. Each solvent extract was evaporated to dryness by a rotary evaporator at 40°C according to method of Rossenthaler (1930). The crude extracts were weighed and kept in deep freezer till used.

2. Toxicity assay:

The crude extracts were tested at five different concentrations. Newly active 4th instar larvae were selected and starved for 4 hours before the experiments. Ten larvae were introduced to treated diet in the petri dish with concentrations of 10, 5, 2, 1 and 0.5 % of crude extracts. The control

was given an artificial diet only. Five replicates were maintained for each treatment with 10 larvae per replicate. Mortality % were recorded after 48 hrs. Larvae were considered dead if they become immobile and have shown no detectable response to the external stimuli. Mortality data were subjected to Probit analysis according to Finney's method Finney (1971).

3. Biological activities:

The effect of the two extracts (*F. nitida* ethanol extract and *E. crassipes* acetone extract) on larval duration, percentage of pupation, pupal weight, and adult emergence of *G. mellonella* carried out. The diets containing LC₅₀ of the extracts were put into 9-cm petri dish with 10 freshly molted pre-weighted fourth-instar larvae. The control was given an artificial diet only and the experiment was performed in three replications. After 48hrs. larvae were fed on untreated diet until pupation. Inspections were carried out until adult emergence and larval duration, larval weight, pupation%, pupae weight, and adult emergence % were recorded daily.

4. Biochemical activities:

The survived *G. mellonella* larvae after 48 hrs of feeding on artificial diet incorporated with LC₅₀ of the two extracts (*F. nitida* ethanol extract and *E. crassipes* acetone extract) were used for various biochemical tests, each experiment was repeated at three times each with ten larvae. A known weight of larvae (whole body) was homogenized in appropriate amount of distilled water using mechanical homogenizer, centrifuged at 10,000g for 5 min at 4 °C and the supernatant was used for tests-freshly or kept in deep freezer until use. The activity of carbohydrate digestive enzymes α -amylase and invertase were measured by the procedure of Ishaaya and Swirski, (1976). Alkaline phosphatase activity was measured by

the method of Bessey *et al.* (1946). The activity of α - and β - esterases were determined according to the method of Van Asperen (1962).

5. Statistical analysis:

Probit analysis was done to calculate the median lethal concentrations for all crude extracts and the data were statistically analysed by means of analysis of variance (ANOVA) (Tukey's test) at $P < 0.05$ using IBM® "SPSS" STATISTICS Ver.26 software, most of the results were expressed in percentage, although actual numbers were used for statistical tests. Results were recorded as mean \pm standard deviation (SD).

Results and discussion

1. Toxicological studies:

The toxicological effects of *F. nitida* and *E. crassipes* extracts on the 4th instar larvae *G. mellonella* at

different concentrations were presented in Table (1) and Figures (1 and 2) , showed that toxicological effect on the 4th instar larvae of *G. mellonella* after 48hrs. of treatment for *F. nitida* extracts (Petroleum ether, acetone, ethanol, chloroform and water) expressed as LC₅₀ were 5.638, 10.312, 2.440, 13.359 and 4.394 %, respectively, and for *E. crassipes* extracts for the same solvents were 4.803, 1.860, 2.550, 12.067 and 3.864 %, respectively. From the previous data we can concluded that for *F. nitida* the most effective crude extract was ethanol extract followed by water, petroleum ether, acetone and chloroform, respectively, and for *E. crassipes* the most effective crude extract was acetone extract followed by ethanol, water, petroleum and chloroform extract, respectively.

Table (1): Effective concentrations of plant extracts on 4th instar larvae of *Galleria mellonella* after 48 hrs. of treatment.

Solvent extracts	LC50	95% Confidence Limit		LC90	95% Confidence Limit		Chi square
		Lower	Upper		Lower	Upper	
<i>Ficus nitida</i>							
Pet. Ether	5.638	4.348	7.936	.751	.638	.900	.491*
Acetone	10.312	7.310	17.239	1.013	.864	1.237	.945*
Ethanol	2.440	2.078	2.878	.387	.318	.459	.681*
Chloroform	13.359	9.101	24.296	1.126	.959	1.386	.840*
Water	4.394	3.514	5.768	.643	.546	.761	.567*
<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i>							
Pet. Ether	4.803	3.868	6.258	.681	.587	.796	.859 ^b
Acetone	1.860	1.535	2.236	.270	.186	.349	.085 ^b
Ethanol	2.550	2.133	3.066	.406	.329	.487	.126 ^b
Chloroform	12.067	8.528	20.337	1.082	.931	1.308	.917 ^b
Water	3.864	3.156	4.884	.587	.499	.689	.940 ^b

Chi square values are significant at $P < 0.05$ levels.

Figure (1): Mortality curve of *Galleria mellonella* 4th instar larvae for the determination of LC50 of *Eichhornia crassipes* leaf extract.

Figure (2): Mortality curve of *Galleria mellonella* 4th instar larvae for the determination of LC50 of *Ficus nitida* leaf extract.

2. Biological studies:

The effects of the two extracts (*F. nitida* ethanol extract and *E. crassipes* acetone extract) on larval duration, percentage of pupation, pupal weight, and adult emergence of *G. mellonella* were showed in Table (2). Last larval instar weight after treatment with LC₅₀ of *E. crassipes* acetone and *Ficus nitida* ethanol extracts were 75 and 60 mg., respectively compared with

146 mg. for the control. Where the larval duration was 25 and 27 days, respectively, while control was 15 days. The pupation percentage was decreased for both extracts, but *F. nitida* ethanol extract was most effective as expressed by the lowest pupation percentage 30%. The weight of the resulted pupae was 80, 70 and 164 mg. for *E. crassipes* acetone, *F. nitida* ethanol extracts and control, respectively.

Table (2): Biological activities of plant extracts on 4th instar larvae *Galleria mellonella*.

Treatments	Last larval instar weight (mg)	Larval duration (days)	Pupation %	Pupal weight (mg)	Adult emergence %
<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i> acetone extract	75 ±3.2b	25 ±1.5b	38±4.5b	80 ±0.2b	0b
<i>Ficus nitida</i> ethanol extract	60±1.3b	27± 0.5b	30±1.5b	70±0.01b	0b
Control	146±5.0a	15 ±4a	93 ±6a	164±5.4a	96 ±7a

Values are means ± standard deviation (SD).

Means followed by different letters within the same row are significantly different (Tukey's test, p < 0.05)

The present findings showed highly effect in pupal weight, tissue degeneration and preventing adult emergence. These results are confirmed with that obtained by Schlöter (1985) who found that the storage of proteins in fat bodies, which is necessary for pupation, did not occur when treated the last larval instar of *E. varivestis* with higher doses of azadirachtin. Larvae take longer to reach the critical weight for ecdysis, which implies an increase of the larval stage duration. Such delays in larval development due to feeding inhibition may result in impaired larval development and unsuccessful emergence of adults. It is likely that this low weight is due to the inhibitory effect of the LC₅₀ of the tow extract on α -amylase activity, and at least in part, this contributes to the decrease in growth rate. Alpha-amylase is a major digestive enzyme, that catalyses the hydrolysis of starch into sugars (Nasr *et al.* (2017). As the artificial diet of *G. mellonella* larvae is composed mainly of starch, it obvious that α -amylase plays an essential role in digestion of ingested food. This conclusion could be supported by Batista-Pereira *et al.* (2002) and Abdel-Rahman and Al-Mozini (2007) who mentioned that the mode of action of the *C. procera* as antifeedant may be due to the digestion inhibition through inactivation of

digestive enzymes. Also, the results of this study confirmed the suggestion of Upadhyay (2013) that the deleterious effects of *C. procera* latex on insect feeding may be due to presence of α -amylase inhibitors.

3. Biochemical studies:

Activities of certain carbohydrate digestive enzymes and detoxification enzymes in *G. mellonella* 4th instar larvae after 48 hrs. feeding on LC₅₀ of *E. crassipes* acetone and *F. nitida* ethanol extracts presented in Table (3). Mean activities of α -amylase enzyme was 27.13 ± 0.8 and 18.45 ± 0.5 $\mu\text{g. glucose/min/g protein}$ for larvae fed on *Eichhornia crassipes* acetone and *Ficus nitida* ethanol extracts, respectively and 90.4 ± 2.4 $\mu\text{g. glucose/min/g protein}$ for control. The reduction of α -amylase activity reached more than 3-folds. Also, the activity of alkaline phosphatase for *E. crassipes* acetone extract and *F. nitida* ethanol extract increased significantly compared with the controls 1277.2 ± 23 , 1122.1 ± 12 and 909.4 ± 25 $\text{mg phenol/min/g. protein}$, respectively. Activities of other detoxifying and carbohydrate hydrolysing enzymes such as α -Esterase, β -Esterase and invertase did not differ significantly than control for both two extracts.

Table (3): Biochemical activities of plant extracts on 4th instar larvae *Galleria mellonella*

Treatments	α -amylase ($\mu\text{g glucose/min/g protein}$)	Alkaline phosphatase ($\mu\text{g phenol/min/g protein}$)	α -esterase ($\mu\text{g } \alpha\text{-naphthol/min/g protein}$)	β -esterase ($\mu\text{g } \beta\text{-naphthol/min/g protein}$)	Invertase ($\mu\text{g glucose/min/g protein}$)
<i>Eichhornia crassipes</i> acetone extract	$27.13 \pm 0.8\text{b}$	$1277.2 \pm 23\text{b}$	$30.2 \pm 1.5\text{a}$	$20.7 \pm 1.7\text{a}$	$20.9 \pm 1.5\text{a}$
<i>Ficus nitida</i> ethanol extract	$18.45 \pm 0.5\text{b}$	$1122.1 \pm 12\text{b}$	$28.05 \pm 1.3\text{a}$	$17.8 \pm 1.2\text{a}$	$18.4 \pm 1.4\text{a}$
Control	$90.4 \pm 2.4\text{a}$	$909.4 \pm 25\text{a}$	$40.2 \pm 1.84\text{a}$	$18.8 \pm 1.50\text{a}$	$20.6 \pm 2.3\text{a}$

Values are means \pm standard deviation (SD).

Means followed by different letters within the same row are significantly different (Tukey's test, $p < 0.05$)

Esterases (α -EST and β -EST) are important detoxifying enzymes which hydrolyse the esteric bond in toxic chemicals, they have been reported to possess detoxification ability against synthetic and botanical insecticides (Zibae,2011). The results of this study indicated that feeding *G. mellonella* larvae on artificial diet contains LC₅₀ of the tow extracts for 48 hrs did not affect significantly both of α and β esterase activities, it induced an obvious and significantly increase in alkaline phosphatase activity. Increasing alkaline phosphatase activity level indicates that the enzyme is involved in detoxification of certain toxic compounds that could be present in the tow extracts and confirmed the suggestion that portion of the digested food were used by larvae fed on the tow extracts for synthesis of specific detoxification enzymes.

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Revision of the thysanopterous (Terebrantia: Thripidae) in Egypt

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Abstract:

The updated checklist of order Thysanoptera, family Thripidae are given. More than 70 species and 37 genera are recorded in Egypt belonging to four subfamilies (Panchaethripinae, Thripinae, Dendrothripinae and Sericothripinae). Synonyms, geographical distribution and host plants are given.

Introduction

Thrips (Thysanoptera: Thripidae) is widespread around the world especially in tropical region. About 6246 species in 782 genera were identified, derived from two suborders: the Terebrantia, whereas are classified into eight families: Aeolothripidae, Adiheterothripidae, Fauriellidae, Heterothripidae, Melanthripidae, Merothripidae, Thripidae and Uzelothripidae and the tubulifera includes a single family, Phlaeothripidae. Thrips are small or minute slender-bodied insects (0.5-15mm). Antenna are short, 6-10 segments. Body color varies from pale to dark black according weather condition. Piercing mouthparts is asymmetrical (Right mandible absent) (Priesner, 1960; Richard and Davies, 1977 and Gullan and Cranston, 1994).

Most species are mycophagous (More than 50%), feed on fungi existing in leaf litter or beneath the bark of trees

(Family Merothripidae and Subfamily Idolothripinae). Other species are phytophagous inhabiting flowers and leaves; they attack many parts of plant as buds, leaves, flowers, fruits and stem. They cause damage by sucking the contents of plant cell resulting leaf and flower defoliation; fruit scarring in some fruit trees and often reduce its market value, also fruits become smaller than normal ones.

Some species of Family Phlaeothripidae cause rolled leaf galls in some oriental trees. Furthermore, some species are known as tospoviruses (Family Bunyaviridae) transmitted as *Frankliniella fusca* Hinds, *F. occidentalis* (Pergande), *F. schultzei* (Trybom) *Thrips tabaci* Lindeman, *T. palmi* Karny and *Scirtothrips dorsalis* Hood. On the other hand, some species are predators that feed on other thrips species or other small arthropods as scale insects and mites (Family Aeolothripidae; *Scolothrips* Family

Thripidae and *Karnyothrips* Watson Family Phlaeothripidae) (Priesner, 1960; Lewis, 1973 and Mound and Kibby, 1998).

The aim of the present research work is to study the revision of the thysanopterous in Egypt.

Results and discussion

Figure (1) showed that more than 150 species are described whereas derived from five families in Egypt.

Key of Thysanoptera

1. Last abdominal segment usually conical; female with saw-like ovipositor; major anal setae arising from sub-apical region of last segment; forewings with longitudinal or across veins and setae.

Suborder Terebrantia (Figure 2a, 2b)

-Last abdominal segment tube-like; female without external ovipositor; major anal setae arising from platelets attached to end of tube; forewings without veins or setae . **Suborder Tubulifera (Figure 2c, 2d)**

Key to families of Egyptian

Terebrantia

-Female with ovipositor weakly developed; antennal eight-segments, segments III and IV with liner, forked or simple sensoria

cone... **Merothripidae (Figure 2c, 2d)**

-Female ovipositor turned downwards away from body; antennae usually seven or eight segments, rarely six or nine segment, segments III and IV developed into slender forked or simple sense cone .. **Thripidae (Figure 2f, 2g)**

-Female ovipositor turned upwards toward body; antennae nine segments, segments III and IV usually with liner sensoria **Aeolothripidae (Figure 2h, 2i)**

-Female ovipositor turned upwards toward body; antennal nine segments, clearly separate and with transverse sensoria. **Melanthripidae (Figure 2j)**

The family Thripidae presently includes about more than 2100 species, this is the second largest family of Thysanoptera. Most genera of the suborder Terebrantia are in this family. In Egypt, this family includes 37 genera and 77 species. It contains of four subfamilies as follow:

Key to subfamilies of Egyptian

Thripidae

-Head and pronotum reticulated; antennal segments III and IV without sense cone; terminal segment long and slender **Panchaetothripinae (Figure 3a, 3b)**

-Head and pronotum not reticulated; antennal segments III and IV with sense cone; terminal segment rarely finely elongate..... **Thripinae (Figure 3c, 3d)**

-Metanotum furca with lyre-shaped, extended to mesonotum; mesonotum without spinula; fore wing curved at apex join to posterior margin.....

Dendrothripinae (Figure 3e, 3f)

-Metanotum without furca; mesonotum with spinula; fore wing wide at apex and not join to posterior margi.....

Sericothripinae (Figure 3g, 3h)

Order :Thysanoptera

Figure (1): Families of Thysanoptera in Egypt.

Figure (2): a, b *Terebratia* a (Last segmented), b (Forewing); c, d *Tubulifera* c (Last segmented), d (Forewing); e *Merothripida* (Last segmented); f, g *Thripidae* f (Ovipositor), g (Antennae); h, i *Aclothripidae* h (Ovipositor), i (Antennae) and j *Melanthripidae* (Antennae).

Figure (3): a, b Panchaetothripinae a (Head and pronotum), b (Antennae); c, d Thripinae c (Head and pronotum), d (Antennae); e, f Dendrothripinae e (Meso and metanotum), f (Forewing); g, h Sericothripinae g (Meso and metanotum) and h (Forewing).

1. Subfamily: Panchaethripinae

The species belonged to Panchaethripinae seem to be associated with leaf; some species feed on grasses and few causes damage to crop seedling. This subfamily consists of forty-two genera and one-hundred forty-five species around the world. In Egypt, it represents by four genera and seven species.

1.1. Genus: *Caliothrips* Daniel

Caliothrips Daniel, 1904, Ent. News, 296.

The species belongs to this genus are young leaf-feeder, several of them are pests of many crops, and few species attacks grasses. This genus is widespread in all countries, especially tropical ones and many different plants. It consists of twenty- three species in the world, while in Egypt it represented by three species.

1.1.1. *Caliothrips deserticola* Priesner

Caliothrips deserticola Priesner, 1960, Publ. Inst. Desert Egypte 13: 226.

Distribution: Sudan (Moritz *et al.*, 2013).

Host plants: Scrub on the rocky slopes (Priesner, 1960).

1.1.2. *Caliothrips graminicola* Bagnall and Cameron

Herciothrips graminicola Bagnall and Cameron. 1932. Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (10) 10: 415.

Caliothrips graminicola Priesner, 1960. Publ. Inst. Desert Egypte, 13: 227.

Distribution: Australia, Iran, India, Nepal, Sri Lanka, South Africa, Sudan, Thailand, Yemen and Zimbabwe (Kudo, 1995 and Mirab-balou, 2013).

Host plant: *Glycine max* (Abd El-Wahab, 2016).

1.1.3. *Caliothrips sudanensis* (Bagnall)

Herciothrips sudanensis Bagnall and Cameron, 1932, Ann. Mag. rlat. Hist. (10) 10: 415.

Caliothrips sudanensis (Bagnall and Cameron; Priesner, 1949, Bull. Soc. Fouad I Ent. 33: 132.

Common name: Cotton leaf thrips

Distribution: Ethiopia, India, Kenya, Nigeria, South Africa, Sudan, and Zimbabwe (Moritz *et al.*, 2013).

Host plant: *Glycine max* (Abd El-Wahab, 2016).

1.2. *Heliothrips* Haliday

Heliothrips, Haliday, 1836, Ent. Mag., 443.

This genus attacks wide range of hosts specially, the hard leaves one. Five species belong to this genus, on the other hand, one species only valid in Egypt.

1.2.1. *Heliothrips haemorrhoidalis* Bouche, 1833

Thrips haemorrhoidalis, Bouche, 1833, Naturg. Schadl. Garten-Ins., 206.

Heliothrips haemorrhoidalis, Priesner, 1926, Thys. Eur., 126.

Heliothrips adonidum Haliday, 1836. Ent. Mag., 3:443.

Common name: Greenhouse thrips, Black greenhouse thrips and Black tea thrips.

Distribution: Widely distributed (Mirab-balou, 2013).

Host plants: *Acalypha* Sp., *Camellia* Sp., *Citrus* Sp., *Croton* Sp., *Laurus nobilis*, *Mangifera indica*, *Prunus persica*, *Pyrus malus* and *Vitis vinifera* (Priesner, 1960 and El-Wakkad, 2007).

1.3. *Hercinothrips* Bagnall

Hercinothrips Bagnall, 1932. Ann. Mag. nat. Hist., 10 (10): 506.

Hercinothrips has been known as a pest of many host plant. The origin distribution is Africa. This genus consists of nine species widespread. *Hercinothrips femoralis* is the only species recorded in Egypt.

1.3.1. *Hercinothrips femoralis* Reuter

Heliothrips femoralis Reuter, 1891. Medd. Soc. Fauna Fl. Fenn., 17:166.

Heliothrips cestsii Pergande, 1895, U.S.D.A., Insect Life, 7 (5):390.

Hercinothrips femoralis, Bagnall. 1932. Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist., Ser. 10, 10(59):506.

Common name: Banded greenhouse thrips and sugar-beet thrips.

Distribution: Widespread in the tropics and subtropics; common in temperate areas in greenhouses, Denmark, Finland, Florida, Georgia, Iceland, Kenya, Nigeria, Norway, Sierra Leone, Sweden, Tanzania and Uganda (Diffie *et al.*, 2008; Kobro, 2011 and Moritz *et al.*, 2013).

Host plant: *Citrus* sp., 2007).

1.4. *Retithrips* Marchal

Retithrips, Marchal, 1019, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. D`Egypte, 17.

One widespread species (Included Egypt) and the second one from Indonesia and Northern Australia.

1.4.1. *Retithrips syriacus* Mayet

Heliethrips syriacus Mayet, 1890, Insectes de la vigne, 451.

Retithrips aegytiacus Marchal, 1910, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 17-21.

Dictyothrips aegytiaca Zanon, 1917-18, L`Agric. Colon., Firenze, XI-XII.

Dictyothrips zanoniana Del Guercio, Note Osservat., Ent. Agr. Firenze, 106-119.

Common name: Castor thrips and Black vine thrips

Distribution: America, Brazil, Congo, Europe, Ghana, India, Iran, Kenya, Lebanon, Libya, Malawi, Morocco, Mozambique, Nigeria, Palestine, Puerto Rico, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Syria, Tanzania, Togo, Tunisia, Uganda and U.S.A . (Mirabalou, 2013 and Moritz *et al.*, 2013).

Host plants: *Acalypha* Sp., *Gossypium* Sp., *Quercus* Sp., *Eucalyptus indica*; *Juglans regia*, *Lawsonia inermis*, *Mangifera indica*, *Myrtus communis*, *Psidium guajava*, *Pyrus cydonia*, *Ricinus communis*, *Rosa centifolia*, *Schinus molle*, *Sc. terebinthifolius*, *Terminalia arjuna* and *Vitis vinifera* (Priesner, 1960 and El-Wakkad, 2007).

2. Subfamily: *Dendrothripinae*

This subfamily comprises a group of leaf-feeding thrips (Live and breed on green leaves not in flowers).

This subfamily includes sixteen genera and about one-hundred described species in the world. In Egypt it represents by two genera and two species.

2.1. *Dendrothrips* Uzel

Dendrothrips, Uzel, 1895, Mon. Ord. Thys. 159.

Several species of *Dendrothrips* are particularly associated with the family Oleaceae and herbs. This genus now includes fifty-six species, and *D. eremicola* is the only species that recorded in Egypt.

2.1.1. *Dendrothrips eremicola* Priesner

Dendrothrips eremicola Priesner, 1960, Publ. Inst. Desert Egypt 13: 281.

Host plants: Wild shrubs and *Olea europaea* (Priesner, 1960 and Wafy, 2018).

Recently, in 2018 this species occurred as an outbreak on olive trees at Ismailia Governorate (Wafy, 2018).

2.2. *Pseudodendrothrips* Priesner

Pseudodendrothrips Priesner, 1960, Publ. Inst. Desert Egypt 13:283.

Pseudodendrothrips is commonly associated with Moraceae, and live on Poaceae, it lives on leaves of plants. There are now twenty-one species listed in this genus and represents in Egypt by one species.

2.2.1. *Pseudodendrothrips aegytiacus* Priesner

Pseudodendrothrips aegytiacus Priesner, 1960, Publ. Inst. Desert Egypte 13:284.

Distribution: Abu Dhabi, Canary Islands, Israel and Southern Africa (Moritz *et al.*, 2013).

Host plants: *Convolvulus arvensis*, *Euphorbia cuneata* and *Lycium arabicum* (Priesner, 1960).

3. Subfamily: *Sericothripinae*

Flower and leaf-feeding thrips. The subfamily *Sericothripinae* is a largely tropical group of about three genera and one-hundred, sixty-eight species. On the other hand, there are

two genera and five species belong to this subfamily in Egypt.

3.1. *Sericothrips* Haliday

Limothrips Haliday, 1836, Ent. Mag., 444.

The genus *Sericothrips* includes about seven species worldwide. In Egypt, this genus represents by three species.

3.1.1. *Sericothrips arenarius* Priesner

Sericothrips arenarius Priesner, 1960, Publ. Inst. Desert Egypte 13: 244.

Host plant: herbs (Priesner, 1960).

3.1.2. *Sericothrips kassimianus* Priesner

Sericothrips kassimianus Priesner, 1950, Bull. Soc. Fouad I Ent., 25.

Hydatothrips kassimianus .Bhatti, 1973. Oriental Insects. 7 (3): 403-449.

Common name: Blood flower thrips.

Distribution: India (Bhatti, 1973).

Host plant: *Cynanchum acutum* (Priesner, 1960 and Wafy, 2018)

3.1.3. *Sericothrips masrensis* Priesner

Sericothrips masrensis Priesner, 1960, Publ. Inst. Desert Egypte 13: 245.

Host plant: unknown (Priesner, 1960).

3.2. *Neohydatothrips* John

Neohydatothrips John, 1929. Zootaxa. 1575: 47–68.

This genus now includes almost one-hundred and eighteen species.

3.2.1. *Neohydatothrips samayunkur* Priesner

Hydatothrips (*Neohydatothrips*) *samayunkur* Kudo, 1995. Zootaxa. 1575: 62.

Common name: Marigold thrips

Distribution: Africa, Asia, Australia, Central and South America, China, India, Kenya, New Zealand, North America and Uganda (Mirab-balou et al., 2011 and Rachana and Varatharajan 2017).

Host plant: *Tagetes erecta* (Abd El-Wahab, 2015).

4. Thripinae

Thripinae represents In Egypt by twenty-nine genus and sixty-four species as follow:

4.1. *Anaphothrips* Uzel

Anaphothrips, Uzel, 1895, Mon. Ord. Thy. 142.

Many species are grass-living. Eighty-six species are belonged to *Anaphothrips*. Only seven species are recorded In Egypt. It considered as minor pests of cereals.

4.1.1. *Anaphothrips alternans* Bagnall

Anaphothrips alternans Bagnall, 1913, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (8), 12: 291.

Common name: Corn thrips and sugarcane thrips.

Distribution: Central America and Cyprus (Priesner, 1960).

Host plant: *Scirpus* Sp.; *Scirpus pungens*; *Panicum turgidum*; *Hordeum vulgare*; *Saccharum officinarum*; *Sorghum halepense*; *Cynodon dactylon*; *Polypogon monspeliensis* (Priesner, 1960).

4.1.2. *Anaphothrips crocatus* Priesner

Anaphothrips crocatus Priesner, 1938, Bull. Soc. Fouad I Ent., 131.

Host plant: *Zygophyllum simplex* (Priesner, 1960).

4.1.3. *Anaphothrips hieroglyphicus* Priesner

Anaphothrips hieroglyphicus Priesner, 1939, Bull. Soc. Fouad I Ent., 352.

Common name: Western desert thrips.

Host plant: Desert shrubs (Priesner, 1960).

4.1.4. *Anaphothrips obscurus* Muller

Thrips obscurus Muller, 1776, O. F., Zool. Dan Prodrum., 96.

Anaphothrips obscurus Uzel, 1895, Mon. Ord. Thys. 279.

Anaphothrips striatus Hinds, 1902, Mon. Thys. N. Amer., 161.

Common name: American grass thrips and Grain thrips.

Distribution: Widely distributed, Algeria, Australia, Canary Islands, China, Denmark, Finland, Iceland, Iran, Hawaii, North America, Norway, Morocco, Sweden, and Turkey (Kobro, 2011; Mirab-balou et al., 2011; Tunc et al., 2012 and Mirab-balou, 2013).

Host plants: Gramineae, *Citrus* sp., *Mangifera indica*, *Polypogon monspeliensis*, *Psidium guajava*, *Pyrus malus* and *Vitis vinifera* (Priesner, 1960 and El-Wakkad, 2007).

It feeds on the leaves of grasses and cereals rather than the inflorescences. It is common in temperate area.

4.1.5. *Anaphothrips parviceps* Priesner

Anaphothrips parviceps Priesner, 1960, Publ. Inst. Desert Egypte 13: 265.

Host plant: Composite (Priesner, 1960).

4.1.6. *Anaphothrips retamae* Priesner
Anaphothrips retamae Priesner, 1934, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, p.275.

Host plant: *Retama raetam* (Priesner, 1960).

4.1.7. *Anaphothrips sudanensis* Trybom

Anaphothrips sudanensis Trybom, 1911, Bull. Bri. Mus. Ent. 9, II: 21.

Euthrips flavicinctus Karny, 1912, Bull. Bri. Mus. Ent. 9, II: 21.

Euthrips (Anaphothrips) alternans Bagnall, 1913, Bull. Bri. Mus. Ent. 9, II: 21.

Euthripscitricinctus Bagnall, 1919, Bull. Bri. Mus. Ent. 9, II: 21.

Euthrips bicolor Morgan, 1925, Bull. Bri. Mus. Ent. 9, II: 21.

Euthrips transvaalensis Faure, 1925, Bull. Bri. Mus. Ent. 9, II: 21.

Common name: Wheat thrips and Maize thrips.

Distribution: In subtropical and tropical regions around the world, China, Ethiopia, India, Kenya, Libya, Mozambique, Morocco, Nigeria, Spain, Senegal, Sri Lanka, South Africa, Sudan U. S. A. and Zimbabwe (Reitz *et al.*, 2011; Tillekaratne *et al.*, 2011; Goldarazena *et al.*, 2012; Moritz *et al.*, 2013 and Rachana and Varatharajan, 2017).

Host plant: *Glycine max* (Abd El-Wahab, 2016).

This species has been known as a pest of grasses, cereal and sugar cane and distributes in tropics regions.

4.2. *Aptinothrips Haliday*

Aptinothrips Haliday, 1836, Ent. Mag., 3: 445.

Aptinothrips represented through the world by five species while in Egypt, only one species valid. Europe being the center of distribution. They live in grasses and have some degree of host specificity.

4.2.1. *Aptinothrips rufus* (Gmelin)

Aptinothrips rufus Gmelin, 1788, Linne Syst. Nat. 2224.

Thrips rufa Gmelin, 1788. Carolia Linn; Syst. Nat., 2224.

Common name: Grass thrips.

Distribution: Algeria, China, Costa Rica, Croatia, Denmark, Ethiopia, Europe, Finland, Iceland, Iran, Italy, Norway, South North Africa, Sweden, Tunisia and Turkey (Raspudici *et al.*, 2009; Kobro, 2011; Tunc *et al.*, 2012; Mirab-balou, 2013 and Marullo and De Grazia, 2013).

Host plant: *Cynodon dactylon* (Priesner, 1960)

4.3. *Ascirtothrips Priesner*

Ascirtothrips Priesner, 1960, Publ. Inst. Desert Egypte 13: 252.

This genus comprises two species in Egypt.

4.3.1. *Ascirtothrips antilope* Priesner

Anaphothrips antilope Priesner, 1923, Ent. Mitteil., XII: 63.

Scirtothrips antilope Priesner, 1932, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 143, 152.

Ascirtothrips antilope Priesner, 1957, Zool. Anz., 159: 7-8.

Distribution: Cyprus, India, Israel and Morocco (Moritz *et al.*, 2013).

Host plants: *Aerva tomentosa*, *Alhagi maurorum*, *Iphiona mucronata*, *Nitraria retusa*, *Pulicaria crispa* and *Zilla Spinosa* (Priesner, 1960).

4.3.2. *Ascirtothrips efflatouni* Priesner

Ascirtothrips efflatouni Priesner, 1960, Publ. Inst. Desert Egypte 13: 253.

Host plant: *Halocnemon strobilaceum* (Priesner, 1960).

4.4. *Baliothrips* Uzel

Baliothrips Uzel, 1895, Mon. Ord. Thys. 204.

Three species have been recorded in this genus. On the other hand, one species only is valid in Egypt.

4.4.1. *Baliothrips vittipennis* Bagnall

Baliothrips vittipennis Bagnall, 1927, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (9), 20: 574.

Common name: Mat sedge thrips.

Distribution: Australia, France and Poland (Priesner, 1960).

Host plant: *Cyperus* Sp (Priesner, 1960).

4.5. *Bolacidothrips* Priesner

Bolacidothrips Priesner, 1930, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 6.

Old World genus, it lives on Poaceae. The genus consists of twelve species, the only species *B. graminis* has been recorded in Egypt.

4.5.1. *Bolacidothrips graminis* Priesner

Bolacidothrips graminis Priesner, 1930, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 6.

Common name: beard grass thrips.

Host plants: *Scirpus* sp., *Triticum* sp., *Cynodon dactylon*, *Imperata cylindrical*, *Phragmites communis*, *Panicum colonum*, *Polypogon monspeliensis*, *Saccharum officinarum*, *Sorghum vulgare* and *Zea mays* (Priesner, 1960).

4.6. *Chirothrips* Haliday

Chirothrips, Haliday, 1836, Ent. Mag., 444.

Widespread genus across old world, it lives in f lowers of Poaceae. Forty-two species spread around the world. Four species recorded from Egypt. It is common in the Holarctic, Neotropical, and Ethiopian regions.

4.6.1. *Chirothrips africanus* Priesner

Chirothrips africanus Priesner, 1932, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 46.

Common name: African thrips.

Distribution: Algeria, China, Cyprus, Ethiopia, Iran, India, Italy, Sudan,

Yemen, and Uzbekistan (Mirab-balou, 2013).

Host plant: Gramineae; Cyperaceae; *Citrus* Sp.; *Cyperus* Sp.; *Cynodon dactylon*; *Cladium mariscus*; *Imperata cylindrical*; *Eragrostis bipinnata*; *Panicum turgidum*; *Mangifera indica*; *Psidium guajava*; *Pyrus malus* and *Vitis vinifera* (Priesner, 1960 and El-Wakkad, 2007).

4.6.2. *Chirothrips meridionalis* Bagnall

Chirothrips meridionalis Bagnall, 1927, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (9), XIX: 566.

Common name: Broomcorn thrips.

Distribution: Algeria, Cyprus, France, India, Iran, Italy, North and South Africa Palestine, Morocco Nigeria and Yemen (Minaei, 2013 and Moritz *et al.* , 2013).

Host plants: *Andropogon halepensis*, *Polypogon monspeliensis* and *Zea mays* (Priesner, 1960).

4.6.3. *Chirothrips mexicanus* Crawford

Chirothrips mexicanus Crawford, 1909, Pomona College Jour Ent., I, 114.

Chirothrips floridensis Watson, 1920, Fla. Ent., IV (2) :21.

Distribution: Hawaii, India, Mexico, Philippines and South America (Moritz *et al.*, 2013)

Host plant: *Glycine max* (Abd El-Wahab, 2016).

4.6.4. *Chirothrips taxanus* Andre

Chirothrips taxanus Andre, 1939, Proc. Ent. Soc. Wash., XLI (6): 200-202.

Distribution: Brazil, Georgia, Mexico and Texas (Diffie *et al.*, 2008 and Monteiro, 2001).

Host plant: *Cucumis sativus* (Abd El-Wahab, 2012).

4.7. *Dorcadothrips* Priesner

Dorcadothrips Priesner, 1932, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 49.

4.7.1. *Dorcadothrips caespitis* Priesner

Dorcadothrips caespitis Priesner, 1932, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 50.

Common name: Cat`s tail thrips.

Host plants: *Cyperus* sp., *Typha* sp. and *Panicum colonum* (Priesner, 1960).

Distribution: Sudan (Priesner, 1960).

4.8. *Eremiothrips* Priesner

Eremiothrips Priesner, 1950, Bull. Soc. Fouad I Ent., 29.

This genus contains of twenty-one species and represents in Egypt by one species.

4.8.1. *Eremiothrips imitator* Priesner

Eremiothrips imitator Priesner, 1950, Bull. Soc. Fouad I Ent., 29.

Host plant: *Haloxylon schweinfurthii* (Priesner, 1960).

4.9. *Euphysothrips* Bagnall

Euphysothrips Bagnall, 1926. Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (9), 18: 646.

Two species only have been known in this genus.

4.9.1. *Euphysothrips minozzii* Bagnall

Euphysothrips minozzii Bagnall, 1926. Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (9), 18: 646.

Common name: Sea rush thrips.

Distribution: Austria, Canary Islands, India, Iran, Iseral, Mozambique, Southern Africa, Southern France, Turkey, and Yemen (Zur Strassen and Kuslitzky, 2012).

Host plants: Gramineae and *Juncus acutus* (Priesner, 1960).

4.10 . *Frankliniella* Karny

Frankliniella Karny, 1910, Mitt. Nat. Ver. Univ. Wien, 46.

Most species live in neotropics area. Some species as *F. fusca*, *F. occidentalis* and *F. schultzei* have been known as virus transmitted. The members of this genus are flower feeding. Two-hundred and thirty-four species are listed from this genus. On the other hand, only five species represent in Egypt.

4.10.1. *Frankliniella dampfi* Priesner

Frankliniella pallid Karny (nec Uzel), 1922, Denkschr. Akad. Wiss. Wien, 98: 114.

Frankliniella dampfi Priesner, 1923, Ent. Mitteil., 12: 64.

Frankliniella sulphurea Karny, 1926, Mem, Dept. Agric. Ind., Ent. Ser., 9: 195.

Common name: African borage thrips and Lantana thrips.

Distribution: India, Italy, Palestine and Sudan (Priesner, 1960).

Host plants: *Alhagi maurorum*, *Arnebia hispidissima*, *Inula crithmoides*, *Iphiona mucronata*, *Pulicaria crispa*, *Trichodesma africanum*, *Triumfetta flavescens* and *Withania somnifera* (Priesner, 1960).

4.10.2. *Frankliniella fusca* Karny

Euthrips fuscus Hinds 1902. Zool. Stud. 49 (6): 826

Frankliniella fusca Karny 1912. Zool. Stud. 49 (6): 826

Common name: Tobacco thrips.

Distribution: Brazil, China, Florida, Georgia, Guadeloupe, Martinique, Spain and U. S. A (Diffie *et al.*, 2008; Monteiro, 2001; Goldarazena *et al.*, 2012; Reitz *et al.*, 2011 and Etienne *et al.*, 2015).

Host plant: *Glycine max* (Abd El-Wahab, 2016).

4.10.3. *Frankliniella occidentalis* Pergande

Euthrips occidentalis Pergande. 1895. U.S.D.A., Div. Ent. Insect Life, 7 (5):392.

Euthrips tritici californicus Moulton, 1911. U.S.D.A., Bur. Ent., Tech. Ser., 21: 28.

Frankliniella occidentalis (Pergaade), Kamy, 1912. Zool. Ann., 4:335.

Fmnkliniella tritici Moultoni, Hood. 1914. Proc. Ent. SOC. Wash., 16:38.

Frankliniella californica Moulton, 1948. Rev. de Ent., 19(1-2):98.

Common name: Western flower thrips, Alfalfa thrips.

Distribution: Widespread around the world (Mirab-balou, 2013).

Host plants: *Citrus* sp., *Antirrhinum majus*, *Begonia tuberhybrida*, *Capsicum annuum*, *Celosia argentea*,

Chenopodium amaranticolor, *Chrysanthemum morifolium*, *Coleus hybridus*, *Convolvulus arvensis*, *Crinum moorei*, *Cucumis sativus*, *Euphorbia seguieriana*, *Gazania rigens*, *Gladiolus grandiflora*, *Glycine max*, *Gomphrena globosa*, *Hippeastrum hybrid*, *H. vittatum*, *Ipomoea tricolor*, *Kalanchoe blossfeldiana*, *Lantana camara*, *Malus pumila*, *Mangifera indica*, *Olea europaea*, *Pelargonium hortorum*, *Petunia hybrid*, *Psidium guajava*, *Ranunculus ficaria*, *Rosa hybrid*, *Solanum nigrum*, *Tropaeolum majus*, *Vinca minor* and *Vitis vinifera* (El-Wakkad, 2007; Abd El-Wahab et al., 2011; Shalaby, 2015; Abd El-Wahab, 2016 and Wafy, 2018).

4.10.4. *Frankliniella schultzei* (Trybom)

Frankliniella schultzei (Trybom, 1910), Raff. Bull. Zool. 42(2):220.

Physopus schultzei Trybom, 1910, Raff. Bull. Zool. 42(2):220.

Frankliniella insularis Moulton, 1936, Raff. Bull. Zool. 42(2):220.

Common name: Common blossom thrips, cotton bud thrips, Tomato thrips and Yellow flower thrips.

Distribution: Tropical to subtropical and southern Mediterranean, America, Angola, Asia, Cape Verde, Benin, Botswana, Burkina Faso, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Congo, Ethiopia, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Kenya, Libya, Madagascar, Mauritius, Morocco, Namibia, New Zealand, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Somalia, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Togo, Tunisia, Uganda, Zambia and Zimbabwe (Moritz et al., 2013).

Host plant: *Glycine max* (Abd El-Wahab, 2016).

4.10.5. *Frankliniella tritici* (Fitch)

Frankliniella varicorne Bagnall, 1919. Bull. Bri. Mus. Ent. 9, II: 39

Thrips tritici Fitch 1948. Bull. Bri. Mus. Ent. 9, II: 39.

Common name: Eastern flower thrips.
Host plant: *Glycine max* (Abd El-Wahab, 2016).

4.11. *Isoneurothrips* Bagnall

Isoneurothrips Bagnall 1915, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (8), 15: 592.

4.11.1. *Isoneurothrips australis* Bagnall

Isoneurothrips australis Bagnall 1915, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (8), 15: 592.

Thrips mediolinus Girault 1926, Ins. Insc. Menstr., 18.

Anomalothrips amygdali Morgan, 1929, Proc. Ent. Soc. Wash, 31: 5.

Common name: Oat thrips.

Distribution: Cyprus, Europe and Turkey (Tunc et al., 2012; Marullo and De Grazia, 2013 and Mirab-balou, 2013).

Host plant: *Avena sativa* (Priesner, 1960).

4.12. *Limothrips* Haliday

Limothrips Haliday, 1836, Ent. Mag., 445.

These species all breed in grass and can cause reduction of cereal yield. *Limothrips* recently includes eight species spread around the world. Of these, two species recorded in Egypt.

4.12.1. *Limothrips angulicornis* Jablonowski

Limothrips angulicornis Jablonowski, 1894, Term. Fuzetek, XVII: 45.

Distribution: Europe, Iran, Italy, North America, Sardinia, Turkey and Western Asia (Moritz et al., 2013).

Host plants: *Hordeum* Sp. and Wild grasses (Priesner, 1960).

4.12.2. *Limothrips cerealium* Haliday

Limothrips cerealium Haliday, 1836, Ent. Mag., 445.

Limothrips auenae Hinds, 1902. Proc. U.S. Nat. Mus., 26(1310):139-141.

Common name: Barley thrips, Cereal thrips, Grain thrips and thunder thrips.

Distribution: Worldwide (Moritz et al., 2013).

Host plants: *Citrus* sp., *Agrostis verticillata*, *Alopecurus agrestis*, *Avena fatua*, *Cynodon dactylon*, *Imperata cylindrical*, *Hordeum vulgare*, *H. maritimum*, *Mangifera indica*, *Panicum turgidum*, *Phalaris paradoxa*; *Phragmites communis*, *Polypogon monspeliensis*, *Psidium guajava*, *Pyrus malus*, *Saccharum officinarum*, *Sorghum halepense*, *Triticum vulgare* and *Vitis vinifera* (Priesner, 1960 and El-Wakkad, 2007).

4.13. *Megalurothrips* Bagnall

Megalurothrips Bagnall, 1915. Ann. Mag. nat. Hist., (8) 15: 589.

All species seem to associate with *Legumin*. Fourteen species are listed in this genus have been recoded.

4.13.1. *Megalurothrips sjostedti* (Trybom)

Physopus sjostedti Trybom. 1908, Wisr. Ergeb. Schwed. Zool. Exped. Kilimandjaro. Meru 1905-06, 3 (16): 4-6.

Physopus variabilis Bagnall, 1913, Ann. Mag. nat. Hist., (8) 12: 294.

Taeniothrips variabilis Steinweden, 1933, Trans. Amer. Ent. Soc., 59: 273-274.

Taeniothrips sjostedti Steinweden, 1933, Trans. Amer. Ent. Soc., 59: 275.

Common name: Bean flower thrips and African bean thrips.

Distribution: Afrotropical Region, Angola, Burundi, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Cape Verde Islands, Chad, Congo, Gabon, Ghana, Gambia, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Mozambique, Niger, Nigeria, Senegal, Seychelles, South Africa, Tanzania, Togo, Uganda, Yemen and Zimbabwe (Moritz *et al.* , 2013).

Host plant: *Glycine max* (Abd El-Wahab, 2016).

4.14. *Microcephalothrips* Bagnall

Microcephalothrips Bagnall 1926, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (9), 18: 113.

It lives in flowers of Asteraceae. This genus presents by only one species widespread.

4.14.1. *Microcephalothrips abdominalis* (D. L. Crawford)

Thrips abdominalis D. L. Crawford, 1910, Pomona, Coll. Journ., 157.

Thrips microcephalus Priesner, 1923, Ent. Mitteil., 12:160.

Microcephalothrips abdominalis Priesner, 1937, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 209.

Common name: Composite thrips and Sunflower thrips.

Distribution: Widespread (Moritz *et al.*, 2013).

Host plants: Compositae, *Chenopodium* sp, *Chrysanthemum* sp, *Tagetes* sp, *Ageratum conyzoides*, *Erigeron crispus*, *Mangifera indica*, *Pulicaria crispa* and *Vitis vinifera* (Priesner, 1960 and El-Wakkad, 2007).

4.15. *Mycterothrips* Karny

Mycterothrips Karny, 1926, Mem. Dept. Agric. Ind., Ent., IX, 199.

Widely spread in Asia, Europe and America in flowers and leaf litter. All species concentrate in old world. Thirty-six species have been identifying in this genus.

4.15.1. *Mycterothrips acacia* Priesner

Mycterothrips acacia Priesner, 1932, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 5, 142.

Common name: Acacia flower thrips.

Distribution: India (Rachana and Varatharajan, 2017).

Host plant: *Acacia nilotica* (Priesner, 1960).

4.15.2. *Mycterothrips echii* Priesner

Mycterothrips echii Priesner , 1931, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 129.

Host plant: *Echium sericeum* (Priesner, 1960).

4.16. *Odontothrips* Serville

Odontothrips Serville, 1843, Ins. Hemipt., 643.

This genus is flower-feeding thrips, especially Legume plant. It consists of thirty-five species spread around the world.

4.16.1. *Odontothrips elbaensis* Priesner

Odontothrips elbaensis Priesner, 1933, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 6.

Common name: Gebel elba thrips.

Host plant: Weeds (Priesner, 1960).

16.2- *Odontothrips karnyi* Priesner

Odontothrips karnyi Priesner, 1924, Konowia, 3: 1.

Common name: Broad bean thrips.

Distribution: Canary Islands, Cyprus, Italy, Palestine and Sudan (Moritz et al., 2013).

Host plants: *Leguminosae*, *Lypinus* sp., *Lathyrus odoratus*, *Medicago hispsida*, *Melilotus messanensis*, *Retama raetam* and *Vicia faba* (Priesner, 1960).

4.17. *Oxythrips* Uzel

Oxythrips Uzel, 1895, Mon. Ord. Thys. 133.

Oxythrips includes thirty-five species.

4.17.1. *Oxythrips tamaricis* (Bagnall)

Anaphothrips tamaricis Bagnall, 1926, Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (9), 18: 645.

Oxythrips narasi Bagnall, 1926 Ann. Mag. Nat. Hist. (9), 18: 648.

Oxythrips tamaricis Priesner, 1938, Bull. Soc. Fouad I Ent., 123.

Common name: Tamarisk thrips.

Host plants: *Juncus* sp., *Suaeda* sp. and *Tamarix nilotica* (Priesner, 1960).

4.18. *Parexothrips* Priesner

Parexothrips Priesner 1960, Publ. Inst. Desert Egypte 13:285.

Old World genus, from Poaceae. Nineteen species have been recorded of this genus.

4.18.1. *Parexothrips tenellus* Priesner

Exothrips tenellus Priesner, 1950, Bull. Soc. Fouad I Ent., 30.

Parexothrips tenellus, Priesner, 1960, Publ. Inst. Desert Egypte, 13: 286.

Distribution: China and India (Moritz et al., 2013).

Host plant: *Imperata cylindrical* (Priesner, 1960).

4.19. *Phlebothrips* Priesner

Phlebothrips aegyptiacus Priesner, 1960, Publ. Inst. Desert Egypte 13: 283.

4.19.1. *Phlebothrips aegyptiacus* Priesner

Phlebothrips aegyptiacus Priesner, 1960, Publ. Inst. Desert Egypte 13: 284.

Common name: Egyptian thrips.

Distribution: South Africa (Moritz et al., 2013)

Host plants: *Convolvulus arvensis*, *Euphorbia cuneata*, *Lycium arabicum* (Priesner, 1960).

4.20. *Psilothrips* Hood

Psilothrips, Hood 1927, Proc. Biol. Soc. Washington, 40: 198.

Thamnothrips Priesner, 1932, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 2.

This genus represents by five species through the world.

4.20.1. *Psilothrips bimaculatus* Priesner

Thamnothrips bimaculatus Priesner, 1932, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 3.

Common name: Bimaculated thrips.

Distribution: Iran (Mirab-balou, 2013).

Host plant: *Lycium arabicum* (Priesner, 1960).

4.21. *Prosopothrips* Uzel

Prosopothrips Uzel, 1895, Mon. Odr. Thy. 165.

Widespread genus associated with Poaceae. Nine species have been recorded around the world.

4.21.1. *Prosopothrips matrouhensis* Priesner

Prosopothrips matrouhensis Priesner, 1960, Publ. Inst. Desert Egypte 13: 277.

Common name: Matrouh thrips.

Host plant: Low vegetation (Priesner, 1960).

4.21.2. *Prosopothrips nigriceps* Bagnall

Prosopothrips nigriceps Bagnall, 1927, Bull. Bri. Mus. Ent. 9, II: 49.

Distribution: Southern France and Turkey (Priesner, 1937 and Tunc et al., 2012).

Host plant: Grasses (Priesner, 1937).

4.21.3. *Prosopothrips salloumensis* Priesner

Prosopothrips nigriceps Priesner, 1938, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 210.

Prosopothrips salloumensis Priesner, 1960, Publ. Inst. Desert Egypte 13:277.

Common name: Salloum thrips.

Host plant: Grasses (Priesner, 1960).

4.22. *Scirtothrips* Shull

Scirtothrips, Shull, 1909, Ent. News, XX: 222.

Species of the genus *Scirtothrips* are small, active thrips. They breed on the young leaves and flowers of plants. Several species are recognized as pests on citrus trees, coffee, and tea. The total number of described *Scirtothrips* is about one hundred and five species. In Egypt, the genus consists of three species.

4.22.1. *Scirtothrips aurantii* Faure

Scirtothrips aurantii Faure, 1929, Transv. Univ. Coll., Bull. 18: 3.

Common name: South African citrus thrips.

Distribution: Subtropics and tropics of Africa, introduced to Queensland (Australia), Angola, China, Ethiopia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Malawi, Nigeria, South Africa, Sudan, Tanzania, Uganda, U. S. A. and Zimbabwe (Reitz *et al.*, 2011 and Moritz *et al.*, 2013).

Host plants: *Cassia* sp., *Citrus* sp., *Cynodon* sp., *Panicum* sp., *Salix* sp., *Acacia nilotica*, *Convolvulus arvensis*, *Mangifera indica*, *Malus pumila*, *Olea europaea*, *Psidium guajava* and *Vitis vinifera* (Priesner, 1960; El-Wakkad, 2007 and Wafy, 2018)

4.22.2. *Scirtothrips citri* Moulton

Eutrips Citri Moulton, 1909. U.S.D.A., Bur. Ent., Tech. Ser. 12, pt. VII: 121-122.

Physothrips citri, Karny, 1912. 2001. Ann., 4:339.

Scirtothrips citri, Hood, 1914. Proc. Ent. Soc. Wash., 16(1):40.

Common name: Citrus thrips.

Distribution: China, Florida, Georgia, Iran and U. S. A. (Diffie *et al.*, 2008 and Reitz *et al.*, 2011)

Host plant: *Citrus* sp. (Salem *et al.*, 2017)

4.22.3. *Scirtothrips dorsallis* Hood

Scirtothrips dorsallis Hood, 1919, Bull. Bri. Mus. Ent. 9, II: 51.

Heliiothrips minutissimus Bagnall, 1919, Bull. Bri. Mus. Ent. 9, II: 51.

Common names: Castor thrips, Chilli thrips, Strawberry thrips and Yellow tea thrips.

Distribution: Oriental and Pacific Region, China, Israel, Ivory Coast, Sri Lanka, South Africa and U. S. A. (Tillekaratne *et al.*, 2011; Reitz *et al.*, 2011; Zur Strassen and Kuslitzky, 2012 and Moritz *et al.*, 2013).

Host plant: *Glycine max* (Abd El-Wahab, 2016).

4.22.4. *Scirtothrips mangiferae* Priesner

Scirtothrips mangiferae Priesner, 1932, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 141-155.

Common name: Mango thrips.

Distribution: Afrotropical and Eastern Mediterranean, Gabon, India, Iran, Libya, Sudan and Yemen (Priesner, 1960; Mirab-balou, 2013 and Moritz *et al.*, 2013).

Host plants: *Citrus* sp., *Ficus carica*, *Mangifera indica*, *Parkinsonia aculeate*, *Pyrus malus* and *Vitis vinifera* (Priesner, 1932 and El-Wakkad, 2007).

4.22.5. *Scirtothrips nubicus* Priesner

Scirtothrips nubicus Priesner, 1936, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 84.

Common name: common fig thrips.

Distribution: Israel and Sudan (Zur Strassen and Kuslitzky, 2012).

Host plants: *Citrus* sp., *Ficus carica*, *Mangifera indica* and *Parkinsonia aculeate* (Priesner, 1960).

4.23. *Scolothrips* Hinds

Scolothrips Hinds 1902, Mon. Thys. N. Amer. 157.

Worldwide thrips. Originally, it appears in old world country. It is predator of Tetranychid mites. Sixteen species have been described through the world.

4.23.1. *Scolothrips latipennis* Priesner

Scolothrips sexmaculatus uzeli Priesner, 1923, Entom. Mitteil., 12: 66, 115.

Scolothrips uzeli Priesner, 1926, Thys. Eur., 241.

Scolothrips latipennis Priesner, 1950, Bull. Soc. Fouad I Ent., 54.

Distribution: Canary Isalnds Crimea, Europe, Iran, Morocco and Spain (Mirab-balou, 2013).

Host plant: Predator of Tetranychidae (Priesner, 1960).

4.23.2. *Scolothrips longicornis* Priesner

Scolothrips longicornis Priesner , 1926, Thys. Eur., 239.

Common name: Tetranychid Predator thrips.

Distribution: Austria, China, Denmark, Finland, Iran, Iceland, Norway, Sweden, Russia and Turkey (Kobro, 2011; Mirab-balou et al., 2011; Tunc et al., 2012 and Mirab-balou, 2013).

Host plant: Predator of Tetranychidae (Priesner, 1960).

4.23.3. *Scolothrips rhagebianus* Priesner

Scolothrips rhagebianus Priesner , 1950, Bull. Soc. Fouad I Ent., 46.

Common name: Okra thrips.

Distribution: China, India, Iran, South Africa and Sudan (Mirab-balou et al., 2011 and Mirab-balou, 2013).

Host plant: Predator of Tetranychidae (Priesner, 1960).

4.24. *Sitothrips* Priesner

Sitothrips Priesner 1931, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 127.

Five species belonged to this genus spread from Europe, Mediterranean region and Africa.

4.24.1. *Sitothrips arabicus* Priesner

Sitothrips arabicus Priesner 1931, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 127.

Distribution: Cyprus, Iran and Georgia (Priesner, 1960 and Mirab-balou, 2013).

Host plants: Grasses and *Hordeum vulgare* (Priesner, 1960).

4.25. *Stenothrips* Uzel

Stenothrips Uzel, 1895, Mon. Ord. Thys. 209.

One species have been identifying, it breads on Poaceae.

4.25.1. *Stenothrips graminum* Uzel

Stenothrips graminum Uzel, 1895, Mon. Ord. Thys. 210.

Common name: Oats thrips.

Distribution: Austria, Croatia, Denmark, Hungary, Finland, Iceland, Iran, Norway, Poland, Sweden and Turkey (Raspudici et al., 2009; Kobro, 2011; Tunc et al., 2012 and Mirab-balou, 2013).

Host plant: Gramineae (Priesner, 1937).

4.26. *Taeniothrips* Amyot and Serville

Taeniothrips Amyot and Serville, 1843, Ins. Hemipt., 644.

They live in flowers and young leaves. It includes thirty-one species. Six species only are valid in Egypt.

4.26.1. *Taeniothrips dianthi* Priesner

Taeniothrips dianthi Priesner, 1921, Wiener Ent. Zeitg., 38: 116, 117.

Common name: Clover pink thrips and carnation thrips.

Distribution: Europe, Morocco, North and South America (Priesner, 1960).

Host plant: *Syzygium aromaticum* (Priesner, 1960).

4.26.2. *Taeniothrips discolor* Karny

Euthrips discolor Karny, 1907, Berliner Ent. Zeitschr., 52:46.

Taeniothrips discolor Priesner, 1926, Thys. Eur., 292.

Common name: Artemisia thrips.

Distribution: Cyprus, Sibiria, South Europe, and Turkey (Priesner, 1960 and Tunc et al., 2012).

Host plants: *Artemisia* sp., *Iphiona mucronata*, *Linaria aegyptiaca* and *Odontospermum graveolens* (Priesner, 1960).

4.26.3. *Taeniothrips niloticus* Priesner

Taeniothrips niloticus Priesner 1930, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 11.

Host plants: *Acacia nilotica*, *Caesalpinia sepiaria* and *Punica granatum* (Priesner, 1960).

4.26.4. *Taeniothrips Sinaiticus* Priesner

Taeniothrips Sinaiticus Priesner 1935, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 318.

Host plants: *Alcanna orientalis* (Priesner, 1960).

4.26.5. *Taeniothrips traegardhi* (Trybom)

Physopus traegardhi Trybom, 1911, Res. Swed. Zool. Exped. Egypt and c., 4, Uppsala, 4.

Taeniothrips niloticus Priesner, 1930, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 11.

Taeniothrips traegardhi Priesner, 1938, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 210.

Distribution: India and Sudan (Priesner, 1960).

Host plants: Grasses, *Caesalpinia sepiaria*, *Lycium arabicum*, *Polypogon monspeliensis*, *Pulica crispa*, *Punica granatum*, *Scirpus badius* *Sorghum vulgare*; *Triticum vulgare* and *Zea mays* (Priesner, 1960).

4.26.6. *Taeniothrips zillarum* Priesner

Taeniothrips zillarum Priesner, 1950, Bull. Soc. Fouad I Ent., 32.

Common name: Zilla thrips.

Host plant: *Zilla spionsa* (Priesner, 1960).

4.27. *Thamnothrips* Priesner

Thamnothrips Priesner, 1932. Bull. Soc. Fouad I Ent., 2.

4.27.1. *Thamnothrips bimaculatus* Priesner

Thamnothrips bimaculatus Priesner, 1932. Bull. Soc. Fouad I Ent., 3.

Host plant: Desert bushes (Priesner, 1932).

4.28. *Thrips* Linne

Thrips Linne, 1776, Fauna Suecica, Ed. I, 220.

It is considered as the largest genus of Thysanoptera, it widespread of the world. Species are leaf and flower feeding, most of them are pest of many plants. Two-hundred and ninety six species have been described.

4.28.1. *Thrips angusticeps* Uzel

Thrips angusticeps Uzel, 1895, Mon. Ord. Thys. 191.

Achaetothrips lobopectera Karny and Bagnallia, Amer. Publ. Co., New Delhi, Indica. 240.

Distribution: Asia, Austria, Canary Islands, Czech Republic, Denmark, England, Europe, Iceland, Iran, Italy, Finland, Morocco, Norway, Palestine, Siberia, Sweden and Turkey (Kobro, 2011; Mirab-balou, 2013 and Moritz *et al.*, 2013).

Host plants: *Triticum* Sp., *Cistanche lutea*, *Chrysanthemum coronarium*, *Convolvulus arvensis*, *Hordeum vulgare* and *Reichardia tingitana* (Priesner, 1960).

4.28.2. *Thrips mareoticus* Priesner

Stenothrips mareoticus Priesner, 1932, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 10.

Thrips quadrisetosus Hood, 1932, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 124.

Thrips tenuisetosus Ruxgs, 1935, (nec Knechtel), Bull. Soc. Sci. Nat. Maroc, 15: 4.

Thrips mareoticus Priesner, 1937, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 210.

Common name: Lavender cotton thrips.

Distribution: Asia, Cyprus, Iran, Germany, Morocco, Palestine and Turkey (Mirab-balou, 2013 and Moritz *et al.*, 2013).

Host plants: Compositae, *Achillea santolina*, *Chrysanthemum coronarium* and *Reichardia tingitana* (Priesner, 1960).

4.28.3. *Thrips mediterraneus* Priesner

Thrips mediterraneus Priesner, 1934, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 276.

Distribution: Armenia, Cyprus, Europe, Iran, Iraq, Israel, Georgia, Northern India, Lebanon, South Ukraine and Turkey (Mirab-balou, 2013 and Moritz *et al.*, 2013).

Host plant: *Phlomis floccose* (Priesner, 1960).

4.28.4. *Thrips microchaetus* Karny

Thrips flavus var. *microchatus* Karny, 1920. Akad. Anzeig, 2.

Thrips microchatus Hood, 1923, Ent. Mitteil., 13: 116.

Common name: Grapevine leaf thrips.

Distribution: Sudan (Priesner, 1960).

Host plants: *Aerva tomentosa*, *Olea europaea*, *Pulicaria crispa*, *Triumfetta flavescens*, and *Vitis vinifera* (Priesner, 1960 and Wafy, 2018).

4.28.5. Thrips nigropilosus Uzel

Thrips nigropilosa Uzel, 1895. Mon. Ord. Thys., 198.

Thrips nigmpilosus, Priesner. 1927. Thys. Eur., 409-414.

Common name: Chrysanthemum thrips.

Distribution: Australia, Canada, China, Croatia, Denmark, Ethiopia, Europe, Fiji, Finland, Hawaii, Iceland, Iran, Japan, Kenya, New Zealand, Norway, Russia, Sweden, Tanzania, Turkey and U.S.A. (Raspudici et al., 2009; Kobro, 2011; Mirab-balou, 2013 and Moritz et al., 2013).

Host plants: *Althaea* Sp. and *Pyrethrum cinerariaefolium* (Priesner, 1937).

4.28.6. Thrips palmi Karny

Thrips palmi Karny, 1925, Raff. Bull. Zool. 42(2): 285.

Distribution: Brazil, China, Denmark, Finland, Guadeloupe, Iceland, India, Martinique, Norway, Sweden, Sri Lanka, Spain and U. S. A. (Monteiro, 2001; Kobro, 2011; Reitz et al., 2011; Tillekaratne et al., 2011; Etienne et al., 2015 and Rachana and Varatharajan, 2017).

Host plants: *Cucumis sativus* and *Glycine max* (Abd EL-Wahab et al., 2012 and Abd El-Wahab, 2016).

4.28.7. Thrips simplex Morison

Physothrips simplex Morison, 1930, Raff. Bull. Zool. 42(2):288.

Thrips simplex Bhatti, 1969, Raff. Bull. Zool. 42(2):288.

Common name: Gladiolus thrips.

Distribution: Australia, Canada, Europe, Hawaii, India, Spain, South Africa, Turkey and U. S. A. (Tillekaratne et al., 2011; Tunc et al., 2012 and Rachana and Varatharajan, 2017)

Host plant: *Gladiolus antakiensis* (Priesner, 1960).

4.28.8. Thrips tabaci Lindeman

Thrips tabaci Lindeman, 1888. Schadl. Ins. d. Tabaks. i. Bessarabien, 15: 61-65.

T. communis Uzel, 1895. Mon. Ord. Thys., 176.

T. bremmenii Moulton, 1907. U.S.D. A., Bull. Ent., Tech.Ser. 12: 59-60.

Common name: Onion thrips, cotton thrips.

Distribution: Widespread (across all the countries).

Host plant: Different kind of plants.

4.29. Trichromothrips Priesner

Trichromothrips Priesner, 1930, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 9.

Thirty-eight species have been recorded.

4.29.1. Trichromothrips bellus Priesner

Trichromothrips bellus Priesner, 1930, Bull. Soc. R. Ent. Egypte, 9.

Common name: Papyrus thrips and seedling barely thrips, wheat thrips.

Distribution: India (Rachana and Varatharajan, 2017).

Host plant: Cyperaceae (Priesner, 1960).

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Native larval parasitoids of fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda* (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae), the recent invasive pest on maize in Egypt and its some biological aspects

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Abstract:

The fall armyworm (FAW) *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J.E. Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is the recent invasive pest species, it spreads successfully across Kom-Ombo city of Aswan Governorate, Upper Egypt in May 2019. It disrupts agriculture, particularly smallholder grain production such as maize cultivation. This study was undertaken to document two parasitoids, *Exorista sorbillans* (Wiedemann) and *Pseudogonia rufifrons* (Wiedemann) (Diptera; Tachinidae) and one parasitoid species *Microplitis* sp. (Hymenoptera: Braconidae), were detected from infected FAW larvae which, were collected from maize fields during August, September, and October. The highest parasitism rate was recorded on 1st October in two locations at Aswan by 30.77%. Moreover, some biological aspects of FAW were recorded, which an average of 156.13 ±16.57 eggs/mass were emerged after an average of 3.47 days, with hatchability of 89.18%. Larval and pupal average duration were 20.93 and 12.60 days, respectively, pre-oviposition, oviposition and post-oviposition were 11, 5.13 and 4.93 days respectively.

Introduction

Fall armyworm (FAW) *Spodoptera frugiperda* (J.E. Smith) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) outbreak was recorded for the first time in early 2016 in West and Central Africa and have currently become the new invasive species in Africa (Goergen *et al.*, 2016). The insect continued invasion and spread across African countries until it was registered in Kom-Ombo city of Aswan Governorate, Upper Egypt in May 2019. FAW is a polyphagous pest, but its greatest harm in Egypt affects maize plants. Many governments have relied on synthetic pesticides, including highly toxic ones, to control the spread of the insect, such as Ethiopia and Kenya, and the effect differs in both

(Prasanna *et al.*, 2018 and Kumela *et al.*, 2019). Among the environmental alternatives that have previously been used for combating FAW is biological control, especially parasitoids (Sisay *et al.*, 2018 and Agboyi *et al.*, 2020). The invasive species often invade a new environment without their natural enemies, which promotes their multiplication and damage to crops. Since, the arrival of the pest to Africa, many studies have been conducted on its natural enemies, which have confirmed the presence of parasitoids of eggs and larvae (Koffi *et al.*, 2020; Castillo, 2020; Kenis *et al.*, 2019; Amadou *et al.*, 2018; Sisay *et al.*, 2018 and Agboyi *et al.*, 2020). The invasive FAW is close to several of local pests

on maize and sorghum by family Noctuidae such as *Eublemma gayneri* Hübner and *Helicoverpa armigera* (Hübner), or close in terms of the genus, *Spodoptera* such as *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd.) and *S. exigua* (Hübner) (El-Gepaly, 2019 and Youssef, 2018), those local pests have a rich array of indigenous natural enemies, which have an opportunity to fight *S. frugiperda*. Hence, there is a need to identify the adapting natural enemies of fall armyworm in Egypt, which could be used for its IPM in the future.

Tachinidae of Diptera and Braconidae of Hymenoptera are important parasitoid families that attack a wide range of agricultural pests around the world. El-Hawagry (2018) summarized the distribution of *Exorista sorbillans* (Wiedemann) and *Pseudogonia rufifrons* (Wiedemann) around the world, African countries, and Egypt. Sharanabasappa *et al.*, (2019) recorded negligible levels of parasitism of FAW by *E. sorbillans* in South India. Gözüaçik *et al.* (2007) found *P. rufifrons* as a larval- pupal parasitoid of *Acantholeucania loreyi* (Duponchel) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae). Also, Braconidae of Hymenoptera recorded on Lepidoptera hosts including *S. littoralis* in many countries including Egypt (Hammad *et al.*, 1965; Shalaby, 1968; Ibrahim, 1974 and Abou Zeid *et al.*, 1978).

This study was undertaken to document three parasitoids of fall armyworm and record the field parasitism in Kom-Ombo, Aswan, Egypt. Also, highlight some biological aspects of FAW.

Materials and methods

1. Larval parasitoid detection:

Natural enemies of fall armyworm larvae were surveyed by collecting host larvae from maize fields in four farmer fields located around Kom-Ombo (Munihah, El-Bayyarah, Iqlit, and El-Sapeel), Aswan

Governorate. Fertilizers and weed control were applied in all fields during planting and hilling. Forty FAW larvae ($20 \leq 3^{\text{rd}}$ larval instar and $20 \geq 4^{\text{th}}$ larval instar) were collected during August, September, and October 2020. Each larva was reared in a transparent plastic container tightly sealed with a silk cloth (50 ml capacity) under an average temperature of 26 ± 2 °C and RH. $\% = 50 \pm 5\%$. Daily, the transparent container was examined from the outside to ensure the presence of parasites, data were recorded, Castor leaves were introduced daily as a feed, and jars get cleaned till parasitoid emergence or normal pupation. Dead pupae due to unknown reasons or bad handling were subtracted from totals. The percentage of parasitism was calculated according to the occurrence of parasitism (Emergence of larval parasitoids from FAW larvae), even if the parasitoid adults not occurred. Samples were preserved appropriately and transferred to identify.

2. Taxonomic Studies:

Insect specimens that were used for the taxonomic study were collected from the injured Maize plants in four locations in Kom-Ombo (Munihah, El-Bayyarah, Iqlit and El-Sapeel), Aswan, Egypt during the 2020 maize season. Material examined were; one parasitoid from one late larva at Munihah, El-Bayyarah and El-Sapeel areas on 1st Oct, three parasitoids from one late larva at Iqlit area on 1st Oct and 16 parasitoids from one early larva at Iqlit area on 2nd Sept. The specimens were killed by Ethyl acetate, and then pinned or preserved in vials or drier Eppendorf by freezing at -4C° till used for easily dissection and study their parts for explained taxonomic characters. An illustrated key to the subfamilies, tribe, genera, and species is presented. The Identification occurs at the classification Department, Plant Protection Research Institute. Each

identified species measured by an ocular micrometer after calibration attached to the dissecting microscope Olympus (Stereomicroscope) for photography of the specimens. The identified specimens were deposited in the side Collection of the Classification Department – Plant Protection Research Institute.

3. Biological aspects of fall armyworm *Spodoptera frugiperda*:

Biological aspects of FAW were carried out in Shandaweel Bio-control Lab., Bio-Control Department, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, at Shandaweel Research Station, Sohag Governorate, Egypt. (Latitude 26° 38' 05" N, Longitude 31° 39' 31" E) under an average temperature of 26±2 °C and 50±5% RH. in October and November 2020. Fifteen egg clusters were obtained from existing colony for the study of some biological aspects of FAW. The experiment was carried out at controlled temp. (25±2 °C) and RH.% (55±5%) room, in early October 2020. Data were recorded every day; the newly hatched larvae were transferred immediately upon hatches to avoid their predation of the remaining eggs. Each ten newly hatched larvae (For each egg cluster) were kept together in a 2-liter plastic jar covered with fine close fabric. Cutting of castor leaves were used for feed 1st – 3rd larval instars and replaced daily, the oldest instars were supplied with five castor leaves, so that the ten larvae were distributed between the leaves to avoid cannibalism. Daily observations were made, and larval development and duration were estimated. Pupal periods were estimated by isolated each pupa in a plastic tube (2 X7 cm) covered with a piece of cotton until the adults emerged. Some biological aspects such as, incubation period, total immature

stages, life cycle, longevity, sex ratio, generation, and life span were recorded,

4. Statistical analysis:

Standard error for each biological parameter of FAW was calculated to declare data dispersal data around the means.

Parasitism ratio was calculated according to the following formula:

$$\text{Parasitism\%} = \frac{\text{No. of parasitized larvae} * 100}{\text{Total collected no.} - (\text{parasitized} + \text{dead})} * 100$$

Results and discussion

1. Parasitism ratio:

The percentage of parasitism on fall armyworm larvae was measured as soon as any of the parasitoid stages were observed during the breeding of the collected FAW larvae. Only 6 of 36 samples of parasitoid stages were developed into the adults, which will be accurately described in the next section. Data in Table (1) discuss the parasitism ratio on FAW larvae ($\geq 3^{\text{rd}}$ instar and $\leq 4^{\text{th}}$ instar) during the last three months of maize season, 2020 in four locations at Kom-Ombo, Aswan, Egypt.

Parasitism starts to appear on 2nd August sample of El-Bayyarah location on late larvae, where one pupa of the parasitoid was exited from larvae with 5.56% parasitism from pupated larvae. Parasitized larvae were continued to record at a relatively higher rate during the last three examination dates (for large larvae), and the highest parasitism rates were recorded in the last examination date in Iqlit and El- Sapeel locations by 30.77%. Only two of the small larvae that were collected showed signs of parasitism (Without the adults leaving the parasite for unknown reasons) in all sites and often in the last two examinations, with 11.76% parasitism as the highest rate in Iqlit on 2nd September.

Table (1): Parasitoids and parasitism rates resulting from incubation of 40 larvae from four sites in Kom-Ombo, Aswan, Egypt in 2020 maize season.

Munihah											
Sample	early larvae	Following				late larvae	Following				Parasitism %
		Developed to Pupae	Dead	parasitized	Parasitism %		Developed to Pupae	Dead	parasitized	Parasitism %	
1st Aug	20	20	0	0	0.00	20	2	0	0.00	0.00	
2nd Aug	20	18	2	0	0.00	20	1	0	0.00	0.00	
1st Sept	20	20	0	0	0.00	20	0	2	11.11		
2nd Sept	20	15	4	1	6.67	20	1	1	5.56		
1st Oct	20	14	5	1	7.14	20	0	3*	17.65		
El-Bayyarah											
1st Aug	20	17	3	0	0	20	0	0	0.00		
2nd Aug	20	18	2	0	0	20	2	1	5.88		
1st Sept	20	17	2	1	5.88	20	3	2	13.33		
2nd Sept	20	16	3	1	6.25	20	3	1	6.25		
1st Oct	20	19	1	0	0	20	4	2**	14.29		
Iqlit											
1st Aug	20	18	2	0	0.00	20	1	0	0.00		
2nd Aug	20	18	2	0	0.00	20	2	0	0.00		
1st Sept	20	18	2	0	0.00	20	2	2	12.50		
2nd Sept	20	17	1	2	11.76	20	2	2***	12.50		
1st Oct	20	19	1	0	0.00	20	3	4**	30.77		
El-Sapeel											
1st Aug	20	17	3	0	0.00	20	3	0	0.00		
2nd Aug	20	18	2	0	0.00	20	3	0	0.00		
1st Sept	20	15	4	1	6.67	20	2	2	12.50		
2nd Sept	20	16	3	1	6.25	20	4	1	6.67		
1st Oct	20	17	2	1	5.88	20	3	4**	30.77		

Parasitoids that completed their life cycle

* *Exorista (Podotachina) sorbillans* (Wiedemann)

** *Pseudogonia rufifrons* (Wiedemann)

*** *Microplitis sp. Foerster*

2. Taxonomical study:

Three larval parasitoids belonging to order Diptera (Two parasitoids) and Hymenoptera (One parasitoid) were detected from FAW larvae that collected from maize fields at Kom-Ombo district in the 2020 season. These parasitoids were:

2.1. *Exorista (Podotachina) sorbillans* (Wiedemann, 1830) :

Exorista (Podotachina) sorbillans (Wiedemann, 1830)

Tachina sorbillans Wiedemann, 1830: 311. Lectotype male (NHMW). Canary Islands (Tenerife). **Order:** Diptera

Family: Tachinidae **Subfamily:** Exoristinae **Tribe:** Exoristini

Distribution: AF: Cameroon, Canary Is., D.R. Congo, Kenya, Malawi, Nigeria, Sierra Leone, Uganda. OR: India, Indonesia, Nepal, Orient. China [see O'Hara and Cerretti 2016: 19], Philippines, Ryukyu Is., Sri Lanka, Taiwan, Thailand, Vietnam. Australasian: Australia, N. Australasian. PA: C. Asia (Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan), Egypt, Europe, Israel, Japan, Mongolia,

and China. Egyptian localities and dates of collection are not precisely known.

The larvae (which were collected for parasitoids detection) were externally examined, two groups of parasitoid eggs Figure 1 (A and B) were observed attached to the head of one larva and another group were attached between the fourth and fifth abdominal segment of the same larva that collected from Munihah area in 1st October 2020. Parasitoid eggs hatched to maggot which immediately penetrated larval cuticle and spend 9 days before the exit of the parasitoid pre-pupae stage outside the caterpillar which turns into pupae within 30 hours. (Figure 1D). Parasitoid pupae were taken 3 days for the emergence of the adult parasitoid Figure 1 (E-J), as the parasitoids were preserved and transferred to the monitoring and Classification Research Department of the Plant Protection Research Institute through the reference insect group. Below the full taxonomic description of these species:

Figure (1): The parasitoid, *Exorista sorbillans* on *Spodoptera frugiperda* larva. A. An egg of parasitoid attached to head capsule. B. Eggs of parasitoid attached between the 4th and 5th abdominal segment. C. Dead larva D. Parasitoid *E. sorbillans* cocoon. E. Dorsal view of adult *E. sorbillans*. F. Lateral view of *E. sorbillans*. G. Dorsal view of *E. sorbillans* abdominal segments. H. Anterior view of *E. sorbillans* head. I. lateral view of *E. sorbillans* head. J. Wing venation.

2.2. *Pseudogonia rufifrons* (Wiedemann)

During the study, one pre-pupal stage of the parasitoid was emerged from two 5th instar of the fall armyworm larvae (Solitary behavior as usual and adult was in healthy form “Figure 2-E”) at El-Bayyarah and El-Sapeel areas on 1st Oct., also three pre-pupal stages of parasitoids were emerged from one 5th instar (gregarious behavior and adult was distorted “Figure 2-H”) of the fall armyworm larvae at Iqlit area on 1st Oct. Pre-pupae turn into pupae within 6 hrs. Figure 2 (C and D). Parasitoid pupae were taken three days for the emergence of the adult parasitoid (Figure 2 E-H), as the parasitoids were preserved and transferred to the monitoring and Classification Research Department of the Plant Protection Research Institute through the reference insect group. Below the full taxonomic description of this species:

Pseudogonia rufifrons (Wiedemann)

Tachina rufifrons Wiedemann, 1830: 318. Lectotype female (ZMUC). China.

Order: Diptera **Family:** Tachinidae
Subfamily: Exoristinae **Tribe:** Exoristini

Distribution: AF: Widespread, including Cape Verde, Nigeria, South Africa, Tanzania, U.A. Emirates, Yemen. AU: Australia, Hawaii, Melanesia, N. Australasian. OR: India, Indonesia, Malaysia, Myanmar, Orient. China (O’Hara and Cerretti 2016), Pakistan, Philippines, Ryukyu Is., Taiwan, Thailand. PA: C. Asia (Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, Uzbekistan), Egypt, all Europe (except British Is.), Japan, Kazakhstan, Korea, M. East (Israel), Mongolia, Pal. China (O’Hara and Cerretti 2016), Russia, and Transcaucasia. Egyptian localities: Coastal Strip, Mariout, Nuzha, Eastern Desert, Wadi Hoff, Gebel Elba, Wadi Edeib, Lower Nile Valley, Delta: Abu Rawash, Sinai, and Wadi El-Tih.

Figure (2): The parasitoid, *Pseudogonia rufifrons* on *Spodoptera frugiperda* larva. A. Infected *Spodoptera frugiperda* larva. B. Dead *Spodoptera frugiperda* larva. C. Maggot of *P. rufifrons* existing of dead *Spodoptera frugiperda* larvae. D. Pupa of *P. rufifrons*. E . Dorsal view of adult *P. rufifrons*. F. Lateral view of adult *P. rufifrons*. G. Interior view of *P. rufifrons* head. H. Dorsal view of distorted adult of *P. rufifrons*.

2.3. *Microplitis* sp.

16 pupae of parasitoid were exerted from one larva from Iqlit area on 2nd Sept 2020 (Figure 3-A), these pupae were emerged to hymenopteran parasitoids after three days of collection

Figure 3 (C-F), as the parasitoids were preserved and transferred to the monitoring and Classification Research Department of the Plant Protection Research Institute through the reference

insect group. Below the full taxonomic description of this species:

Microplitis Foerster, 1862

Type-species: *Microgaster obscure* Nees. Orig. design.

Order: Hymenoptera **Family:** Braconidae
Subfamily: Microgastrinae Foerster, 1862 **Tribe:** Microgastrini Foerster,

Genus *Microplitis* can be recognized by a large areolet, mesopleuron without prepectal carina, roughly sculptured propodeum often with a median longitudinal carina, propodeum evenly curved in the lateral view, shape, and sculpture of first

metasomal tergite, and with a weakly defined groove separating second and third tergum (Nixon, 1965; Mason, 1981; Austin and Dangerfield, 1992; 1993). Genus *Snellenius* Westwood was re-described by Mason (1981).

Distribution: *M. rufiventris* Kok. was recorded in Turkestan by Kokujev (1914) parasitizing *Spodoptera littoralis* Boisd. Also, recorded on *Heliothisarmigera* Hb. And *S. exigua* by (Thompson, 1946 and Gerling, 1971) who reported that this parasitoid was distributed in both Middle East and Europe where it attacks several noctuid species.

Figure (3): The parasitoid *Microplitis* sp, on *Spodoptera frugiperda* larva. A. Pupae emerged from *Spodoptera frugiperda* larva. B. An empty cocoon. C and D. Adult of *Microplitis* sp. E. Wing venation. F. Female genital system.

3. Biological aspects of *Spodoptera frugiperda* :

Data presented in Table (2) refer to some biological aspects of fifteen FAW egg masses until the death of the adult insects. No eggs were arranged between 49 – 258 eggs with an average of 156.13 ± 16.57 , these eggs were started to emerge from the 3rd day after laying to the 4th day with an average of 3.47 ± 0.13 days, as the incubation period. Hatchability was ranged between 80-100% with an average of $89.18 \pm 1.42\%$. The average duration of larvae and pupae were 20.93 ± 0.68 and 12.60 ± 0.34 days, respectively. Adults were emerged after approximately, 33.53 days from hatching (Larval and pupal durations) as total immature stages, so that the life cycle is about 37.76 days (by combining the incomplete life cycle with the incubation period of the eggs). Pre-oviposition period reached 4.93 ± 0.23 days, bringing the average generation to 42.69 days. Oviposition and post-oviposition were recorded 11 ± 0.31 and 5.13 ± 0.24 , respectively.

In earlier studies, Igyuve1 *et al.* (2018), Sharanabasappa, *et al.* (2018), Dahi *et al.* (2020) and Gamil (2020) reported that the incubation period was 2, 3, 3.4 and 2.29 days respectively,

however, in this study the average incubation period was 3.47 ± 0.13 days. In partial or full agreement with the present results, Gamil (2020) recorded 97.33% of eggs were hatched to larvae still 9.56 days for pupation which in turn lasted 9.56 days. Also, Dahi *et al.* (2020) mentioned that, larval duration was 23.7 days, pupal duration was 9.4 days while, in this study, mean hatchability, larval and pupal duration were $89.18 \pm 1.42\%$ while, 20.93 ± 0.68 and 12.60 ± 0.34 days, respectively. The differences between studies and the present data could be attributed to the difference in the pest strains, the difference in food varieties used for larval feeding, or the different temperature and RH.% used.

The results of Tendeng *et al.* (2019) showed that the total duration of *S. frugiperda* cycle is between 22 and 28 days with an average of 25 days at 25 °C. Which gives on average 15 generations a year. Castro and Pitre (1988) have shown that *S. frugiperda* development cycle is between 28 to 38 days when the pest is fed with sorghum and 35 to 45 days when fed with corn. The FAW is a formidable invasive pest as it has a rapid development cycle that varies with temperature (Chapman *et al.*, 2000 and Barros *et al.*, 2010).

Table (2): Some biological aspects of *Spodoptera frugiperda* under laboratory condition at Sohag Governorate.

Egg mass	No. of eggs	Incubation period/Days	Hatchability %	No. of Larvae	Larval Period/Days	Pupal period/Days	No. of Pupae		No. of Emergence Adults		Emergency %	Sex		Male Longevity/Days	Female Longevity/Days	Pre-Oviposition/Days	Oviposition/Days	Post-Oviposition/Days
							Healthy	maltformation	Healthy	maltformation and dead pupae		Male	Female					
1	125	3.5	84.00	105	20	12	89	6	86	3	96.63	36	50	15.5	22.5	4	12	6
2	141	4	85.82	121	23	14.5	107	4	102	5	95.33	45	57	13.5	23	5	13	5
3	89	4	95.51	85	19.5	15	82	3	80	2	97.56	31	49	12.5	18.5	5	9	4
4	85	3	92.94	79	21.5	13.5	79	0	73	6	92.41	33	40	13.5	20	4	11	5
5	49	3	91.84	45	23.5	14	44	1	38	6	86.36	12	26	14.5	22	6	11	5
6	150	3	100	150	19	12.5	147	3	143	4	97.28	60	83	15.5	21	4	12	5
7	236	4	90.68	214	17	10.5	210	4	208	2	99.05	95	113	14.5	23	4	12	7
8	245	3	93.06	228	20	11	222	6	217	5	97.75	97	120	12.5	20	5	10	5
9	258	3	89.53	231	20	11.5	226	5	221	5	97.79	104	117	13.5	20	6	10	4
10	186	4.5	81.72	152	24	13	150	2	148	2	98.67	63	85	14.5	20.5	5	9	6
11	165	3.5	80.00	132	23	13	128	4	126	2	98.44	60	66	15.5	21.5	4	12	6
12	235	4	84.68	199	23.5	12.5	179	7	175	4	97.77	52	123	13	21.5	6	11	4
13	147	3	85.71	126	24.5	12	121	5	118	3	97.52	50	68	13.5	22	6	11	5
14	125	3	93.60	117	20	13	115	2	112	3	97.39	52	60	14.5	22	4	12	6
15	106	3.5	88.68	94	15.5	11	91	3	88	3	96.70	34	54	14	20	6	10	4
Mean ±SE	156.13 ±16.57	3.47 ±0.13	89.18 ±1.42	138.53 ±14.71	20.93 ±0.68	12.60 ±0.34	132.67 ±14.38	3.67 ±0.5	129 ±14.41	3.67 ±0.37	96.44 ±0.83	54.93 ±6.81	74.07 ±8.09	14.03 ±0.26	21.17 ±0.34	4.93 ±0.23	11 ±0.31	5.13 ±0.24

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Preliminary tests for new low cost and reusable bulking agents in the artificial larval diet of Mediterranean fruit fly *Ceratitis capitata* and peach fruit fly *Bactrocera zonata* (Diptera: Tephretidae)

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Abstract:

A preliminary tests have been executed to evaluate replacing of the traditional wheat bran that used as bulking agent in the artificial larval diet of Mediterranean and peach fruit flies with Sackcloth (can wash and reuse) to overcome storage, handling and waste manage problems of the diet residue also replaced with fine and rough saw dust (priceless material) to reduce costs. quality control tests (Pupal weight, Pupal size, Emergence, Deformity, Sex ratio, Flight and starvation) executed to compare the traditional wheat bran based with the suggested sawdust based and sackcloth based diets and revealed that results were very close for both fruit flies (Mediterranean and peach fruit flies). For medfly, there were no significant differences between standard diet and rough sawdust diet for all quality control tests, but they differ significantly from both sackcloth and fine sawdust diets. For peach fruit fly, results revealed that diets based on the alternatives were superior to the standard diet for majority of the biological parameter tested through quality control tests.

Introduction

Fruit flies considered the most serious insect pests worldwide attacking more than 300 plant species, including several species of high commercial value (Liquido *et al.*, 1991). Rearing these flies in the laboratory permits attempts at Sterile Insect Technique (SIT) programs, biological control in addition to basic researches in different areas. Sterile Insect Technique is one of the principal techniques for controlling of medfly (Hendrichs *et al.*, 2002). To be effective, the SIT requires large numbers of high-quality insects be released (Dyck *et al.*, 2005). The

production of insects must be timely and cost effective. Many economical alternatives for the solid bulking agents in the artificial larval diets have been used by many researchers such as, flaked agar (Maeda *et al.*, 1953), dehydrated carrot powder (Mitchell *et al.*, 1965), wheat shorts and middling (Nadel, 1970), sugarcane bagasse and wheat germ (Peleg and Rhode, 1970), fluid larval medium (Schroeder *et al.*, 1972) , dried carrot, wheat bran and rice bran (Awadalla and Faris, 1973), digestive bran and fresh carrot pulp (Barnes, 1976), pulverized paper (Zumreoglu *et al.*, 1979), sugarcane bagasse and sugar beet bagasse (Vargas

et al., 1983), (Bruzzone and Schwarz Gehrke, 1987) studied a recycling larval rearing medium where the diet can be reused after certain treatments to readjust its features without adding any ingredients except water and Nipagin), mill feed (Vargas, 1989) and toilet paper (Kakinohana and Yamagishi, 1991). A "liquid" larval diet has been developed that discard the bulking agent (Tanaka *et al.*, 1969). All alternatives used as bulking agents in fruit fly mass-rearing facilities, suffer from some problems caused by the solid bulking agents including residues management (Disposal and tray cleaning), storage space, high costs, labor, and sanitation.

In the present work, to overcome costs, the low cost sawdust were used as an alternative to the wheat bran bulking agent, also, to overcome storage, handling and waste challenges of traditional wheat bran based diet, and reduce costs also, the reusable sackcloth were used as an alternative to the wheat bran bulking agent that can be washed and reused many and many times.

Materials and methods

1. Flies strains:

Mediterranean and Peach fruit flies lab strains (Horticultural crops insects department laboratories - Plant Protection Research Institute) that reared upon an artificial larval diet composed of sugar (As a source for carbohydrate) 82 gm., dried sterile yeast (As a source for protein) 82 gm., wheat bran (As a bulking agent) 330 gm., sodium benzoate 3 gm., citric acid 3 gm. (Preservatives) and water 500 ml. The adult flies feed normally upon water, sugar and hydrolyzed protein (4:1).

2. Bulking agents:

2.1. Sackcloth:

Sackcloth characterized by its wide meshes and high ability to keep humidity, so it presents an excellent physical medium that larvae can move

easily through the fiber meshes in addition to keep humidity for longer period. Diet prepared by saturating multiple sheets of sackcloth (18 X 16 cm² weighting 150 gm.) with the liquid diet instead of the wheat bran that used as bulking agent.

2.2. Sawdust (Fine and rough):

Traditional sawdust (As the waste residue from wood processing) sifted to fine and rough dusts. Diets prepared by replacing the wheat bran content by 207 gm. fine sawdust (Fine sawdust diet) and replaced by 330 gm. rough sawdust (Rough saw dust diet) to get the same physical feature of the diet.

3. Quality control tests Experiments details:(IAEA, 2014):

3.1. Weight of pupae:

Record average weights 10 pupae two days before emergence (Five replicates).

3.2. Size pupae:

Calculated volumetrically by counting the number of pupae per one ml using graduated cylinder and record the average size per pupa (Five replicates).

3.3. Emergence percentage:

Calculate number of successfully emerged flies for each 100 pupae and estimate the emergence percentage (Five replicates).

3.4. Ratio of deformed flies:

Calculate number of flies that failed to emerge or emerge with deformation for each 100 pupae to estimate the deformity percentage (Five replicates).

3.5. Sex ratio:

For each group of 100 emerged adult flies, The numbers of males and females are counted and recorded (Five replicates).

3.6. Flight ability:

100 pupae for each treatment placed into one PVC cylinder coated internally by talcum powder and put inside a plastic transparent bag with metal frame inside to make it

swallowed, on emergence, calculate the flies succeeded to fly and escape the cylinder to be the flier individuals (Five replicates).

3.7. Survival under stress:

A number of 100 flies are caged separately (Transparent cups with top with a fiber mish top cover to supply aeration) without any feeding material or water and calculate how long the fly can persist alive without any nutrition.

Results and discussion

1. Mediterranean fruit fly:

1.1. Pupal weight:

Results in Table (1) regarding to the pupal weight revealed that control and rough sawdust pupae have the superior weight with mean of 11.0 mg /pupa and 10.86 mg /pupa but they differ significantly from sackcloth which came as second rank with mean weight of 10.44 mg/pupa and finally with the least weight, pupae reared upon fine sawdust larval diet with mean weight of 9.48 mg/pupa.

1.2. Pupal size:

Table (1) show that there was no significant difference between control pupae and rough sawdust pupae with mean pupal size of 0.021 ml /pupa and 0.020 ml/pupa respectively while sackcloth pupae and fine sawdust pupae have the same pupal size with means of 0.0188 ml.

1.3. Emergence percentage:

Data in Table (1) showed that there is no significant difference between control pupae, fine and rough sawdust pupae with mean emergence

percentages of 97.0, 96.4 and 97.6 % respectively and significantly different from sackcloth which has a lower emergence percentage mean of 94.4 %.

1.4. Deformity percentage:

Results of deformed flies (Table 1) came with no significant differences among the four treatments with mean percentage of 0.6, 0.4, 1.2 and 1.2 % for control, sackcloth, fine sawdust and rough sawdust diet, respectively.

1.5. Sex ratio:

Data obtained in (Table 1) revealed that male : female ratio came as ♂48 : ♀52 , ♂53 : ♀ 47, ♂52 : ♀48 and ♂51 : ♀ 49 for control, sackcloth, fine sawdust and rough sawdust diet respectively.

1.6. Flight ability:

Percent fliers differ significantly among the four groups, Rough sawdust came with greatest percent with mean of 84.6 % followed by fine sawdust (73.2 %) then sackcloth fliers (63.2 %) and finally, control as the least flier percentage with mean of 65.6 %.

1.7. Survival under Stress (Starvation):

Data in (Table 1) show that there were a significant differences among the four groups, rough sawdust has the longest life span (In hours) without food (Mean of 129.8 hours) followed by sackcloth (119.8 hours) then fine sawdust fliers (113.8 hours) and finally control, as the least life span with mean of 107.8 hours.

Table (1): Results of quality control tests for standard (Control), sackcloth, fine sawdust and rough sawdust diets for larval rearing of medfly.

Parameter	Control	Sackcloth	Fine sawdust	Rough sawdust
Pupal weight	11.0 ± 0.031 a1	10.44 ± 0.081 b1	9.48 ± 0.159 c1	10.86 ± 0.092 a1
Pupal size	0.021 ± 0.0003 a2	0.0188 ± 0.0008 b2	0.0188 ± 0.0002 b2	0.020 ± 0.0002 a2
Emergence	97.0 ± 0.316 a3	94.4 ± 0.245 b3	96.4 ± 0.510 a3	97.6 ± 0.245 a3
Deformity	0.6 ± 0.245 a4	0.4 ± 0.245 a4	1.2 ± 0.583 a4	1.2 ± 0.374 a4
Sex ratio	♂ 48 ♀ 52	♂ 53 ♀ 47	♂ 52 ♀ 48	♂ 51 ♀ 49
Flight	65.6 ± 0.4 c6	63.2 ± 0.20 d6	73.2 ± 0.374 b6	84.6 ± 0.40 a6
Starvation	107.8 ± 0.2 d7	119.8 ± 0.45 b7	113.8 ± 0.374 c7	129.8 ± 0.374 a7

2. Peach fruit fly:

2.1. Pupal weight:

Results in Table (2) revealed that pupal weights differ significantly among the four diets, Rough sawdust came as the highest weight with mean of 14.82 mg., followed by pupae resulted from sackcloth with a mean weight of 13.18 mg. then, fine sawdust pupae with mean weight of 12.96 mg. and finally, standard (Control), with the least pupal weight mean of 10.86 mg.,

2.2. Pupal size:

Table (2) showed that pupae resulted from rough sawdust has the highest size with a mean of 14.82 ml that differ significantly from the rest diets. Then, as the second order, fine sawdust pupae with a mean of 0.0243 ml. while, control and sackcloth diet with no significant difference between them and mean pupal size of 0.0239 and 0.0238 ml respectively.

2.3. Emergence percentage:

Results in Table (2) revealed that percent of emergences differ significantly among the four diets, sackcloth has the highest percentage with mean of 95 %, followed by fine sawdust based diet with mean percentage of 95 %, then rough sawdust diet which has a mean of 83.4 % and finally the control diet which has the least emergence percentage of 63.8 %.

2.4. Deformity percentage:

Results of deformed flies (Table 2) came with no significant differences

among the four treatments with mean percentage of 0.6 %, 1.2 %, 0.4 % and 1.2 % for control, Sackcloth, Fine sawdust and Rough sawdust diet respectively.

2.5. Sex ratio:

Data obtained in Table (1) revealed that male : female ratio came as ♂54.5: ♀ 45.5 , ♂ 55: ♀45, ♂ 54.5: ♀45.5 and ♂ 50: ♀ 50 for control, sackcloth, fine sawdust and rough sawdust diet, respectively.

2.6. Flight ability:

Diet based on sackcloth (Table 2) came with the superior flight ability with mean 80.4 % that differ significantly from the rest of the diets, followed by both of control and fine sawdust diets with no significant difference between them and means of 58.4 % and 60.4 % respectively, and rough sawdust based diet has the least flight percentage of 50.4 % mean.

2.7. Survival under Stress (Starvation):

Table (2) show that pupae resulted from rough sawdust has the highest ability to live under stress of food absence with a mean of 113.4 hours which differ significantly from the rest diets. Then, as the second order, both sackcloth and fine sawdust pupae with means of 113.6 and 104.8 hours respectively. while, control that differ significantly from the other diets, came as the least ability to survive under stress mean live span of 79.2 hours.

Table (2): Results of quality control tests for standard (Control), sackcloth, fine sawdust and rough sawdust diets for larval rearing of peach fruit fly.

	Standard (Control)	Sackcloth	Fine sawdust	Rough sawdust
Pupal weight	10.86 ± 0.051 d1	13.18 ± 0.02 b1	12.96 ± 0.051 c1	14.82 ± 0.073 a1
Pupal size	0.0239 ± 0.001 c2	0.0238 ± 0.001 c2	0.0243 ± 0.001 b2	0.0251 ± 0.001 a2
Emergence	63.8 ± 0.663 d3	95 ± 0.316 a3	90.4 ± 0.510 b3	83.4 ± 0.245 c3
Deformity	0.6 ± 0.245 a4	1.2 ± 0.20 a4	0.4 ± 0.245 a4	1.2 ± 0.20 a4
Sex ratio	♂54.5 ♀ 45.5	♂ 55 ♀45	♂ 54.5 ♀45.5	♂ 50 ♀ 50
Flight	58.4 ± 0.510 b5	80.4 ± 0.510 a5	60.4 ± 0.490 b5	50.4 ± 0.510 c5
Starvation	79.2 ± 0.374 c6	113.6 ± 0.245 b6	104.8 ± 0.374 b6	113.4 ± 0.245 a6

Results of quality control tests (Pupal weight, pupal size, emergence,

deformity, sex ratio, flight and starvation - for both of the

Mediterranean and peach fruit flies) revealed that traditional wheat bran based artificial larval diet was very close to the new diets based on Sackcloth, fine and rough Sawdust (Used as bulking agents) in spite of the significant differences that showed through the statistical analysis of the results but these differences will compensated through successive generations reared upon the same new diets as mentioned by Kamikado *et al.* (1987), Souza *et al.* (1988) and Economopoulos (1992) whose demonstrated that adaptation of the fruit flies to the laboratory artificial diet for colonization need several generations.

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Toxicity of clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*) plant extract and essential oil to the two-spotted spider mite *Tetranychus urticae* (Acari: Tetranychidae) and predatory mite *Phytoseilius persimilis* (Acarina: Tetranychidae and Phytoseiidae)

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Abstract:

In the present study plant extracted clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*) was extracted either by hexane or acetone. Also, commercial essential oils for the same plant and vertimec acaricid, were tested against *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae) eggs and adults and phytoseiid predatory mite *Phytoseiulus persimilis* Athias-Henriot (Acari: Phytoseiidae) by using spray technique. The clove hexane extracts high toxic against eggs and adult of *T. urticae* than acetone extract. The mortality percentage for *P. persimilis* using hexane extract, recorded that clove caused high toxicity against *P. persimilis* followed by the acetone extracts. The clove essential oil exhibited a high degree of efficiency against eggs and adult female of *T. urticae*. The LC₅₀ value of the biocide (Vertemic) against *T. urticae* adult were 0.0005 ml/L. The Identification was carried out using GC/MS analysis, as mentioned before in material and methods. Eleven compounds were identified by comparing with instrument database library. Thin Layer Chromatography, (TLC) was used to separate and isolate of various compound present in experimental clove hexane extracts of *S. aromaticum*, three compounds eugenol, caryophyllene and eugenyl acetate were identified by comparing with instrument data base library.

Introduction

Two-spotted spider mite *Tetranychus urticae* Koch (Acari: Tetranychidae), is widely distributed globally and a common pest of many plants. In this context, the use of some plant extracts can present a realistic alternative to synthetic acaricides because of their efficiency

against pests. Plant extracts can affect pest behavior, including repelling the pest or prohibiting feeding activity, and pest physiology, including molting and respiratory inhibition, growth and fecundity reduction, and cuticle disruption (Enan, 2001 and Gokce *et*

al., 2011). Plant extracts are also an environmentally interesting tool because of their biodegradability and minimal side effects on non-target organisms as well as on the environment (Attia *et al.*, 2012).

Many predaceous are now used as biological control agents in various agricultural ecosystems and are important as predators of phytophagous mite in IPM programs. *Amblyseius swirskii* Athias-Henriot (Acari: Phytoseiidae) is one of the most important generalist indigenous predators of tetranychid mite (Ebadollahi *et al.*, 2014). Many studies proved that *Syzygium aromaticum* has considered as important aromatic spices which contains a necessary essential and responsible compound of antimicrobial activity (Kumar *et al.*, 2012 and Pandey and Singh, 2011). The oil of *S. aromaticum* has inhibition activity for the germs, fungi and Insect repellent (Liu , 1987).

The aim of this study used the Clove hexane extract against of *T. urticae* followed by evaluation of their chemical constituents by Gas chromatography-Mass spectrometry (GC-MS).

Material and methods

1. Rearing of mites *Tetranychus urticae* :

Initial colony of the two spotted spider mite, *T. urticae* was taken from the Laboratory of Acarology in Plant Protection Research Institute Giza Egypt. Bean (*Phaseolus vulgaris*) seeds were planted in plastic pots (15 cm. diameter) at a rate of 6-7 seeds per pot and incubated under muslin cage to prevent any infestation. Pots containing lima bean seedlings (15cm long) were taken to the laboratory, then infested leaves of *T. urticae* were transferred to these plants and left to reproduce under laboratory condition (25± 2°C and 60%±5 RH.). The initial colony was

supplied with fresh bean plants from time to time.

2. Preparation of plant materials and extraction of crude bioactive compound:

Plant materials were obtained from Cairo University Faculty of Agriculture Ornamental Horticulture Department. Flower buds of clove (*S. aromaticum*.). This part was chosen to be extracted either by hexane or acetone.

3. Extraction procedure:

A weight of 250 g of each plant was ground in an electric grinder into fine powder then soaked in solvents, extracted using two different solvents; either hexane or acetone. The fine powder was weighted then soaked in 350 mL hexane or 500 mL acetone and left for 2hrs then filtered to dryness under vacuum using a rotary evaporator in water bath at 60°C the crude extract was then weighed and adjusted to 10 mL volume with acetone, and kept in a refrigerator until testing (Su and Horvat, 1981).

4. Bioassay tests:

Laboratory evaluation of the crude plant extracts and a biocide were conducted against *T. urticae* using either; hexane or acetone. Four concentrations of each extract were used.

5. Commercial essential oils:

Commercial essential oils were obtained from El Hawag factory. Essential oil was kept in a refrigerator until using. Series of aqueous concentrations of essential oil were prepared with Triton X-100 as a emulsifier agent at a rate of 0.1%.

6. Biocide (Vertimec):

Abamactin (Vertimec) 1.8% E.C. commercial formulation recommended as acaricid for controlling the two spotted spider mite *T. urticae*. Vertimec is produced by Sanganta Agro Egypt.

7. Treatment of adult stages:

Leaf discs of *Acalypha* (2 cm diameter) were placed separately upside –down on moist cotton Pads in Petri-dishes. Ten adults of *T. urticae* were placed on each disc then treated with one of the different treatments, sprayed by glass atomizer with different concentrations of the hexane extract which dissolved in acetone. The hexane extract concentrations of clove extract were used at 0.05, 0.0375, 0.018 and 0.009 mg/ml, and with acetone extract concentrations of Clove extract was used at 0.1, 0.05, 0.025 and 0.0125 mg/ml, Control discs were sprayed with acetone. While Clove oil was used as 2%, 1%, 0.05% and 0.025%; Control treatment was operated by water with Triton x-100 at rate of 0.1%. The concentrations with Biocide vertimec used as 0.0125, 0.0625, 0.003125 and 0.001 ml / L. Control was sprayed by water. Four replicates were made for each concentration. All treated discs were kept at 25±.2 °C and 55%±5 RH. Mortality was estimated for adult females after 24h of spraying. The percentage of mortality was determined and corrected by Abbott's formula (1925) as follows:

$$\text{Percentage of mortality} = \frac{\% \text{ tested mortality} - \% \text{ control mortality}}{100 - \% \text{ control mortality}} \times 100$$

LC₅₀, LC₉₀ and slope values were calculated according to Finney (1971) and using (Ldp line) software by (Bakr, 2000).

8. Ovicidal action (Treatment of eggs):

To investigate the ovicidal activity of the clove extract, ten adult females were placed on *Acalypha* leaf discs (2 cm diameter) on wet cotton wool in a petri dish and allowed to put eggs. The petri dish was incubated for 24hrs at 25±.2 °C and 55%±5 RH. Then adult's females were removed from the leaf discs. There after eggs were counted and sprayed by a glass atomizer

with a serial concentrations of clove plant hexane extracts 0.05, 0.025, 0.0125 and 0.00625 mg/ml; while with acetone extract the concentrations of clove extract were used at 0.1, 0.05, and 0.025. Control discs were sprayed with acetone. Essential oil as 5%, 2.5%, 1.25% and 0.05% for clove. Control treatment was operated by Triton x-100 at rate of 0.1%. The concentrations with biocide (Vertimec) used as 0.0125, 0.0625, 0.003125 and 0.001 ml / L. Control sprayed with water. Four replicates were used for each concentration. Treated eggs were incubated at 25±0.2 °C and 55%± 5 RH. for three days till hatching. The numbers of hatching and non-hatching eggs were recorded. Unhatchability was corrected by Abbott's formula (1925). LC₅₀, LC₉₀ and slope values were computed according to Finney (1971) and using Ldp line software according to Bakr (2000).

9. Natural enemies and culture:

The phytoseiid predatory mite *Phytoseiulus persimilis* Athias-Henriot (Acari: Phytoseiidae) was used in this study. *P. persimilis* was obtained from Lab. of Acarology cultures of Plant Protection Department, National Research Centre, Dokki- Giza. Predatory mites were transferred to clean *Acalypha*, leaves put on wetted cotton in a large tray. Individuals of *T. urticae* were added as prey then kept in an incubator at 28 ± 1 °C and 70% R.H. *Acalypha* leaf discs (2 cm diameter) were placed separately upside – down on moist cotton wool in a Petri dish. Ten adults of *T. urticae* were placed on each disc with five adults of *P. persimilis* was sprayed with clove hexane extract 0.05, 0.025, 0.0125 and 0.00625 mg/ml. Acetone extract were used as 0.05, 0.025, 0.0125 and 0.00625 mg/ml for Clove. Control discs were sprayed with acetone. Biocide Vertimec concentrations used as 0.0125, 0.0625, 0.003125 and 0.001 ml / L. Control

sprayed with water. Essential oil concentration was used as 2%, 1%, 0.05% and 0.25% for Clove; Then kept in an incubator at 28±1°C. Control treatment was operated by Triton x-100 at rate of 0.1%. Four replicates were used for each concentration. Mortality percentages were calculated after 24h of treatment and corrected by Abbott's formula, (1925). LC₅₀, LC₉₀ and slope values were computed according to Finney (1971) and using Ldp line software according to Bakr (2000).

10. Isolation and identification :

Chromatographic techniques thin - Layer Chromatography (TLC) was used to separate the constituents of one plant hexane extract. The method used is as described by Su and Horvat (1981). TLC is a useful technique to determine bioactive compound from plant extract.

11. Identification of hexane plant extracts (GC/ MS chromatogram):

The chemical constituent's crude of hexane clove extract which gave high toxicity to *T. urticae* was identified by GC/MS (gas chromatography- mass spectrometry). For complete and rapid characterization of the separated compounds we have used Gas chromatography Mass spectrometric (GC/MS) method. Total GC running time was 30 min. The relative percentage amount of each component was calculated by comparing its average peak area to the total areas.

12. Purification of bioactive compound(s) using Silica Gel Chromatography:

The crude hexane flower buds extract of clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*) (5g) was subjected to silica gel column chromatography (After adding 5ml of acetone to crude), to separate the extract into its component fractions.

Chromatography was performed on 20X20 cm were covered with a thin layer 0.5mm thick of silica gel Gf 254.

The tested material was spotted 2.5 cm away from the edges and with 2.0 cm between each spot. Solvent system was used in attempt to fractionate investigated plant extract. Toluene: acetic acid (9:1v/v) was used in all plant extract. The plates were removed and allowed to dry under room condition (20°C±2). Subsequently the sample components are identified by comparison of their retardation factor (R_f) Values with those of the separated standards.

Each plate was exposed to ultra violet light at wavelength UV 254 nm. The movement of each separating spot of the extract was expressed by its retardation factor (R_f). Values were calculated for each spot using the following formula:-

$$R_f = \frac{\text{distance traveled by solvte from the point of application to the center of spot}}{\text{distance traveled by the solvent front}}$$

This treatment may show some of spots the spots were recorded on the plates directly. The R_f value of each fraction was calculated. After developing of the plats, the silica gel layer at each fraction was abraded and collected on filter paper. The fraction was eluted with acetone. The acetone was evaporated and kept in freezing till used.

Leaf disc of *Acalypha* (2 cm diameter) were placed separately upside -down on moist cotton Pads in Petri-dishes. Fifteen adults of *T. urticae* were placed on each disc and sprayed with four bands then mortality percentages were calculated after 24h of treatment and corrected by Abbott's formula, (1925).

Results and discussion

1. Toxicity of clove *Syzygium aromaticum* plant extract and essential oil to the two-spotted spider mite *Tetranychus urticae* and predatory mite *Phytoseilius persimilis*:

Results in Table (1) show that clove (*S. aromaticum*) hexane extract exhibited a high degree of efficiency against adult of *T. urticae* recording overall mean of mortality ranged from 72.5- 98.3%, while 0.009 mg/mL concentration caused 82.5% mortality after 3 day but 0.0375mg/mL concentration caused 90% mortality after 24 hours of application increased to 100% after 3 days from application where 0.05 mg/mL caused 95-100% after 1, 2 and 3 days of application. For acetone extract Results reveals that it is less toxic than hexane extract where 0.0125 mg/mL concentrate Caused 67.5% after 3 days the mortality increased by increasing the conc. from 67.5-100% with 0.0125-0.1 mg/mL

conc. After 3 days. But Clove essential oil recording overall mean of mortality range of 15- 93% with 0.25-2% concentration, while 0.25 % concentration caused 10% mortality after 1 day, but 2% concentration caused 87.5% mortality after 1 day of application increased to 100% after 3days from application.

Slope values of clove, LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ shown in Table (2). The LC₅₀ values were 0.0068, 0.01 and 0.83 for Clove with hexane, acetone extract and essential oil respectively. The LC₉₀ values were 0.03, 0.07 and 2.1 with hexane, acetone extract and essential oil respectively, while slope value 1.76, 1.62 and 3.0 respectively.

Table (1): Toxicity of Clove *Syzygium aromaticum* plant extract (Hexane and acetone) and essential oil on *Teranychus urticae* adult stage.

Clove extract with	Con.	% mortality after			Overall mean
		1 day	2 day	3 day	
Hexane	0.009 mg/ml	60	75	82.5	72.5
	0.018 mg/ml	77.5	90	97	88.1
	0.0375 mg/ml	90	96	100	95.0
	0.05 mg/ml	95	100	100	98.3
Acetone	0.0125 mg/ml	52.5	60	67.5	60.0
	0.025 mg/ml	75	80	85	80.0
	0.05 mg/ml	87.5	90	97	91.5
	0.1 mg/ml	92.5	95	100	95.0
Essential oil	0.25%	10	15	20	15.0
	0.5%	35	45	52.5	44.0
	1%	62.5	75	80	72.5
	2%	87.5	92.5	100	93.0

Table (2): LC₅₀, LC₉₀ and Slope values of Clove *Syzygium aromaticum* plant extract (Hexane and acetone) and Essential oil on *Teranychus urticae* adult stage.

Tested materials	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀	Slope
Clove hexane extract mg/ml	0.0068	0.03	1.76
Clove acetone extract mg/ml	0.01	0.07	1.62
Clove essential oil %	0.83	2.1	3.0

Table (3) showed that clove hexane extract caused a high degree of efficiency against *T. urticae* eggs recording overall mean of hatchability ranged from 59-33% with 0.00625-0.05 mg/mL conc. while 0.00625 mg/mL caused 66% hatchability after 3 days, and 0.025 mg/mL conc. Caused 33and 50% hatchability after 1 and 3 days. By increasing the conc. Increased the hatchability as used 0.05 mg/mL

conc. caused 37% hatchability after 3 days. While clove acetone extract recording overall mean of hatchability ranged from 72-25% with 0.0125- 0.1 mg/mL, while 0.0125 mg/mL caused 67 and 78% hatchability after 1and 3 days, but 0.1 mg/mL concentration caused 20 and 30% hatchability after 1and 3 days of application. Clove essential oil recording overall mean of hatchability ranged from 78 and 23.6% with 0.625

and 5% concentrations, while 0.625% concentration caused 77% hatchability after 1 day, but 5% concentration caused 22% hatchability after 1 day of application increased to 25% after 3 days. Slope values, LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ shown in Table (4). The LC₅₀ values

were 0.01, 0.02 and 2.1 for *S. aromaticum* with hexane, acetone extract and essential oil. The LC₉₀ values were 0.4, 0.2 and 10 with hexane, acetone extract and essential oil, while slope value 0.79, 1.57 and 1.92 respectively

Table (3): Toxicity of clove *Syzygium aromaticum* plant extract (Hexane and acetone) and essential oil on *Teranychus urticae* eggs.

Extract	Con.	% hatchability after			Overall mean
		1 day	2 day	3 day	
Hexane	0.00625 mg/ml	53.1	59	66	59
	0.0125 mg/ml	46	52	57	51
	0.025 mg/ml	33	44	50	42
	0.05 mg/ml	29	34	37	33
Acetone	0.0125 mg/ml	67	72	78	72
	0.025 mg/ml	55	67	74	65
	0.05 mg/ml	30.5	36.9	41	36
	0.1 mg/ml	20	25	30	25
Essential oil	0.625%	77	79	80	78.0
	1.25%	64	69	70	67.6
	2.5%	40	43	45	42.6
	5%	22	23.9	25	23.6

Table (4): LC₅₀, LC₉₀ and slope values of clove *Syzygium aromaticum* plant extract (Hexane and acetone) and Essential oil on *Teranychus urticae* eggs.

Tested materials	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀	Slope
Clove hexane extract mg/ml	0.01	0.4	0.79
Clove acetone extract mg/ml	0.02	0.2	1.57
Clove essential oil %	2.1	10	1.92

Table (5) showed that *S. aromaticum* hexane exhibited a high degree of efficiency against *P. persimilis* recording overall mean of mortality ranged from 38-86% when used 0.00625- 0.05 mg/mL concentrations, while 0.00625mg/mL caused 35% mortality after 1 day but 0.05 mg/mL caused 85% mortality after 1 day of application, while with acetone extract results recorded that *S. aromaticum* caused high toxicity against *P. persimilis*, the overall mean for *S. aromaticum* caused 30-81% mortality with 0.006- 0.05mg/mL concentration, while after 1 day the

mortality was 30, 50, 60 and 80% for 0.006, 0.0125, 0.025 and 0.05mg/mL. Results with essential oil recorded that the overall mean for *S. aromaticum* caused 26-81% mortality with 0.25- 2 % concentration, while after 1-day mortality were 25, 40, 60 and 80% with 0.25, 0.05, 1 and 2% concentrations. Slope values, LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ shown in Table (6). The LC₅₀ values were 0.009, 0.017 and 1.01 for *S. aromaticum* with hexane, acetone extract and essential oil. The LC₉₀ values were 0.05, 0.11 and 3.4 with hexane, acetone extract and essential oil, while slope value 1.65, 1.57 and 2.3 respectively.

Table (5): Toxicity of clove *Syzygium aromaticum* plant extract (Hexane and acetone) and essential oil on *phytoseiulus persimilis* predator.

Extract	Con.	% mortality after			Overall mean
		1 day	2 day	3 day	
Hexane	0.00625 mg/ml	35	40	40	38
	0.0125 mg/ml	65	70	70	68
	0.025 mg/ml	80	80	85	81
	0.05mg/ml	85	85	90	86
Acetone	0.00625 mg/ml	30	30	30	30
	0.0125 mg/ml	50	55	60	55
	0.025 mg/ml	60	65	65	63
	0.05mg/ml	80	80	85	81
Essential oil	0.25%	25	25	30	26
	0.5%	40	45	45	43
	1%	60	65	65	63
	2%	80	80	85	81

Table (6): LC₅₀, LC₉₀ and Slope values of clove *Syzygium aromaticum* plant extract (Hexane and Acetone) and Essential oil on on *phytoseiulus persimilis* predator.

Tested materials	LC ₅₀	LC ₉₀	Slope
Clove hexane extract mg/ml	0.009	0.05	1.65
Clove acetone extract mg/ml	0.017	0.11	1.57
Clove essential oil %	1.01	3.4	2.3

Data in Table (7) showed effect of the biocide (Vertemic) against *T. urticae* recorded 65- 92.5% mortality with 0.001-0.0125mL/l after 1 day, while after 3 day caused 87.5-100%. The overall mean recorded 76, 84, 94 and 96.8% with 0.001, 0.003, 0.006 and 0.0125 mL/l concentration. The hatchability recorded 80, 62.5, 38.7 and 27% with the same concentration after 1 day, while after 3day the hatchability increased to 87, 69, 44 and 31%, while

toxicity against *P. persimilis* recoded 45, 55, 75 and 95% after 1 day and increased to 50, 65, 85 and 100% after 3 days. Slope, LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ shown in Table (8). The LC₅₀ values of the biocide were 0.0005, 0.0029 and 0.0025 mL/L for *T.urticae* adult, *T. urticae* egg and *P. persimilis*, while LC₉₀were 0.009, 0.09 and 0.012 mL/Lfor *T.urticae* adult, *T. urticae* egg and *P. persimilis*.

Table (7): Toxicity of acaricide, vertimec on *Tetranychus urticae* adult, eggs and *Phytoseiulus persimilis* predator.

Trials	Con. ml/L	% mortality			mean
		1 day	2 day	3 day	
<i>Tetranychus urticae</i> adult	0.001	65	77.5	87.5	76.0
	0.003	77.5	85	90	84.0
	0.006	87.5	95	100	94.0
	0.0125	92.5	98	100	96.8
<i>Tetranychus urticae</i> eggs	0.001	80	84	87	83.6
	0.003	62.5	66	69	65.8
	0.006	38.7	42	44	41.5
	0.0125	27	29	31	29.0
<i>Phytoseiulus persimilis</i> adult	0.001	45	45	50	46.6
	0.003	55	60	65	60.0
	0.006	75	80	85	80.0
	0.0125	95	95	100	96.0

Table (8): LC₅₀, LC₉₀ and Slope values of vertimec on *Tetranychus urticae* adult, eggs and *Phytoseiulus persimilis* predator.

Tested materials	LC ₅₀ ml/L	LC ₉₀ ml/L	slope
<i>Tetranychus urticae</i> adult	0.0005	0.009	0.97
<i>Tetranychus urticae</i> egg hatchability	0.0029	0.09	0.85
<i>Phytoseiulus persimilis</i>	0.0025	0.012	1.88

2. Identification of flower buds of clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*) hexane extract by using GC/MS technique:

The chemical constituents of flower buds hexane extract. Was identified out using GC/MS analysis. Table (9) showed that the chemical constituents of flower buds of clove (*S. aromaticum*) hexane extract. Chemical names, percent area, R_t molecular weight M.W., structure and formula of the detected compound flower buds of clove Figure (1) Showed the chromatogram of the flower buds of clove (*S. aromaticum*) hexane extract. Eleven compounds were identified by comparing using instrument database library. Table (9) showed that the GC chromatogram show 10 peaks corresponding to 11 compounds. The compound number one was methylthio [2,3,7,8,12,13,17,18 octaethylporphyrinato] indium its area was 1.71% with R_t 13.67min. The compound number two was penitrem its area was 2.43% with R_t16.06 min. Compound number 3 was

(3,6diterbutyl1azulenyl) (3,5diterbutyl4hydroxyphenyl) methane its area was 1.43% with R_t 18.35min. Compound number 4 was 2,5-Cyclohexadien-1-one,3-bromo-2 Methoxy-6-(methoxy methyl -4,4-dimethyl) its area was 7.05% with R_t 24.57 min. The compound number 5 was Caryophyllene its area was 11.13% with R_t 26.03min. The compound number 6 was 1carboxaldehyde5,5dimethyl 12methylene 3cyclohexene its area was 2.52% with R_t 26.96min. The compound number 7 was Eugenol its area was 1.65% with R_t28.58min. The compound number 8 was 2fluoropyridine its area was 5.16% with R_t 32.14min. The compound number 9 was Methyl 13 decarboxy methyl phaeophorpidea its area was 3.28% with R_t 37.13 min. The compound number 10 was Carotene its area was 6.81% with R_t 40.52 min. The compound number 11 was Lycoxanthin its area was 1.37% with R_t 43.82 min.

Figure (1): Gas chromatogram GC/MS of the of flower buds of Clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*.) hexane extract.

Table (9): Chemical constituents of flower buds of clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*) hexane extract.

No.	Compound	Area%	R _t	structure	M.W.	M.formula
1	Methylthio[2,3,7,8,12,13,17,18]octaethylporphyrinato Indium	1.71	13.67		694	C ₃₇ H ₄₇ InN ₄ S
2	PENITREM	2.43	16.06		633	C ₃₇ H ₄₄ ClNO ₆
3	(3,6 ditertbutyl 1 azulenylyl) (3,5ditertbutyl 4 hydroxyphenyl) Methane	1.43	18.35		712	C ₃₈ H ₄₀ N ₄ O ₁₀
4	2,5-Cyclohexadien-1-one,3-bromo-2 ethoxy-6-(methoxy methyl -4,4-dimethyl)	7.05	24.57		274	C ₁₁ H ₁₅ BrO ₃
5	Caryophyllene	11.13	26.03		204	C ₁₅ H ₂₄
6	1carboxaldehyde5,5dimethyl 12methylene 3cyclohexene	2.52	26.96		150	C ₁₀ H ₁₄ O
7	Eugenol	1.65	28.58		164	C ₁₀ H ₁₂ O ₂
8	2fluoropyridine	5.16	32.14		97	C ₅ H ₄ FN
9	Methyl 13 decarboxy methyl Phaeophorpeida	3.28	37.13		548	C ₃₄ H ₃₆ N ₄ O ₃
10	Carotene	6.81	40.52		536	C ₄₀ H ₅₆
11	Lycoxanthin	1.37	43.82		552	C ₄₀ H ₅₆ O

3. Isolation and Identification of the toxic components in plant extract:

Thin layer chromatogram indicated the different fraction obtained from hexane plant extracts. After the development with the solvent system, the band and region which have the same R_f values, were scraped from the

glass plate and extracted with acetone. Such extracts were then used for bioactivity and identification studies. Four bands were evident in the TLC plate visualized under visible light (Figure 2). Compound with R_f values of 0.22, 0.32, 0.67 and 0.83 were visualized in TLC chromatograms.

Figure (2): Separation of clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*) compounds the toluene : acetic acid (9:1 v/v).

Tests were conducted to determine the bioactivity of different fractions against *T. urticae* compound having acaricide properties. The fraction with R_f 0.83 in hexane extract of *S. aromaticum* had a considerable acaricide activity.

4. Identification of best potent fraction component:

The best potent of flower buds of Clove (*S. aromaticum*.) was identified by GC/MS analysis. Analysis through GC-MS used to identify the volatile and semivolatile compounds present in the clove extract. To identify the chemical constituents of the fraction band number four which proved to be the highest potent fraction against mite adult. The identification was carried out using GC/MS analysis.

Table (10): Chemical constituents of spot of flower buds of clove (*Syzygium aromaticum*) hexane extract.

R_t (min.)	Area%	Compound	M.W.	chemical formula
23.79	14.96	Eugenol	164	$C_{10}H_{12}O_2$
27.87	2.16	Caryophyllene	204	$C_{15}H_{24}$
29.46	1.77	Eugenyl acetate	206.10	$C_{12}H_{14}O_3$

Table (10) represents the chemical composition of the fraction band from the bud of clove (*S. aromaticum*). As can be seen from this table, three compounds representing about clove, were characterized. Table (10) presents the compound names, percent area, R_t , molecular weight (M.W.) and chemical formula of the detected compound of fraction band four. Figure (3) showed the chromatogram of this fraction.

Three compounds eugenol, caryophyllene and eugenyl acetate were identified. The major components are shown in Table (10). The area of three compounds were 14.96, 2.16 and 1.77% with R_t 23.79, 27.87 and 29.46 min respectively.

Figure (3): Gas chromatogram of the hexane extract isolated from clove buds fraction four.

Clove (*S. aromaticum*) plant hexane, acetone extract and essential oil were the most effective compound on the susceptible strain of *Tetranychus urticae* where LC_{50} was 0.0068, 0.01 and 0.83. Hanifah *et al.* (2012) indicated that generally, the plant extracts showed various degrees of repellency against the larval mites and the repellency increased with increasing concentrations of the extracts. At the lowest concentration (0.01%), onion extract gave the highest repellency (30%) followed by clove and cinnamon (23%). Syahputra and Endarto (2013). Found all the aqueous extracts assayed could not cause the death of the predator *H. axyridis*. Aqueous seed extracts of *J. curcas* and *M. elengi* at a concentration of 5% could not cause phytotoxicity symptoms on the citrus leaves of *Citrus sinensis*. The high acaricidal activity of the clove (*S. aromaticum*) essential oil was perhaps attributable to the high level of eugenol. Clove oil represented the most repellent property. This kind of activity may be due to the high content of eugenol compound. This agrees with Araújo *et al.* (2012) who reported that eugenol component had a strong repellency property on *T. urticae*.

Our results obtained that LC_{50} values of the biocide were 0.0005, 0.0029 and 0.0025 mL/L for *T. urticae* adult, *T. urticae* egg and *P. persimilis*,

while LC_{90} were 0.009, 0.09 and 0.012 mL/L for *T. urticae* adult, *T. urticae* egg and *P. persimilis*. Trumble and Morese (1993) reported that the best economic returns were generated by abamectin against *T. urticae* in combination with *P. persimilis*. This indicates that the chemical application for two-spotted spider mite can be successfully integrated with biological control. Abou El-Ela (2014) studied that vertimec gave 76.34% and 77.31% in two seasons 2007 and 2008 against *T. urticae*. Also, Sayed *et al.* (2006) found that the vertimec is more effective than actellic and biofly against *T. urticae*.

GC/MS was performed to identify the semivolatile and volatile compounds present in the flower buds of clove (*S. aromaticum*) hexane extracts. Eleven compounds were identified by comparing with instrument data base library. The results of this study could lead to the compound Eugenol was 1.65% with R_t 28.58. The same result was obtained by Lee and Shibamoto (2001) aroma extract from dried clove buds (*S. aromaticum*) was obtained by using steam-distillation under mild conditions (55°C and 95 mm Hg). The major aroma constituents of clove buds were eugenol (24.371 mg/g) and eugenyl acetate (2.354 mg/g). The antioxidant activity of clove bud extract and its major aroma components were eugenol

and eugenyl acetate studied by Alma *et al.* (2007). Its chemical composition was analyzed by GC/MS. The result showed that the essential oil mainly contained about 87.00% eugenol, 8.01% eugenol acetate and 3.56% β -caryophyllene. Rana *et al.* (2011) used column chromatography to separate the eugenol rich fraction from clove oil. Thin Layer Chromatography (TLC) was used to separate and isolate of various compound present in experimental Clove hexane extracts of *S. aromaticum*, subsequent tests on their acaricidal activities were assessed. (TLC) was initially performed as a qualitative method to document the extract constituents, Valle Jr *et al.* (2016) This method has been widely used to separate secondary metabolites like polyphenols, flavonoids, saponins, alkaloids and steroids, including amino acids, proteins, peptides, hormones and pesticides, Bhawani *et al.* (2012).

In this study, chemical composition of clove (*S. aromaticum*) bud were analysis through GC/MS has identified the volatile and semivolatile compounds present in this extract. The compound eugenol, carophyllene and Eugenol acetate. The same result was obtained by Razafimamonjison *et al.* (2014) the oils were analyzed by GC and ten constituents were identified from the whole. The major constituent in bud, leaf and stem oils was eugenol, with increasing percentages from bud (72.08 - 82.36%) to leaf (75.04 - 83.58%) and stem (87.52 - 96.65%).

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Virulence of entomopathogenic fungi *Beauveria bassiana* against the seed bug *Graptostethus servus* (Hemiptera : Lygaeidae) and its immune response

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Abstract:

The pathogenicity of native isolate of entomopathogenic fungi *Beauveria bassiana* against seed bugs *Graptostethus servus* (Fabricius) (Hemiptera: Lygaeidae) was investigation for the first time in laboratory bioassay. The results obtained that *G. servus* was highly susceptible to *B. bassiana*. The calculated LC₅₀ was 2.9x10⁶ spores/ml and the LT₅₀ values was 4.16 days. The mechanisms of *G. servus* immune defenses against *B. bassiana* was studied. Result revealed that both of total protein, total carbohydrates, Esterase and alkaline phosphatase activities were significant decreased after 48-72hrs. post treatment than control. There was significant decreased in Glutathione S-transferase (GST) after 24 -72 hrs. posttreatment. Both of phenoloxidases and peroxidase activity were significantly increased after 24hrs. and recorded non-significant decreased after 48 and 72hrs. posttreatment than control.

Introduction

The seed bugs *Graptostethus servus* (Fabricius) (Hemiptera: Lygaeidae) belong to order Hemiptera and suborder, Heteroptera which included family Lygaeidae are recognized as seed bugs (Magsi *et al.*, 2018). These seed bugs is distributed in Japan, except for Hokkaido island (Yasunaga *et al.*, 1993) and in Africa, Europe, Asia, and the south Pacific Island (Hussain *et al.*, 2014; Kment *et al.*, 2005 and Pericart, 2001). Chin *et al.* (2018) reported that, during the dry season there are various swarms of native sucking bugs *G. servus* appear in Darwin, Palmerston, Katherine and rural areas in China. In Egypt, Ibrahim and Elshewy (2020) recorded a swarms of both seed bugs *G. servus* and *Spilostethus pandurus* (Scopoli) (Hemiptera : Lygaeidae) during June

2017, 2018 and 2019 and early winter seasons 2020 and in Giza Governorate, Egypt, on oil crops such as *Sesamum indicum* (Pedaliaceae), sorghum crops (*Sorghum bicolor*) and milkweed plants (*Convolvulus arvensis* L.).

The seed bugs *G. servus* as sap - sucking bugs are known as a pest of not only Convolvulaceous crops such as *Ipomoea tuberosa* (L.) but also other families of crops such as *Gossypium* spp., sorghum bicolor (L.) Moench, in various regions (Khaing *et al.*, 2002; Kment *et al.*, 2005 and Yeates, 2001). Suzaki and Okada (2016) suggested that *G. servus* have a serious damage to sunflower, *Helianthus annuus* L. because *G. servus* can grow on sunflower seed in the rearing laboratory (Gamberale-Stille and Tullberg, 1999 and 2001). Chin *et al.* (2018) recorded that huge swarm of *G. servus*

aggregated on fruit trees, ornamentals, vegetables and native trees. The bugs are attracted to moisture from irrigation, and rain. They also make large groups to aggregate and mate. They occasionally cause indirect damage on fruit or vegetable crops, as pin-prick spots by feeding on moisture found on fruit, shoots or flowers, and cause physical damage by breaking off stems and making scratch marks on leaves, flowers or fruit by moving on the plants in a large groups. There is not much information on using biological control for controlling seed bugs *G. servus* in literature. These findings may be considered the first investigation of the susceptibility of seed bugs *G. servus* adult to infection by entomopathogenic fungi *Beauveria bassiana* as promising biocontrol agent.

The aim of this study to evaluate the virulence of native isolate of entomopathogenic fungi *B. bassiana* against seed bugs *G. servus* and recording the physiological reactions to infection.

Material and methods

1. Rearing of seed bugs

Graptostethus servus :

Individuals of the seed bugs adults and nymphs was collected from faculty of Agriculture Experimental Station, Cairo University, and Giza, Egypt. Seed bugs were transported to the laboratory and placed in plastic cages supplemented with pods of milkweed plant for feeding, which renewed every two day intervals. Sheets papers were added to prevent cannibalism and a saturated piece of cotton will hanged in all cages. All cages were covered with muslin for ventilation. Adult were injecting there egg out the muslin caver, Eggs were collected over the muslin caver and incubated in petri dish supplemented with a pieces of moistened cotton wool until hatching. All hatches were

transferred to new cages for rearing as pervious methods.

2. Entomopathogenic fungi culture:

The entomopathogenic fungi *B. bassiana* (Hypocreales : cordycipitaceae) isolate used in these experiments was isolated from Soil which collected from East Owainat at New valley Governorate , Egypt, during 2018 . Using larvae of the greater wax moth, *Galleria mellonella* L. for trapping of entomopathogenic fungi methods According to Zimmermann (1986). *B. bassiana* was cultured on autoclaved Sabourad dextrose yeast agar media (SDAY), at 25 ± 1 °C for 14 days (Nada 2015).

3. Bioassays procedure:

Spores were collected from the culture media by rinsing with sterilized aqueous solution of 0.02% Tween 80, and then filtered through cheese cloth to reduce mycelium clumping. By using Haemocytometer (Neubauer improved HBG, Germany 0.100 mm X 0.0025mm²) concentrations of spores were counted. For bioassay, the suspensions were prepared at concentrations of 10^6 , 10^7 , 5×10^7 and 10^8 spores/ml (Nada, 2006).

Adult of *G. servus* were treated with dipping methods technique for 10 seconds in each concentration and the residual suspension was then filtered out with filter paper. In control adults were treated with sterile aqueous solution of 0.02% tween 80. A total of 25 insect were used for each concentration and control. The treated insect and control were maintained individual in transparent plastic boxes (d=6cm, h=3cm) with holes in the cover for ventilation, and supplement with saturated filter paper. All plastic boxes were supplemented with pods of milkweed plant for feeding which renewed every two days. Then all boxes were incubated in $25 \pm$ °C. Mortality was monitored daily for 7 days after treatment.

4. Biochemical studies:

Adults were treated with 1×10^7 spores/ml of *B. bassiana* as previous methods. Sterile aqueous solution of 0.02% tween 80 was used as control. After 24, 48 and 72 hrs. the surviving larvae were used for the biochemical analysis using methods of Gholamzadeh- Chitgar *et al.* (2015).

4.1. Sample preparation:

Adults of *G. servus* were collected after 24, 48 and 72 post treatment (n=20 per treatment for each enzymes). Samples were homogenized separately in 250 μ l of 0.2 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.0) containing 0.05 % triton X- 100 using a plastic pestle. Then, the homogenate was centrifuged at 12000g for 10 min at 4°C. The supernatant was used as an enzyme solution for assessing the total protein, total carbohydrates, Alpha esterases, Alkaline phosphatase, glutathione S-transferase (GST), phenoloxidases and peroxidases.

4.2. Biochemical analysis:

4.2.1. Determination of total proteins:

Protein reagent was prepared by dissolving 100mg of Coomassie Brilliant blue G-250 in 50ml 95% ethanol. To this solution 100ml 85% (W/V) phosphoric acid were added. The resulting solution was diluted to a final volume of 1 liter. Sample solution (50 μ l) or for the preparation of standard curve 50 μ l of serial concentrations containing 10 to 100 μ g bovine serum albumin was pipetted into test tubes. The volume in the test tube was adjusted to 1 ml with phosphate buffer (0.1M, pH 6.6). Five millimetres of protein reagent were added to test tube and the contents were mixed either by inversion or vortexing. The absorbance at 595 nm was measured after 2 min and before 1 hrs. against blank prepared from 1 ml of phosphate buffer and 5 ml protein reagent (Bradford, 1976).

4.2.2. Determination of total carbohydrates:

Total carbohydrates were estimated in acid extracts of a samples by the phenol-sulphuric acid reaction of DuBois *et al.* (1956). Total carbohydrates were extracted and prepared for assay according to Crompton and Birt (1987). Sample (1 gm) was homogenized in 0.3N HClO₄(5 ml) at 0°C for 1 min. The homogenate was kept in ice for further 10 min. Insoluble matter was removed by centrifugation for 3 min.at 2000 r.p.m and washed twice in ice cold HClO₄ (5ml) by redispersion and centrifugation. The three-supernatant combined into acid extract. Hundred microliters of the acid extract were added into a colorimetric tube to 0.5 ml of phenol (20 present w/v). Then 5 ml of concentrated sulphuric acid were added rapidly with shaking. The tubes were allowed to stand 10 min, and then they were shaken and placed for 10-20 min in water bath at 25 to 30 °c before readings. Blanks were prepared by substituting distilled water for the sugar solution. The absorbance of characteristic yellow orange color is measured at 490 nm against blank. Total carbohydrate is expressed as: μ g glucose / gm fresh weight.

4.2.3. Determination alpha esterases:

Alpha esterases (α -esterases) was determined according to Van Asperen (1962) using α -naphthyl acetate as substrates, respectively. The reaction mixture consisted of 5ml substrate solution (3×10^{-4} M α -or β -naphthylacetate, 1% acetone and 0.1M phosphate buffer, pH7) and 20 μ l of larval homogenate. The mixture was incubated for exactly 15 min at 27°C, then 1 ml of diazoblue color reagent (Prepared by mixing 2 parts of 1% diazoblue B and 5 parts of 5% sodium lauryl sulphate) was added. The developed color was read at 600 or 555 nm for α - naphthol produced from

hydrolysis of the substrate. α - naphthol standard curves was prepared by dissolving 20 mg α - naphthol in 100ml phosphate buffer, pH7 (stock solution). Ten millilitres of stock solution were diluted up to 100ml by the buffer. Aliquots of 0.1, 0.2, 0.4, 0.8 and 1.6 ml of diluted solution (equal to 2, 4, 8, 16 and 32 μ g naphthol) were pippered into test tubes and completed to 5 ml by phosphate buffer. One millilitre of diazoblue reagent was added and the developed color was measured as mentioned before.

4.2.4. Determination of alkaline phosphatase:

Acid and alkaline phosphatases were determined according to the method described by Powell and Smith (1954). In this method, the phenol released by enzymatic hydrolysis of disodium phenylphosphate reacts with 4-aminoantipyrine, and by the addition of potassium ferricyanide, the characteristic brown color is produced. The reaction mixture consisted of 1 ml carbonate buffer (pH 10.4) for alkaline phosphatase or 1 ml citric buffer (pH 4.9) for acid phosphatase, 1 ml of 0.01 M disodium phenylphosphate (Substrate), and 0.1 ml sample. Mix and incubate for exactly 30 min at 37 C0. At the end of incubation period .0.8 ml of 0.5 N NaOH was added to stop the reaction. Then add 1.2 ml of 0.5 N NaHCO₃, followed by the addition of 1 ml of 4-aminoantipyrine solution (1%) and 1 ml potassium ferricyanide (0.5 %) . The produced color was measured immediately at 510 nm. The enzyme activity is expressed by unit (U), where 1 unit will hydrolyze 1.0 u mole of p-nitrophenyl phosphate per minute at 37 Co, and pH 10.4 and 4.8 for alkaline and acid phosphatases, respectively.

4.2.5. Determination of Glutathione S- transferase (GST):

Glutathione S-transferase (GST) catalyzes the conjugation of reduced glutathione (GSH) with 1-

chloro 2,4-dinitrobenzene (CDNB) via the -SH group of glutathione. The conjugate , S-(2,4-dinitro-phenyl)-L-glutathione could be detected as described by the method of Habig *et al.*(1974).The reaction mixture consisted of 1 ml of the potassium salt of phosphate buffer (pH6.5),100 μ l of GSH and 200 μ l of larval homogenate. The reaction started by the addition of 25 μ l of the substrate CDNB solution. The concentration of both GSH and CDNB was adjusted to be 5mM and 1mM, respectively. Enzyme and reagents were incubated at 30°C for 5 min. The increment in absorbance at 340 nm was recorded against blank containing everything except the enzyme to determine the nanomole substrate conjugated/min/larva using a molar extinction coefficient of 9.6/m M/cm.

4.2.6. Determination of phenoloxidases:

Phenoloxidase activity was determined according to a modification of Ishaaya (1971), in a reaction mixture consisting of 0.5 ml phosphate buffer (0.1 M, pH 7), 200 μ l enzyme solution and 200 μ l catechol solution (2%). Prior to the initiation of the reaction, the substrate and other ingredients of the reaction mixture were separately incubated at the optimum temperature of the reaction (25 °c). Enzyme reaction was initiated by adding catechol solution. Then after exactly 1 min, the optical density was determined. Zero adjustment was against sample blank. The phenol oxidase activity was determined as O.D. units $\times 10^3$ at an absorbancy of 405 nm.

4.2.7. Determination of peroxidases:

Peroxidase activity was determined according the procedure given by Hammerschmidt *et al.* (1982). To a spectrophotometer sample cuvette, 1.5 ml of pyrogallol (0.05 M) and 100 UL enzyme extract were added. The readings were adjusted to zero at 420

NM. To initiate the reaction, 100 UL of hydrogen peroxide (1%) was added to the sample cuvette. The enzyme activity was expressed as change in absorbance /min/ g sample.

5. Statistical analysis:

The corrected mortality percentages were statistically computed according to Finney (1971), to determine the LC₅₀ and LT₅₀ values, using "Ldp" software by Bakr (2000). All data of Biochemical analysis was expressed as the mean \pm standard error. Statistical analysis Obtained data was analyzed as one way ANOVA, using Proc ANOVA in SAS (Anonymous. 2003), and means were compared by Tukey's HSD ($P= 0.05$ level) in the same program.

Results and discussion

1. Virulence of *Beauveria bassiana* for *Graptostethus servus*:

The obtained results showed that *G. servus* adults are highly susceptible to infection with entomopathogenic fungi *B. bassiana* and demonstrated the first report documenting the pathogenicity of *B. bassiana* to *G. servus*. The correspondents LC₂₅, LC₅₀ and LC₉₀ values were 3×10^5 , 2.9×10^6 and 2.08×10^8 spores/ml, respectively ($\chi^2= 0.407$, slope= 0.689 ± 0.18 , $P < 0.816$) (Figure 1). Mortality was observed from 4 days after treatment. Mean lethal time LT₂₅, LT₅₀ and LT₉₀ values were 3.12, 4.16 and 7.2 days, respectively ($\chi^2= 0.79$, slope= 5.38 ± 1.008 , $P < 0.851$) (Figure 2). After

death insect were incubated in high humidity at $25 \pm ^\circ\text{C}$ and observed the emerged of the growth mycelium and spores from insect body to prove the pathogenicity (Figure 3).

B. bassiana was used by Steinhaus (1975) to monitor (Hemiptera : Lygaeidae). Reports of naturally occurring epizootics induced by *B. bassiana* in populations of *B. leucopterus* support the idea of using Entomopathogenic fungi against chinch bugs.

Also, Krueger *et al.* (1991) reported that Adults of chinch bug, *B. leucopterus* are highly susceptible to *B. bassiana* under laboratory conditions. Entomopathogenic fungi isolates of *B. bassiana* and *Metarhizium anisopliae* were tested for pathogenicity and virulence in *B. leucopterus* eggs in a laboratory analysis. According to Samuels *et al.* (2002) all entomopathogenic fungi treated isolates were virulent to chinch bug eggs.

Adult chinch bugs can be killed by *B. bassiana* at high conidial concentrations, according to Boyle and Cutler (2012), who also found that early instars were more vulnerable to infection than nymphs and adults. Sahayaraj and Borgio (2010) announced for the first time that cotton seed bugs *Oxycarenus hyalinipennis* (Costa) (Hemiptera: Lygaeidae) are susceptible to *M. anisopliae* in an in vitro bioassay, with LC₅₀ values of 1.93×10^5 spores/ml.

Figure (1): Percentage mortality regression line of *Graptostethus servus* treated with *Beauveria bassiana*.

Figure (2): Time-mortality regression line of *Beauveria bassiana* at concentration 10^8 spores/ml against *Graptostethus servus* .

Figure (3): (A): Healthy *Graptostethus servus* and (B): Sporulation process of *Beauveria bassiana* in *Graptostethus servus* cadavers after death .

2. Biochemical analysis:

2.1. Determination of total proteins:

Proteins are integral components of living cells and are made up of a variety of substances such as enzymes, hormones, and antibodies, all of which are important for an organism's proper functioning (Fagan *et al.*, 2002). Data in Table (1) showed that total protein activity of adult was decreased significant during 48 and 72 hrs. after fungal infection than control (16.97, 12.3, 28.7 and 23.3 mg/g. b. wt., respectively). Our results match what was found by Nada (2015) who reported that Total protein activity in green bug *Nezara viridula* (L.)

(Hemiptera: *Pentatomidae*) treated with *Metarhizium anisopliae* and *B. bassiana* were significantly decreased. Vidhya *et al.* (2016) reported a significant reduction of total protein on arm worm *Spodoptera litura* treated with three entomopathogenic fungi *Verticillium lecanii* , *B. bassiana* and *M. anisopliae* at fourth day after infection compared with control. El-Sayed and Yousef (2021) explained that when *Spodoptera littoralis* (Boisd) (Lepidoptera : Noctuidae) treated with *Purpureocillium lilacinum* (*Paecilomyces lilacinus*) this prompted a sharp decreased in total protein in cadavers after death .

Table (1): Effect of *Beauveria bassiana* on total protein in *Graptostethus servus*.

Hours after treatment	Total protein (mg/g.b.wt)		F	P	M.S.D
	Control± SE	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> ± SE			
24	22.3±0.4 ^a	21.1±1.06 ^a	0.94	0.39	3.15
48	28.7±0.73 ^a	16.97±0.5 ^b	170.64	0.0002	2.49
72	23.3±0.93 ^a	12.3±1.17 ^b	54.37	0.0018	4.142

^aMean, within a row, bearing different subscripts are significantly different.

2.2. Determination of total carbohydrates:

Carbohydrates are the primary source of energy for the formation and growth of living cells, and they also act as fundamental basic elements for cells and components of a variety of metabolic intermediates. The current investigation proved that in the first 24h, the total carbohydrates activity was slight decreased than control (84.3 and 86.2, respectively). After that, there is a sharp significant decreased after 48, 72 h than control (77.7, 59.8, 91.7 and 84.97 mg/g.b.wt, respectively) (Table 2). Our results match what found by Elbanna *et al.* (2012) who

reported that total carbohydrates contains in 5th instars of *Schistocerca gregaria* Forskål (Orthoptera: Acrididae), treated with *M. anisopliae* was actual decreased after 24h than control. Nada (2015) mentioned that there are significant decreased of total carbohydrates activity when adults of *N. viridula* treated with both entomopathogenic fungi *M. anisopliae* and *B. bassiana*. In contrast El-Sayed and Yousef (2021) reported that there is a significant increase in total carbohydrates in haemolymph of *S. littoralis* treated with *P. lilacinum* than control.

Table (2): Effect of *Beauveria bassiana* on total carbohydrates in *Graptostethus servus*.

Hours after treatment	Total carbohydrates (mg/g.b.wt)		F	P	M.S.D
	Control ±SE	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> ±SE			
24	86.2±0.92 ^a	84.3±1.7 ^a	0.99	0.38	5.314
48	91.7±1.4 ^a	77.7±0.9 ^b	69.45	0.001	4.64
72	84.97±1.9 ^a	59.8±1.08 ^b	132.56	0.0003	6.069

^aMean, within a row, bearing different subscripts are significantly different.

2.3. Determination of Alkaline phosphatase:

Under the name of dephosphorylation, alkaline phosphatase is a hydrolytic enzyme that removes phosphate groups from a variety of molecules, including nucleotides, proteins, and alkaloids, in alkaline conditions (Zibae *et al.*, 2009 and 2011). Data represented in Table (3) revealed that after 24hrs. the activity of Alkaline phosphatase was

slight decreased than control (83.3 and 92.67 mU/g.b.wt, respectively). There are a significant decreased after 48 and 72hrs. compared with control (59.3, 66, 136 and 170.67 mU/g.b.wt, respectively). These results are in agreement with Gad and Nada (2020) which recorded a highly significant reduction of Alkaline phosphatase activity on *N. viridula* treated with *B. bassiana* than control during 24hrs. post treatment.

Table(3): Effect of *Beauveria bassiana* on alkaline phosphatase activity in *Graptostethus servus*.

Hours after treatment	Alkaline phosphatase (mU/g.b.wt)		F	P	M.S.D
	Control ±SE	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> ±SE			
24	92.67±3.7 ^a	83.3±4.37 ^a	2.65	0.179	15.92
48	136±7.2 ^a	59.3±6.67 ^b	61.80	0.0014	27.077
72	170.67±6.67 ^a	66±4.62 ^b	169.99	0.0002	22.289

^a Mean, within a row, bearing different subscripts are significantly different.

2.4. Determination of alpha esterases activity (ESTs):

Esterases (ESTs) play an important role in the insect's life by catabolizing the esters of higher fatty acids, which stimulates activity in the flight muscles and allows insects to fly by mobilizing lipids, including those found in the fat body, and degrading inert metabolic esters including various xenobiotic (Roslavtseva *et al.*,1993). Table (4) observed that after 48-72hrs. post treatment there are a significant

decreased on EST activity than control (396.33, 250, 579.67 and 451.67 Ug α-naphthol/min/g.b.wt, respectively). According to Cao *et al.* (2016), the observed decrease in ESTs activities by *M. anisoplae* IM1330189 isolate can overcome EST immunity by inhibiting EST transcription on the hemocytes of *Locusta migratoria*, while IBC200614 isolate has no apparent effect on ESTs activities, implying that the insects are resistant to IBC200614 due to the stability of ESTs activities.

Table (4): Effect of *Beauveria bassiana* on alpha esterases activity in *Graptostethus servus*.

Hours after treatment	Alpha esterases (Ug α-naphthol/min/g.b.wt)		F	P	M.S.D
	Control ±SE	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> ±SE			
24	373±6.7 ^a	392.6±3.7 ^a	6.66	0.0613	21.165
48	579.67±11.84 ^a	396.33±7.9 ^b	166.21	0.0002	39.48
72	451.67±14.66 ^a	250±5.8 ^b	163.92	0.0002	43.73

^aMean, within a row, bearing different subscripts are significantly different.

2.5. Determination of Glutathione-S-transferase activity:

Glutathione-S-transferase (GST) is involved in metabolite removal as well as tissue protection from free radical damage, and increase in insecticide-resistant insects, according to Papadopoulos *et al.* (2000). Data represented in Table (5) revealed that GST was significant decreased stalely during 24, 48 and 72hrs. after treatment than control . In insects of different orders, increased expression of genes for detoxifying

enzymes developing resistance to various xenobiotics was observed. During the progression of infection, the activity of esterases and GST in the degradation of toxic molecules may play a significant role in protecting insects from pathogens (Dubovskiy *et al.*, 2012). Gillespie *et al.* (2000) explained that reduced Esterase and GST activity during the acute phase of mycosis may be linked to successful entomopathogenic fungi inhibition of the host defense systems.

Table(5): Effect of *Beauveria bassiana* on Glutathione-S- transferase activity in *Graptostethus servus*.

Hours after treatment	GST (mmol sub.conjugated/min/g.b.wt)		F	P	M.S.D
	Control \pm SE	<i>B. bassiana</i> \pm SE			
	24	44 \pm 2.03 ^a			
48	41 \pm 1.15 ^a	26.9 \pm 0.59 ^b	133.32	0.0003	3.575
72	43 \pm 1.17 ^a	30 \pm 1.097 ^b	73.36	0.0010	4.4519

^aMean, within a row, bearing different subscripts are significantly different.

2.6. Determination of phenoloxidases activity:

Phenoloxidases are play a key role in nodule formation and encapsulation. The hydroxylation of mono and diphenols to quinone intermediates is catalysed by Phenoloxidases, which are located in the host cuticle. Phenoloxidases products are involved in a participant in a variety of critical processes such as defense, wound healing, cuticle sclerotisation, and foreign particle identification and melanization. The results in Table (6) showed that there was a significant increase of phenoloxidases activity in the first 24h after treatment than control (5.03 and 3.83 O.D./min/g.b.wt , respectively), whoever it decreased after 48 and 27

h than control (3.6, 3.4, 4.07 and 3.73 O.D./min/g.b.wt, respectively). Our result matches what was found by Gad and Nada (2020), who reported that, phenoloxidases activity in the haemolymph of *N. viridula* was significant increased during 24hrs. post infection than control, then decreased . Serebrov *et al.* (2006) reported that inhibiting detoxification enzymes dramatically increases the death rate of insects from fungal infection, suggesting that detoxification enzymes are involved in the creation of insect resistance to Entomopathogenic fungi and opening new avenues for the production of highly effective combined biological products based on Entomopathogenic fungi and detoxification enzyme inhibitors.

Table (6): Effect of *Beauveria bassiana* on phenoloxidases activity in *Graptostethus servus*.

Hours after treatment	Phenoloxidases (O.D./min/g.b.wt)		F	P	M.S.D
	Control \pm SE	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> \pm SE			
	24	3.83 \pm 0.12 ^b			
48	4.07 \pm 0.15 ^a	3.6 \pm 0.12 ^a	6.32	0.066	0.515
72	3.73 \pm 0.13 ^a	3.4 \pm 0.06 ^a	5.26	0.0835	0.403

^aMean, within a row, bearing different subscripts are significantly different.

2.7. Determination of peroxidases activity:

Peroxidases as antioxidant enzymes play a pivotal role of defense against pathogens and insecticides (Jia *et al.*, 2016). Table (7) obtained that there is a significant increase in peroxidases activity during 24hrs post treatment than control (8.6 and 6.2 O.D./min/g.b.wt, respectively), while

the activity of peroxidases was stable and not significant decreased after 48 and 72 hrs post treatment . Result revealed that seed bugs *G. servus* were highly susceptibility to infection by entomopathogenic fungi *B. bassiana* and represent as the first record documenting the pathogenicity of *B. bassiana* on *G. servus* . When living spores come into contact with an

insect's cuticle, they germinate, and then penetrate the insect's cuticle and start to expand within its host's body, reducing the insect's ability to feed and movement (Elbanna *et al.*, 2012). Trudeau *et al.* (2001) confirmed that invasion of the insect body and haemolymph occurs conidia bind to the cuticle of a suitable host and germinate, triggering a series of recognition and enzyme activation reactions in both the host and the fungal parasite. The activation of the phenoloxidases and other cascade enzymes occurs as a result of protective responses to fungi infection. The activities of glutathione S transferases, nonspecific esterases, and alkaline phosphatases were altered by fungi, which is thought to be a

nonspecific body reaction to integument harm or fungal toxin. Fungi also evolved strategies to defeat the immune systems of insects over time. The first mechanism involves modifying the morphology and formation of their cell surface in order to evade the host immune system (Cao *et al.*, 2016). Entomopathogenic fungi, for example, have cells with various morphologies, such as no cell wall or cells that are almost in the host hemolymph; these types help in the dispersion and clustering of entomopathogenic fungi in the hemocoel and may increase the surface area to consume further nutrients (Cao *et al.*, 2016).

Table (7): Effect of *Beauveria bassiana* on peroxidases activity in *Graptostethus servus*..

Hours after treatment	Peroxidases (O.D./min/g.b.wt)		F	P	M.S.D
	Control ±SE	<i>Beauveria bassiana</i> ±SE			
24	6.2±0.25 ^b	8.6±0.31 ^a	36.77	0.0037	1.098
48	4.9 ±0.06 ^a	4.6±0.12 ^a	5.40	0.0808	0.358
72	6.83±0.09 ^a	3.87±0.15 ^a	304.65	< 0.0001	0.472

^aMean, within a row, bearing different subscripts are significantly different.

In this study there is inhibition of detoxification enzymes sharply increases insect death rate from fungal infection which indirectly confirms the involvement of detoxification enzymes in the formation of insect resistance to entomopathogenic fungi. *B. bassiana* was found to be severely deficient in total protein after 48 hours in the current research. According to Gillespie *et al.* (2000) , a decrease in the total protein content of adult *S. gregaria* haemolymph during infection with *M. anisopliae* was reported. During parasitism, the parasite may secrete proteolytic enzymes into the insect's haemocoel, which hydrolyze the host protein, causing the host haemolymph to lose soluble protein. Furthermore, after 24 hours of care, the total carbohydrates content of the infected

decreased. This result agrees with Elbanna *et al.* (2012) who reported a decreased in total protein and total carbohydrates contents after 24h of infected *S. gregaria* with *M. anisopliae*.

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Diversity and abundance of spiders and other arthropods in quinoa plants treated with some chemical salts and their effects on downy mildew and yield

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Abstract:

Experiment was conducted at Fayoum Governorate, Egypt during two successive winter season, 2018-2019 and 2019-2020 on quinoa plants to study effects of some chemical salts on spiders, other arthropods, downy mildew and its effects on quinoa yield. Treatments used were copperal max, calcivin, potassium silicate, max. growth and mix. Spiders and other arthropods were sampled using pitfall traps. A total of 424 spiders, representing 9 families. Spider recorded the highest number with max. growth and lowest number with potassium silicate in first season. While in second season, the highest number recorded with mix. and the lowest recoded also with potassium silicate. The most abundant families were Lycosidae and Linyphiidae spiders represented 46.64, 30.49 % and 44.78, 26.87%, during the two seasons, respectively. The most abundant species were *Wadicosa fidelis* (O.Pickard-Cambridge) and *Sengletus extricates* (O.Pickard-Cambridge) in two seasons. According to Shannon-Wiener and Simpson, it was found that plot treated with max. growth treatment (90 individuals) and mix. (99 individuals) included the highest number of dominant species the highest numbers of individuals decreased to 39 individuals in control. Sørensen quotient of similarity between treatment and control concluded that 66.67 and 47.62% in copperal max, 66.67 and 50% in calcivin, 81.82 and 50% in potassium silicate, 81.82 and 60% in max. growth, and 84.21 and 35% in mix in two seasons respectively. The total number of pests and predators was higher in first season (3128 individuals) than in the second season (2676 individuals). The results obtained that the disease is caused by *Peronospor avariabilis*. Mix treatment was the lowest disease incidence and disease severity and the highest yield Kg/fed during two seasons. Statistical analysis proved that no significant differences were observed in first season and high significant differences between mix. growth treatment and other treatments.

Introduction

Quinoa is a very recent crop was introduced to Egypt. Quinoa is considered an important crop due to it can grow and gives considerable yield in new reclaimed salty soil with salty water (1800 ppm) where wheat or many other crops cannot grow (Abd El-Moity and Ali, 2016). Edible quinoa seeds are grown in some cases and places. Green leaves are eaten as vegetables (Gee *et al.*, 2006). Recent research has focused on greater reliance on conservation and attraction of endemic natural enemies to reduce chemical inputs for management of pests (James *et al.*, 2003 and James and Price, 2004). Also, it is important to find alternative measures to control plant diseases which do not harm the environment and at the same time increase yield and improves product quality (Batish *et al.*, 2007 and Camprubí *et al.*, 2007). Nutrients are important for growth and development of plants and microorganisms, and they are important factors to reduce pests (Agrios, 2005). As predators, spiders are important biological control agents in agro-ecosystems, playing a vital role in structuring arthropod communities and thus having a significant role in the balance of nature (Nyffeler *et al.*, 1994 and Marc *et al.*, 1999). Agricultural practices affect the patterns of soil fauna abundance, richness, and diversity. Also, the presences of groups such as Araneae are related to ecological equilibrium, quality, and sustainability of the agricultural systems. (Silva *et al.*, 2018). Downy mildew is one of the limiting diseases for quinoa plants (Choi *et al.*, 2010). Most studies (Abd El-Moity and Ali, 2016) agree with our finding which indicated that the downy mildew pathogen is identification as *Peronospora farinosa* f. sp. *chenopodii*. While, certain

studies indicated that the quinoa downy mildew pathogen is *Peronospora variabilis* (Choi *et al.*, 2010).

From this point of view, this is an attempt to study biodiversity of spiders and other arthropods in quinoa plants treated with some chemical salts and their effect on downy mildew and yield.

Materials and methods

1. Experimental design:

Field experiments were conducted for two winter successive seasons, 2018-2019 and 2019-2020 at Ibshway; Fayoum Governorate. An area of about 200 m² was divided into 18 equal plots that received 5 treatments and control of 3 replicates each. A spilt plots design with three replicates was used. Seeds of quinoa (*Chenopodium quinoa*, Caryophyllales, Amaranthaceae) were Variety Egypt 1 planted. Plots were distributed in a complete randomized block design. All plots received the normally recommended agricultural practices except the absence of any pesticides. Soil fertilizer at the rate of 45:25: 60 N: P: K. in addition to sprays with treatments after month after farming plants and repeated each 15 day. The field experiment was under conditions of natural downy mildew infection.

2. Treatments used:

All treatments used were produced under Central Lab. of Organic (CLOA), Agric. Research center, Giza, Egypt. They were used at 1 liter/200-liter water . The treatments rates of spray as follow :

Trade name: Copperal max. **Active ingredient:** CuSO₄ 8% **Rate/200 Liter water:** 1Liter

Trade name: Calcivin **Active ingredient:** Cacl₂ 15 % **Rate/200 Liter water:** 1Liter

Trade name: Potassium silicate **Active ingredient:** K_2SiO_3 15% **Rate/200 Liter water:** 1Liter

Trade name: Max. growth **Active ingredient:** Fe 5% + Zn 5% + Mn 5% **Rate/200 Liter water:** 1Liter

Trade name: Mix. (All treatments) **Active ingredient:** $CuSO_4$ + K_2SiO_3 + max. growth + $CaCl_2$ as alone) **Rate/200 Liter water:** 1Liter **Control:** Water

3. Spider abundance and diversity:

To determine the effect of fertilizer treatments on spider abundance and diversity in the agroecosystem, spiders were sampled using pitfall traps method as described by Southwood (1978) and Slingsby and Cook (1986). Three pitfall traps were placed in each fertilizer treatment every week and three in control plot. Arthropod specimens were placed in 70% alcohol and some droplets of glycerin. Spiders were counted and sorted in the laboratory and identified to species level as much as possible.

3.1. Frequency and abundance values:

The frequency values of the most abundant species were classified into three classes according to the system adopted by Weis Fogh (1948); "Constant species" more than 50% of the samples, "accessory species" 25-50 % of the samples and "accidental species" less than 25%. On the other hand, the classification of dominance values were done according to Weigmann (1973) system in which the species were divided into five groups based on the values of dominance in the sample; Eudominant species (>30% individuals), dominant species (>10-30% individuals), subdominant (>5-10% individuals), recedent species (1-5% individuals) and subrecedent species (<1% individuals).

3.2. Species diversity:

The community structure of soil spiders was described using the species

richness, Shannon-Wiener and Simpson indices "S". The Shannon-Wiener Index "H'" is one of the most common ecological indexes, it may provide an indication of community stability under the balance of nature and it may also respond differently of geographical, developmental, or physical factors. Higher number of H' indicates higher number of species, higher relative abundance and species evenness, so, it means increase in diversity. While Simpson Index "S" is more responsive to changes in the importance of most dominant species, it is a measure of dominance (i.e. The probability of two randomly selected individuals will be of the same species) (Nestle *et al.*, 1993). A community dominated by one or two species is less diverse than one in which several different species have a similar abundance. The two indices were calculated as described by Ludwig and Reynolds (1988):

$$H' = -\sum (ni / n) \ln (ni / n) \text{ and } S = \sum (ni/n)^2$$

Where ni is the number of individuals belonging to the i th of "S" taxa in the sample and "n" is the total number of individuals in the sample

3.3. Sørensen quotient of similarity:

To allow a comparison of the two samplings between microhabitats of the two cultivation systems, Sørensen's quotient of similarity (Sørensen, 1948) was used to determine the similarities of spider species composition among the communities, it is: $QS = 2 C / A + B$

Where: A and B are the number of species in samples A and B, respectively, and C is the number of species shared by the two samples; QS is the quotient of similarity and ranges from 0 to 1.

4. Identification of the pathogen that cause downy mildew:

The samples of infected leaves of quinoa were examined by the staff of the Mycology and Plant Disease Survey Research, Plant Pathology Research Institute. ARC

Disease assessment:

$$\text{Disease incidence} = \frac{\text{Number of disease plants}}{\text{Total number of inspected plants}} \times 100\%$$

(Mhada *et al.*, 2015)

$$\text{Disease severity} = \frac{\sum (\text{Rating no.} \times \text{no. of plants in each rating})}{\text{Total of plants} \times \text{highest rating}} \times 100\%$$

(Abd El-Moity and Ali, 2016)

Disease severity was assessed according to 0 – 5 scale (Mhada *et al.*, 2015).

5. Statistical analysis:

All collected data for various treatments were statistically analyzed according to the technique of analysis of variance for split-plot arranged in randomized complete block design using the InfoStat computer software package (Version, 2012). The differences among treatment means were compared by LSD as a post hoc test at $\leq 5\%$ level of significance (Gomez and Gomez, 1984).

Results and discussion

1. Spider assemblages:

During the 2018- 2019 and 2019-2020 seasons, 424 spiders, representing 9 families, were captured with pitfall traps Tables (1 and 2). Lycosidae and Linyphiidae spiders represented 46.64, 44.78% and 30.49-26.87%, during the two seasons, respectively, of the total number of trapped spiders. These two spider families were the primary ground-dwelling predators in quinoa field. These results agree with (Abd El-Karim *et al.*, 2016; Tahir and Butt, 2009 and Rizk *et al.*, 2012) who found that most of individuals collected belong to family Lycosidae. Also, as shown in Tables (1 and 2), during first season a total number of 223 spiders were collected during this

experiment; belonged to 9 families, 18 genera and 18 species. Adults comprised 69.51%, while Juvenile were 30.49%. The sex ratio was 1 ♀: 5.46 ♂. In second season, a total number of 201 spiders were collected; belonged to 9 families, 19 genera and 19 species. Adults comprised 64.68%, while Juvenile were 28.86%. The sex ratio was 1 ♀: 4.42 ♂. The 9 families found in the present study represent 21.95% of the 41 families recorded in Egypt (El-Hennawy, 2017).

These results as Ebaid and Mansour (2006) who found that spiders recorded 799 and 937 individuals for the two seasons, respectively in plot treated with mixture of some chelated microelements (Powder of; zinc 12%, mn 12%, fe 12%, cu 12% and 6% liquid boron).

2. Under each treatment during two seasons:

Different treatments influenced spider abundance. The effect of tested treatments on spiders inhabiting land of management is presented in Tables (1 and 2).

2.1. Copperal max (Cuso4):

A total of 31 and 29 individuals were collected and identified to 6 families, 11, 12 genera and 11, 12 species in two seasons respectively. Adults comprised 96.78, 96.55%, while Juvenile averaged 3.23, 3.45% respectively. The sex ratio was 1♀:3.29♂, 1♀:2.5♂ respectively. The most abundant species *Sengletus extricates* (O.Pickard-Cambridge) , Linyphiidae (7 and 6 individuals) in two seasons respectively.

2.2. Calcivin (Cacl2):

A total of 53 and 32 individuals were collected and identified to 6 and 7 families, 11 genera and 11 species. Adults comprised 47.17, 81.25%, while Juvenile were 52.83 and 18.75% respectively. The sex ratio was 1♀:5.25♂

and 1♀:2.25♂ in two seasons respectively. The species that recorded the highest numbers were *Wadicosa fidelis* (O.Pickard-Cambridge) (27 indiv.) and *Pardosa* sp. (7 individuals), Lycosidae in first season while *Pardosa* sp. (6 individuals), Lycosidae and *S. extricates*, Linyphidae (6 individuals) in second season.

2.3. Potassium silicate (K2sio3):

A total of 26+ (1 egg sac) and 25 individuals were collected and identified to 7 and 6 families, 12 and 10 genera and 12 and 10 species respectively. Adults comprised 84.62 and 96% while, Juvenile averaged 15.38 and 4%. The sex ratio was 1♀:10♂ and 1♀:7♂ in two seasons respectively. *S. extricates*, Linyphidae (8, 7 individuals) recorded the highest numbers in two seasons respectively.

2.4. Max. growth (Fe + zn + mn):

A total of 59 and 31 (+1 egg sac) individuals were collected and identified to 6 and 5 families, 12 and 11 genera and 12 and 11 species respectively. Adults comprised 47.46 and 90.32%, while Juvenile averaged 52.54 and 9.68%. The sex ratio was 1♀:8.33♂ and 1♀:4.6♂ in two seasons respectively. The most abundant species were *W. fidelis* (27 individuals), Lycosidae and *S. extricates*, Linyphidae (7 individuals) in first season while in second season, *W. fidelis* (5 individuals) and *Pardosa* sp. (5 individuals), Lycosidae and *Enoplognatha gemina* Bosmans and Van Keer, Theridiidae (5 individuals).

2.5. Mix. (Cu+ca+k2+ fe but cacl2 as alone):

A total of 30 (+1 egg sac) and 69 individuals were collected and identified to 5 and 6 families, 9 and 8 genera and 9 and 8 species respectively. Adults comprised 90 and 33.33%, while Juvenile averaged 10 and 66.67%. The sex ratio was 1♀:5.5♂ and 1♀:2.9♂ in two

seasons respectively. The most abundant species, were *Pardosa* sp. (5 individuals), Lycosidae and *S. extricates*, Linyphidae (6 individuals) in first season while in second season, *W. fidelis* (50 indiv.) and *Pardosa* sp. (5 individuals), Lycosidae and *S. extricates*, Linyphidae (9 individuals).

3. Control:

A total of 24 and 15 individuals were collected and identified to 5 and 6 families, 10 and 9 genera and 10 and 9 species respectively. Adults averaged 95.83 and 93.33%, while Juvenile comprised 4.17 and 6.67%. The sex ratio was 1♀:6.67♂ and 1♀:1.33♂ in two seasons respectively. the most abundant species collected *S. extricates* (6 individuals) and *Mermessus denticulatus* (Banks), Linyphidae in first season while in second season, *S. extricates* (3 indiv.), Linyphidae and *Zelotes* sp. (4 individuals), Gnaphosidae. Ebaid and Mansour (2006) found that the mean total numbers of predators in the plots, which received mixture of some chelated microelements (Powder of; zinc 12 %, mn 12 %, fe 12 %, cu 12 % and 6 % liquid boron) were 116 and 151.5 in two successive seasons respectively and there are insignificant differences between microelements and untreated cotton plots of some predacious species (Beetles, aphid lion rove beetles and true spider). Tahir and Butt (2009) indicated that abundance and spatial distribution of a spider species significantly depend on the type of management practice in the field.

4. Species richness:

During the two seasons, among the total of 21 species and 9 families were collected (Tables 1 and 2), 13 species of 7 families were recorded in copperal max treatment, 15 species of 8 families in calvin treatment, 13 species of 7 families Potassium silicate treatment, 13

species of 6 families were recorded in Max. growth treatment, 12 species of 8 families were recorded in mix treatment and 13 species of 7 families in control. A total of 6 species had common occurrence in all treatment during the two seasons. Family Eutichuridae was absent in treatments with Potassium silicate and control. Family Thomisidae was absent in treatments with copperal max., potassium silicate, max. growth and control. Family Dictynidae was found only in potassium silicate treatment and control. Also, during two seasons, the highest numbers of individuals recorded in the plot treated with max. growth (90 individuals) and mix (99 individuals) decreased to 39 indiv. in control. These results agreement with (Siemann, 1998), who indicated that fertilizer application increases plant biomass production, supporting high numbers of herbivores as well as detritivores, thus enhancing predator abundance.

5. Frequency and abundance values:

Tables (3 and 4) showed spiders associated with quinoa plants as affected by different fertilizers. In first season, Family Lycosidae and Linyphididae were considered "Constant" (C) in calcivin treatment and control according to Weis Fog system which occupied 66.04 and 54.17% of the collected spiders. While considered "Accessory (ac) and Accidental (A) in the other treatments. Members of *W. fidelis* was "Eudominant" in treatments with calcivin and Max. growth according to Weigmann classification of dominance. However, in the second year, Family Lycosidae and Linyphididae were considered "Constant" (C) in treatments with Potassium silicate and mix. Whereas considered "Accessory (ac) and Accidental (A) in other treatments. Members of *W. fidelis* was "Eudominant"

in treatments with mix. Similar results were reported by (Abd El-Karim *et al.*, 2016) who found that family Lycosidae was considered "constant" in *Calendula* treated with fertilizers with 50.32 and 59.39% in two seasons, respectively. These results agreed with the results obtained by (Shuang-Lin and Bo-Ping, 2006 and Abd El-Karim *et al.*, 2016) who indicated that members of family Lycosidae: ranged between "dominant" and "eudominant" (According to Weigmann classification of dominance).

6. Species diversity:

The biodiversity of spiders in the plots treated is compared using Shannon Wiener "H" and Simpson "S" Indices of diversity (Table 5). In first season, The cover plantation of quinoa in different plots varies in their species richness; the plot treated with max. growth recorded the highest population of total number 59 individuals. Its ecosystem is made of 6 families, 12 genera and 12 species; followed by calcivin that recorded spider population of 53 individuals, belonging to 6 families, 11 genera and 11 species. While the control recorded the least species richness of 24 individuals. While in second season, the plot treated with mix recorded the highest population of total number 69 individuals of 6 families, 8 genera and 8 species. The biodiversity index calculation indicates that (Copperal max. and potassium silicate) and (Copperal max., calcivin and max. growth) were the most diverse; the species richness of spiders in different families and their equitability (Evenness) were higher in two seasons respectively. According to Simpson Index which is a measure of dominance (responsive to changes for the most dominant species), it was found that calcivin (0.30) and max. growth (0.32) in 1st season and mix (0.55) in 2nd season included the highest number

of dominant species. The present results agree with Öberg (2007) who stated that organic practice may add diversity to the soil structure and increase the abundance of prey and in turn the abundance of spiders. The same results were recorded by (Schmidt *et al.*, 2005) as they found that abundance of spiders in organic fields was more than conventionally.

7. Similarity of species

In two seasons 2018 and 2019, community of spiders collected from control (24 and 15 individuals) was lower than those collected from copperal max. treatment (31 and 29 individuals), calcivin treatment (53 and 32 individuals), potassium silicate treatment (26 and 25 individuals), max. growth treatment (59 and 31 individuals) and mix treatment (30 and 69 individuals) respectively. Also, among the 21 species obtained, 11 and 12 species were collected from copperal max. treatment, 11 and 11 species from calcivin treatment, 12 and 10 species from potassium silicate treatment, 12 and 11 species from max. growth treatment, 9 and 8 species from mix treatment and 10 and 9 species from control in two successive seasons. To estimate spider composition of that different microhabitat, Sørensen's quotient of similarity was applied by comparing the number of species and individuals of control apparently with catch one of those treatments. It is concluded that the similarity to control compared by other treatments recorded 66.67 and 47.62% in copperal max, 66.67 and 50% in calcivin, 81.82 and 50% in potassium silicate, 81.82 and 60% in max. growth and 84.21 and 35% in mix in two seasons respectively.

8. Total numbers, dominance and abundance degrees of arthropod pests

and their natural enemies by pitfall trap:

Tables (6 and 7) indicated a total of 3128 individuals in the 1st season and 2676 individuals in the 2nd season were counted from 9 samples on quinoa plants from seedling to maturity by using pitfall trap. The number of individuals was (539 and 490 individuals) in copperal max treatment, (520 and 432 individuals) in calcivin treatment, (660 and 400 individuals) in potassium silicate treatment, (450 and 443 indiv.) in max. growth treatment, (493 and 490 individuals) in mix treatment and (466 and 421 individuals) in control in 2018 and 2019 season, respectively. The dominance and abundance degrees indicated that Collembola, Muscidae, Formicidae, and Spiders recorded the highest dominant and abundant in both seasons. Birkhofer *et al.* (2008) indicated that the application of both organic and inorganic fertilizers to ecosystems has been shown to increase the populations and diversity of soil fauna. These results documented by Salem *et al.* (2012) who found that some predators help in planning Integrated Pest Management (I.P.M.) strategies.

9. Downy Mildew and yield:

9.1. Identification of the pathogen cause downy mildew:

Symptoms of downy mildew on quinoa plants were observed on the lower leaves of plants in the form of necrotic spots on the upper surface and correspondingly grayish black conidiophores bear conidiospores of the pathogen on the lower surface (Table 8). Light microscopy revealed presence of colorless dichotomously branched sporangiophores (2 – 3.2 μ width), slightly curved at the far point bearing hyaline sporangia. Spores are 1deciduous mostly avoid, 11.0 – 15.6 μ 20.0 – 25.5 μ .

dark brownish oospores were observed embedded into leaf tissues. The disease is caused by *peronospora avariabilis* Gaum, formerly *peronospora farinose* F. sp. *chenopodii* Byford (Choi *et al.*, 2010).

9.2. Disease assessment and grain yield:

From Table (8) all treatments were affected by disease incidence where max. growth considered the higher value 43.3 and 41.3% during 2019 and 2020 respectively compared to other treatments. The lowest values occurred with mix treatment where recorded 6.67 and 6.0% during 2019 and 2020 season. Also, the same results were found with disease severity where max. growth 15.23 and 17.67% during 2019 and 2020 respectively and mix recorded 2.47 and 2.63%. Significant differences between all treatments were occurred. Results indicated that The highest value of yield Kg/fed was evident with treatment mix 1711.67 and 1692.67 Kg/fed. while the lowest value recorded in control with 619.33 and 703 Kg/fed. in 2019 and 2020 respectively. Significant differences between all treatments were occurred. These results agreement with Danielsen *et al.* (2003), who found that the most significant disease affecting quinoa cultivation in South America, is downy mildew and reducing the yield up to 33-

58% and even up to 99% in some quinoa fields.

10. Statistical analysis :

Statistical analysis proved that no significant differences were observed between means of treatments in first season and high significant differences between mix treatment and other treatments. These results showed the application on chemicals salts effect of biodiversity of spiders and arthropods. From former results we can conclude that application of chemical salts improves spiders biodiversity and at the same time reduce incidence and severity of downy mildew and increase quinoa yield. These obtained data indicate that use of nutrients can conserve biodiversity in agro ecosystem. These agree with Attwood *et al.* (2008) and Whittingham (2011) who revealed that programmes in numerous countries have attempted to reduce the severity of agriculture's negative influence on biodiversity by paying farmers to reduce management intensity through reduced pesticide and synthetic fertilizer inputs or by converting farms to organic practices.

Table (1) Richness of spider species inhabiting quinoa plants under effects of different fertilizer treatments in 2018-2019 season

Families & taxa names	copperal Max		Calcivin		Potassium silicate		Max. growth		Mix		Control		Σ		Σ	Total	%									
	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀												
Lycosidae																										
<i>Wadicosa fidelis</i>	3	3		2	25		1	1	30	1	1	1	5	9+2▲	57	104	46.64									
<i>Pardosa sp.</i>	1		6	1	4	1+1▲	4		2	5	3	23	0	1	24											
<i>Hogna ferox</i>	2		1		1		1		2	2	2	9	0	0	9											
Theridiidae																										
<i>Enoplognatha gemina</i>	5		5				5			3	1	21	0	0	21	28	12.56									
<i>Kochiura aulica</i>	3		1				1			1	1	1	5	0	6											
<i>Eryopsis sp.</i>			1							1	1	1	0	0	1											
<i>Theridion sp.</i>																										
Philodromidae																										
<i>Thanatus albini</i>						1				1	3	3	2	0	5	5	2.24									
Linyphiidae																										
<i>Mermessus denticulatus</i>	2		2	1			2			4	2	3	1	1	22	68	30.49									
<i>Prinerigone vagans</i>	1						2			2	1	5	0	0	5											
<i>Erigone sp.</i>							2			2	1	3	0	0	3											
<i>Sengletus extricatus</i>	7		4				5	1	1	5	1	33	2	3	38											
Gnaphosidae																										
<i>Zelotes sp.</i>		1											0	1	1	7	3.14									
<i>Micaria dives</i>														0	0											
<i>Drassodes pubescens</i>					1		1			2	1	4	0	2	6											
Eutichuridae																										
<i>Cheiracanthium isiacum</i>		1											1	0	1	2	0.90									
Salticidae																										
<i>Phlegra flavipes</i>	2			1	1								4	1	1	7	3.14									
<i>Pellenes sp.</i>														0	0											
<i>Heliphannes sp.</i>													1	0	1											
Thomisidae																										
<i>Xysticus sp.</i>			1										1	0	0	1	0.45									
Dictynidae																										
<i>Lathys sp.</i>													0	0	0	0	0.45									
Total	23	7	1	21	4	28	20	2	4	25	3	31	22	5	3	22	5	3	20	3	1	131	24	68	223	
	31		53		26 + 1 Egg Sac		59		30 + 1 Egg Sac		24		223													

▲ = Egg sac

Table (2) Richness of spider species inhabiting quinoa plants under effects of different fertilizer treatments in 2019-2020 season

Families & taxa names	copperal Max		Calcivin		Potassium silicate		Max. growth		Mix		Control		Σ		Σ	Total	%					
	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀	♂	♀								
Lycosidae																						
<i>Wadicosa fidelis</i>	1	2	1	2	2	2	1	3+1▲	1	4	45			6	13+1▲	46	90	44.78				
<i>Pardosa sp.</i>	3		6		2		5		3			1		20	0	20						
<i>Hogna ferox</i>	1				2		1					1		4	1	0						
Theridiidae																						
<i>Enoplognatha gemina</i>	4		3		5		5		2					19	0	0	22	10.95				
<i>Kochiura aulica</i>		1			1									1	1	0						
<i>Eryopsis sp.</i>		1												0		0						
<i>Theridion sp.</i>														0	1	0						
Philodromidae																	7	3.48				
<i>Thanatus albini</i>	3	1	1		1							1		6	1	0						
Linyphiidae																	54	26.87				
<i>Mermessus denticulatus</i>	1	2	2	2			3	1	2			1		9	4	1						
<i>Primerigone vagans</i>		1	2	1	1		1							4	2	0						
<i>Erigone sp.</i>							1							1	0	0						
<i>Sengletus extricatus</i>	5	1	1	3	2	6	2	1	2	7	2	2	1	23	7	3						
Gnaphosidae																	15	7.46				
<i>Zelotes sp.</i>							2					3	1	5	1	0						
<i>Micaria dives</i>				1										0	0	1						
<i>Drassodes pubescens</i>			2				1	2				1	1	3	3	2						
Entychuridae																	6	2.99				
<i>Cheiracanthium isiacum</i>	1			2			1	1		1				2	0	4						
Salticidae																	5	2.49				
<i>Phlegra flavipes</i>	1			1	1				1					3	0	1						
<i>Pellenes sp.</i>												1		0	1	0						
<i>Heliphannes sp.</i>																0						
Thomisidae																	1	0.50				
<i>Xysticus sp.</i>									1					0	1	0						
Dictynidae																	1	0.50				
<i>Lathys sp.</i>												1		0	1	0						
Total	20	8	1	18	8	6	21	3	1	23	5	3	16	7	46	8	6	1	106	24	58	201
		29		32			25		69		15			201								

▲ = Egg sac

Table (4) Dominance-frequency relationship of spider communities associated with quinoa plants affected by different fertilizers during 2019-2020

Families & taxa names	Copperal Max			Calcivin			Potassium silicate			Max. growth			Mix			Control											
	Total	Sp%	Dom.	Frq.	F.%	Dom.	Frq.	F.%	Dom.	Frq.	F.%	Dom.	Frq.	F.%	Dom.	Frq.	F.%	Dom.									
Lycosidae																											
<i>Wadicosa fidelis</i>	3	10.34	D	3	9.38	sd	4	16	R	32.00	ac	5	16.1	D	35.48	ac	50	72.5	E	76.81	C	1	6.67	sd	13.33	A	
<i>Pardosa sp.</i>	3	10.34	D	6	18.75	D	2	8	sd			5	16.1	D			3	4.35	R			1	6.67	sd			
<i>Hogna ferox</i>	1	3.45	R				2	8	sd			1	3.23	R								1	6.67	sd			
Theridiidae																											
<i>Enoplognatha gemina</i>	4	13.79	D	3	9.38	sd	5	20	D			5	16.1	D			2	2.9	R								
<i>Kochiura aulica</i>	1	3.45	R				1	4	R	24.00	A						1										
<i>Egyropris sp.</i>																											
<i>Theridion sp.</i>	1	3.45	R																								
Philodromidae																											
<i>Thanatus albini</i>	4	13.79	D	1	3.13	R	1	4	R	4.00	A						1					1	6.67	sd	6.67	A	
Linyphiidae																											
<i>Memessus denticulatus</i>	3	10.34	D	4	12.50	D						4	12.9	D			2	2.9	R				1	6.67	sd	26.67	ac
<i>Prinerigone vagans</i>	1	3.45	R	3	9.38	sd	1	4	R	32.00	C	1	3.23	R	25.81	ac	1										
<i>Erigone sp.</i>																											
<i>Sengletus extricatus</i>	6	20.69	D	6	18.75	D	7	28	D			2	6.45	sd			9	13	D				3	20	D		
Gnaphosidae																											
<i>Zelotes sp.</i>																											
<i>Micaria dives</i>				1	3.13	R				4.00	A						2	6.45	sd				4	26.7	D	40.00	ac
<i>Drassodes pubescens</i>				2	6.25	sd						3	9.68	sd									2	13.3	D		
Eutichuridae																											
<i>Cheiracanthium sp.</i>	1	3.45	R	2	6.25	sd						2	6.45	sd			1	1.45	R				1	1.45	R	1.45	A
Salticidae																											
<i>Philegra flavipes</i>	1	3.45	R	1	3.13	R						1	4	R	4.00	A							1	1.45	R	1.45	A
<i>Pellenes sp.</i>																											
<i>Heliphannes sp.</i>																											
Thomisidae																											
<i>Xysticus sp.</i>																											
Dictynidae																											
<i>Lathys sp.</i>																											
Total	29			32			25					31					69					15					

Frequency (abundance), by Weis Fog

> 50 % = Constant (C)
 25 - 50 % = Accessory (ac)
 > 25 % = Accidental (A)

Dominance, by Weigmann

> 30 % = Eudominant (E)
 10 - 30 % = Dominant (D)
 5 - 10 % = Subdominant (sd)
 1 - 5 % = Recedent (R)
 > 1 % = Subrecedent (Sr)

Table (5): Estimation of Shannon-Wiener and Simpson Indices of spider diversity two seasons

	Copperal Max	Calcivin	Potassium silicate	Max. growth	Mix	Control
First Season, 2018-2019						
Shannon-Wiener Index	2.15	1.69	2.14	1.67	2.03	2.06
Simpson Index	0.14	0.30	0.16	0.32	0.15	0.15
Second season, 2019-2020						
Shannon-Wiener Index	2.27	2.22	2.02	2.24	1.02	2.03
Simpson Index	0.12	0.12	0.16	0.12	0.55	0.16

Table (6) Dominance and abundance (D & A) of arthropod pests and their natural enemies collected from quinoa plantation using pitfall traps during 2018-2019 season, Fayoum Governorate.

Order	Family	Copperal Max		Calcivin		Potassium silicate		Max. growth		Mix		Control		Total						
		D%	A%	D%	A%	D%	A%	D%	A%	D%	A%	D%	A%							
Coleoptera	Carabidae	9	1.67	44.44	8	1.54	66.67	10	1.52	44.44	11	2.44	66.67	9	1.83	55.56	7	1.50	66.67	54
	Staphylinidae	2	0.37	11.11	3	0.58	22.22	4	0.61	22.22	4	0.89	33.33	1	0.20	11.11	1	0.21	11.11	15
	Coccinellidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.20	11.11	0	0	0
Collembola	Collembola	74	13.73	100	97	18.65	100	106	16.06	100	99	22.00	100	72	14.60	100	107	22.96	100	555
	Muscidae	141	26.16	88.89	122	23.46	77.78	98	14.85	66.67	79	17.56	66.67	104	21.10	66.67	78	16.74	100	622
Heteroptera	Miridae	0	0	0	1	0.19	11.11	0	0	0	1	0.22	11.11	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Aleyrodidae	1	0.19	11.11	0	0.00	0.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.21	11.11
Homoptera	Aphididae	13	2.41	55.56	24	4.62	77.78	29	4.39	77.78	8	1.78	33.33	11	2.23	44.44	9	1.93	44.44	94
	Cicadellidae	3	0.56	33.33	5	0.96	33.33	3	0.45	33.33	9	2.00	44.44	1	0.20	11.11	6	1.29	33.33	27
	Formicidae	238	44.16	100	191	36.73	100	359	54.39	100	153	34.00	100	246	49.90	100	208	44.64	88.89	1395
Hymenoptera	Insect parasitoids	5	0.93	33.33	6	1.15	44.44	8	1.21	44.44	7	1.56	55.56	6	1.22	33.33	7	1.50	33.33	39
	Parasitoid wasps	1	0.19	11.11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
Orthoptera	Acrididae	2	0.37	22.22	0	0.00	0.00	1	0.15	11.11	1	0.22	11.11	0	0	0	1	0.21	0.041	5
	Gryllidae	1	0.19	11.11	1	0.19	11.11	3	0.45	11.11	0	0.00	0.00	0	0	0	0	0	0	5
Thysanoptera	Thripidae	3	0.56	33.33	3	0.58	11.11	3	0.45	22.22	6	1.33	44.44	1	0.20	11.11	8	1.72	44.44	24
	Labiduridae	2	0.37	22.22	1	0.19	11.11	1	0.15	11.11	1	0.22	11.11	1	0.20	11.11	1	0.21	11.11	7
Dermapter	Lepidoptera	4	0.74	33.33	0	0	0	4	0.61	22.22	7	1.56	33.33	2	0.41	22.22	6	1.29	22.22	23
	Isopoda	0	0	0	2	0.38	22.22	0	0	0	1	0.22	11.11	1	0.20	11.11	1	0.21	11.11	5
Myriapoda	Myriapoda	8	1.48	33.33	3	0.58	22.22	5	0.76	33.33	4	0.89	33.33	7	1.42	44.44	1	0.21	11.11	28
	Spiders	31	5.75	88.89	53	10.19	100	26	3.94	77.78	59	13.11	100	30	6.09	88.89	24	5.15	77.78	223
Total	Snails	1	0.19	11.11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1
	Total	539			520			660			450			493			466			3128

Table (7) Dominance and abundance (D & A) of arthropod pests and their natural enemies collected from quinoa plantation using pitfall traps during 2019–2020 season, Fayoum Governorate.

Order	Family	Copperal Max		Calcivin		Potassium silicate		Max. growth		Mix		Control		Total						
		D %	A %	D %	A %	D %	A %	D %	A %	D %	A %	D %	A %							
Coleoptera	Carabidae	11	2.24	44.44	8	1.85	55.56	13	3.25	88.89	9	2.03	55.56	15	3.06	66.67	13	3.09	55.56	69
	Staphylinidae	6	1.22	33.33	2	0.46	22.22	1	0.25	11.11	5	1.13	33.33	3	0.61	22.22	1	0.24	11.11	18
	Coccinellidae	3	0.61	22.22	1	0.23	11.11	1	0.25	11.11	6	1.35	33.33	1	0.20	11.11	3	0.71	11.11	15
Collembola	Collembola	78	15.92	100	113	26.16	100	79	19.75	100	111	25.06	33.33	81	16.53	100	105	24.94	100	567
	Muscidae	163	33.27	88.89	91	21.06	66.67	128	32.00	33.33	46	10.38	88.89	119	24.29	77.78	16	3.80	66.67	563
Heteroptera	Miridae	0	0	0	1	0.23	11.11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	1	0.24	11.11	2
Homoptera	Aleyrodidae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
	Aphididae	6	1.22	33.33	8	1.85	33.33	3	0.75	33.33	10	2.26	55.56	12	2.45	55.56	4	0.95	22.22	43
	Cicadellidae	3	0.61	22.22	5	1.16	22.22	2	0.50	22.22	4	0.90	44.44	1	0.20	11.11	2	0.48	22.22	17
	Formicidae	159	32.45	100	129	29.86	88.89	137	34.25	100	187	42.21	88.89	163	33.27	100	226	53.68	100	1001
Hymenoptera	Insect parasitoids	10	2.04	55.56	9	2.08	33.33	5	1.25	33.33	7	1.58	66.67	5	1.02	33.33	6	1.43	44.44	42
	Parasitoid wasps	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0
Orthoptera	Acrididae	0	0	0	2	0.46	11.11	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2
	Gryllidae	1	0.20	11.11	1	0.23	11.11	0	0	0	1	0.23	11.11	0	0.00	0.00	1	0.24	11.11	4
	Thripidae	4	0.82	33.33	7	1.62	44.44	0	0	0	10	2.26	22.22	4	0.82	33.33	3	0.71	22.22	28
Dermapter	Labiduridae	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.45	11.11	0	0	0	4	0.95	33.33	6
	Lepidoptera	5	1.02	33.33	9	2.08	44.44	1	0.25	11.11	4	0.90	33.33	5	1.02	22.22	9	2.14	44.44	33
Isopoda	Isopoda	0	0.00	0.00	2	0.46	22.22	0	0	0	0	0	0	2	0.41	22.22	1	0.24	11.11	5
	Myriapoda	9	1.84	44.44	10	2.31	55.56	5	1.25	22.22	10	2.26	55.56	6	1.22	55.56	11	2.61	33.33	51
Spiders	Spiders	29	5.92	100	32	7.41	100	25	6.25	100	31	7.00	88.89	69	14.08	66.67	15	3.56	77.78	201
	Snails	3	0.61	11.11	2	0.46	22.22	0	0	0	0	0	0	4	0.82	11.11	0	0	0	9
Total	Total	490			432			400			443		490				421			2676

Table (8): effect of treatments on incidence and severity of downy mildew, biodiversity of spiders and grain yield of quinoa plants

Treatments	Spider		Grain yield		Assessment of diseases				% Reduction			
	2019		2020		Disease incidence %		Disease severity %		2019		2020	
					2019	2020	2019	2020				
Copperal Max	3.56a	3.22b	1564b	1613.33b	11.67e	14.33e	3d	4e	88.33	85.67		
Calcivin	6.22a	3.56ab	1402e	1491.67e	31.67c	35c	7.13c	12.07c	68.33	65.00		
Potassium silicate	2.78a	2.78b	1518.33c	1581.33c	20.33d	24.67d	4.60d	6.47d	79.67	75.33		
Max. growth	6.67a	3.22b	1433d	1502.67d	43.33b	41.33b	15.23b	17.67b	56.67	58.67		
Mix. (all treatments)	2.89a	7.67a	1711.67a	1692.67a	6.67f	6f	2.47d	2.63e	93.33	94.00		
Control	2.67	1.89b	619.33f	703f	100a	100a	68a	72.17a	0.00	0.00		
LSD (5%)	5.12	4.24	5.01	2.52	2.34	2.34	2.2	1.52				

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**Insecticidal , biochemical efficacy and digestive enzymes of isolated endophytic fungi on
Agrotis ipsilon larvae (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae)**

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Abstract:

The black cutworm *Agrotis ipsilon* (Hufnagel) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is a worldwide pest of different economic crops. The aim of the present work is to study the effect of five isolated endophytic fungi *Aspergillus flavus* MRDS 301, *Curvularia lunata* MRDS 302, *Chaetomium madrasense* MRDS 303, *Alternaria alternate* MRDS 304 and *Aspergillus flavus* MRDS 305 against the 3rd larval instar of *A. ipsilon* , to investigate the cumulative percentage mortality of the larvae was treated with five isolated endophytic fungi can be arranged according to the most effective compounds 50, 58.88, 45.55, 42.22 and 40%, respectively. The results showed that biochemical effect on the metabolites (Total carbohydrates, total protein and free amino acids) and digestive enzymes activity (Amylase , invertase, proteases and lipase), the total carbohydrate content in *A. ipsilon* treated larvae was decreased for the larvae fed for 3day on treated leaves with all isolated endophytic fungi at concentration 10⁷ spores /mL sterilized water. While *A. flavus* MRDS 301 and *C. lunata* MRDS 302 caused decreases in proteins and free amino acid percentage compared to control. A significant reduction in α -Amylase, invertase, proteases and lipase activated were observed in most treated relative to control. In other hand, larvae treated with *C. madrasense* MRDS 303 and *A. alternate* MRDS 304 recorded an increase in invertase, proteases and lipase activities compared to control.

Introduction

The black cutworm *Agrotis ipsilon* (Hufnagel) (Lepidoptera: Noctuidae) is one of the most severe insect pests in Egypt, this noctuid is polyphagous and attacks a large number of field and vegetable crops (Abo El-Ghar *et al.*, 1996). The growers usually use the conventional insecticides, especially organophosphates, in controlling this pest. However, the use of pesticides has resulted in

environmental contamination (Frank *et al.*, 1990) negative effects on non-target organisms (Franz, 1974). One very exciting area in mycology involves the study of fungal endophytes. The term “endophyte” was coined by De Bary (1884) and is used to define fungi or bacteria that occur inside asymptomatic plant tissues. Fungal endophytes are ubiquitous and are dominated by Ascomycota (Arnold and Lutzoni, 2007). Different genera of fungal

entomopathogens have been reported as naturally occurring fungal endophytes, and it has been shown that it is possible to inoculate plants with fungal entomopathogens, making them endophytic. Their mode of action against insects appears to be due to antibiosis or feeding deterrence. Research aimed at understanding the fungal ecology of entomopathogenic fungi, and their role as fungal endophytes, could lead to a new paradigm on how to successfully use these organisms in biological control programs (Vega, 2008).

The present work aimed to investigate insecticidal and biochemical efficacy of five isolated endophytic fungi (*Aspergillus flavus* MRDS 301, *Curvularia lunata* MRDS 302, *Chaetomium madrasense* MRDS 303, *Alternaria alternate* MRDS 304 and *Aspergillus flavus* MRDS 305) against the 3rd larval instar of *A. ipsilon*.

Materials and methods

1. Isolation of endophytes:

The isolations of endophytic fungi from maize hybrids were carried out according to Parsa *et al.* (2013) with some modification by El-Lebody *et al.* (2021).

2. Insect culture:

Susceptible strain of the black cutworms, *A. ipsilon* was reared on castor leaves away from any insecticidal contamination in the laboratory of Pest Physiology Department, Plant Protection Research Institute, Agricultural Research Center, Giza, Egypt under controlled laboratory conditions at $25 \pm 2^\circ\text{C}$ and $65 \pm 5\%$ RH.

3. Insecticidal activity:

The isolated endophytic fungi were tested individually against *A. ipsilon* 3rd instar larvae to investigate its insecticidal activity. The castor leaves (*Ricinus communis*) were washed, dried and used as food for *A. ipsilon* larvae. The isolated endophytic fungi at

concentration 10^7 spores /mL were placed on the surface of the leaves and left for a few minutes to dry. Each *A. ipsilon* 3rd instar larvae were transferred singly in small vials (3.5diam, 8cm high) with treated leaves. Castor leaves treated with sterilized distilled water were used as control. Three replicates (10 larvae each) were used for each treatment. Three days post-treatment, dead larvae were counted, and alive ones were transferred to small vials containing untreated castor leaves and renewed as needed. Dead larvae were recorded at 3, 6, 9 and 12 interval days.

4. Biochemical studies:

For the biochemical studies 3rd instar larvae were treated as previously described (30 larvae / three replicates) with the isolated endophytic fungi at concentration 10^7 spores /mL for 3 days. Ten live larvae per treatment and control were randomly selected for the biochemical analysis.

5. Preparation of insects for biochemical analysis:

The insects were prepared as described by Amin (1998). They were homogenized in distilled water (50 mg of larvae /5ml sterilized distilled water). Homogenates were centrifuged at 8000 rpm for 15 min at 2°C in a refrigerated centrifuge. The deposits were discarded and the supernatants, can be stored at least one week without appreciable loss of activity when stored at 5°C .

6. Biochemical analysis:

Total carbohydrate was estimated according to Dubois *et al.* (1956). Total protein content was determined according to the method of Bradford (1976). Total amino acids were assayed according to the method described by Lee and Takabashi (1966). Total carbohydrate was extracted and prepared for assay according to Crompton and Birt (1967). Amylase and invertase activities were assayed according to the method described by Ishaaya and Swiriski (1976). Starch and

sucrose was used as substrates for amylase and invertase, respectively. Proteolytic activity was measured as described by Tatchell *et al.* (1972), Lipase activity was determined by a slight modification of the procedure of Tahoun and Abdel-Ghaffar (1986).

7. Statistical analysis:

The data were statistically analysed by means of analysis of variance (ANOVA) (Tukey's test) at $P < 0.05$ using IBM® "SPSS" STATISTICS Ver.26 software, most of the results were expressed in percentage, although actual numbers were used for statistical tests. Results were recorded as mean \pm standard deviation (SD).

Results and discussion

1. Insecticidal activity:

The accumulated mortality and latent effect of isolated endophytic fungi from the maize hybrids at concentration 10^7 spores /mL against the 3rd larval instar of *A. ipsilon* were presented in Table (1) revealed that *A. flavus* MRDS 301 recorded high mortality percentage (14.44%) and *C. lunata* MRDS 302 recorded (10%) where *C. madrasense* MRDS 303 and *A. alternata* MRDS 304 recorded (5.55%) and *A. flavus* MRDS 305 was

lowest insecticidal potentials (2.22%) after 3 days of treatment. After 6 days of treatment, *C. lunata* MRDS 302, *A. flavus* MRDS 301, *A. alternata* MRDS 304, *C. madrasense* MRDS 303 and *A. flavus* MRDS 305 were (27.77, 24.44, 22.22, 17.77 and 15.55%), respectively. After 9 days were (31.11, 27.77, 2.22, 18.88 and 15.55%), respectively. The obtained data also showed that after 12 days of treatment, insecticidal activity arranged according the highest mortality percentage for *C. lunata* MRDS 302, *A. flavus* MRDS 301, *C. madrasense* MRDS 303, *A. alternata* MRDS 304, and *A. flavus* MRDS 305 were (58.88, 50, 45.55, 42.22 and 45.55%), respectively. It was noticed that the mortality percentages of all treatments increased lateral with time. The obtain result agree with El-Shershaby (2010) as slight toxicity by testing cappariss extracts on the black cutworm, *A. ipsilon* and El-Lebody *et al.* (2021) noticed that the mortality percentages of all treatments increased lateral with time. After 14 days of treatment, latent pathogenicity ranged between 2.5% to 25% for *C. madrasense* MRDS 303 and *A. flavus* MRDS 301, respectively.

Table (1): Insecticidal effects of endophytic fungi of maize hybrids against the 3rd larval instar of *Agrotis ipsilon*.

Endophytic fungi	Days			
	3	6	9	12
<i>Chaetomium madrasense</i> MRDS 303	5.55%	17.77%	18.88%	45.55%
<i>Alternaria alternate</i> MRDS 304	5.55%	22.22%	22.22%	42.22%
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> MRDS 305	2.22%	15.55%	15.55%	40%
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> MRDS 301	14.44%	24.44%	27.77%	50%
<i>Curvularia lunata</i> MRDS 302	10%	27.77%	31.11%	58.88%
Control	2.22%	3.33%	4.44%	5.55%

2. Biochemical analysis:

Carbohydrates are of vital importance since they can be utilized by the insects' body for production of energy or conversion of lipids or proteins (Fahmy, 2017). That explains the total carbohydrate content in *A.*

ipsilon larvae was decreased for the larvae fed on treating leaves with the isolated endophytic fungi at concentration 10^7 spores /ml for 3 days (Table 2). Under stress conditions, more sugars might be metabolized to meet out the energy expenses. This

could be the reason for the carbohydrate level depletion in the treated insects (Fahmy , 2008)., that explain the increased in proteins and free amino

acid percentage in the *A. ipsilon* larvae treated with *C. madrasense* MRDS 303, *A. alternata* MRDS 304 and *A. flavus* MRDS 305 compared to controls.

Table (2): Effect of Endophytic fungi on the Metabolites of *Agrotis ipsilon* 3rd larval instar.

Endophytic fungi	Total proteins (mg/g.b.wt)		Total carbohydrates (mg/g.b.wt)		Free amino acids(ug alanine/g.b.wt)	
	Mean ± SD	% Change to control	Mean ± SD	% Change to control	Mean ± SD	% Change to control
<i>Chaetomium madrasense</i> MRDS 303	22.13± 1.52 a	47.53	5.24±0.26 b	-8.23	61.9±1.73 a	16.01
<i>Alternaria alternata</i> MRDS 304	21± 1.80 a	40	5.08±0.13 b	-11.03	63±2.29 a	18.07
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> MRDS 305	16.23± 0.58 b	8.2	4.85±0.19 b	-15.06	55.73±1.48 b	4.44
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> MRDS 301	12.76± 0.81 c	-14.93	3.34±0.16 c	-41.51	40.96±1.74 c	-23.24
<i>Curvularia lunata</i> MRDS 302	11.73±0.49 c	-21.8	5.65±0.17 a	-1.05	43.16±2.02 c	-19.12
Control	15± 1.05 b	0	5.71±0.33 a	0	53.36±4.56 b	0
LSD	2.05		0.39		4.5	
F	41.22		45.65		40.15	
P	.0001***		.0001***		.0001***	

Carbohydrates are of vital importance since they can be utilized by the insects' body for production of energy or conversion of lipids or proteins (Fahmy, 2017). That explains the total carbohydrate content in *A. ipsilon* larvae was decreased for the larvae fed on treating leaves with the isolated endophytic fungi at concentration 10^7 spores /ml for 3 days (Table 2). Under stress conditions, more sugars might be metabolized to meet out the energy expenses. This could be the reason for the carbohydrate level depletion in the treated insects (Fahmy , 2008)., that explain the increased in proteins and free amino acid percentage in the *A. ipsilon* larvae treated with *C.*

madrasense MRDS 303, *A. alternata* MRDS 304 and *A. flavus* MRDS 305 compared to controls.

Metabolism of carbohydrates is controlled mainly by carbohydrate hydrolyzing enzymes. In Table (3) there is a significant reduction in digestive enzyme amylase and Invertase in most treatment of larvae feeding on endophytic fungi relative to control. Amylases hydrolyze starch into the monosaccharides, glucose, and fructose and secreted by larva salivary glands and midgut (Ribeiro *et al.*, 2000). Invertases cleave sucrose into the mono saccharides, glucose, and fructose and are secreted and worked in the gut of the larvae (Heil *et al.*,

2005). The final product of carbohydrate metabolism is glucose, the increase of these enzymes during the larval stage suggested that these enzymes degrade carbohydrates to glucose for chitin build-up (Wyatt, 1967). In this study isolated endophytic fungi decreased the activity of digestive enzymes. So, degradation of carbohydrates also decreases. This leads to disturbance in chitin building

and the failure of the molting process. In recently, attention has been focused on the idea of using digestive enzyme inhibitors that affect the growth and development of pest species. Inhibitors of insect amylases and proteases obtained have been demonstrated to be important in the control of insect pests (Franco *et al.*, 2000 and Mehrabadi *et al.*, 2012).

Table (3): Effect of Endophytic fungi on the digestive enzymes of *Agrotis ipsilon* 3rd larval instar.

Endophytic fungi	Invertase (ug glucose/min/g.b.wt)		Amylase (ug glucose/min/g.b.wt)		Proteases (ug D,L alanine/min/g.b.wt)		Lipase (mU/g.b.wt)	
	Mean ± SD	% Change to control	Mean ± SD	% Change to control	Mean ± SD	% Change to control	Mean± SD	% Change to control
<i>Chaetomium madrasense</i> MRDS 303	272.33±7.76 a	8.21	119.33±6.65 c	-37.85	56.5±3.04a	37.37	108.33± 4.50bc	4.84
<i>Alternaria alternate</i> MRDS 304	257.33±10.59 b	2.25	109.33±8.38 c	-43.06	50.63±2.55 b	23.09	126.66±5.68 a	22.58
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> MRDS 305	202±5.29 d	-19.73	150±9.64 b	-21.87	31.9±1.85 d	-22.44	74± 5.29 e	-28.38
<i>Aspergillus flavus</i> MRDS 301	144.66±8.96 e	-42.52	108.33±5.68 c	-43.58	22.96±3.32 e	-44.18	93.66± 4.04d	-9.35
<i>Curvularia lunata</i> MRDS 302	238.33±3.78 c	-5.30	146±7 b	-23.96	36.3±2 .28 cd	-11.74	114.66± 6.50b	10.96
Control	251.66±10.40 bc	0	192±13 a	0	41.13±4.56 c	0	103.33± 3.78 c	0
LSD	14.59		15.54		5.47		9.01	
F	99.11		40.65		48.02		38.69	
P	.0001***		.0001***		.0001***		.0001***	

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- Negotiation research spans many disciplines (Abd-Rabou, 1996).
- This result was later contradicted (Simmons and Abd-Rabou, 2009).
- This effect has been widely studied (Abd-Rabou, 1998; Simmons *et al.*, 2002; Evans and Abd-Rabou, 2005 and Abd-Rabou *et al.*, 2005).

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Reference list entries should be alphabetized by the last names of the first author of each work.

Journal article

Abd-Rabou, S. (1998): The efficacy of indigenous parasitoids in the biological control of *Siphoninus phillyreae* (Homoptera: Aleyrodidae) on pomegranate in Egypt. Pan-Pacific Entomologists, 74 (3): 169-173.

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Abd-Rabou, S. and Simmons, A. M. (2012): *Bemisia tabaci* (Hemiptera: Aleyrodidae) whitefly as a pest in Egypt. Advances In Agricultural Research In Egypt, 10 (1): 1-82.

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